

GLOBAL RESEARCH JOURNAL OF BUSINESS MANAGEMENT

VOL. 4, NO. 1: JUNE 2024

**ISSN PRINT: 2811-1710
ISSN ONLINE: 2811-1729**

**ASSOCIATION OF MANAGEMENT & SOCIAL
SCIENCES RESEARCHERS OF NIGERIA
(AMSSRN)**

**GLOBAL RESEARCH
JOURNAL OF
BUSINESS
MANAGEMENT
(GRJBM)**

Volume 4, No. 1: June 2024

A Publication of the
**Association of Management and Social
Sciences Researchers of Nigeria (AMSSRN)**

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15656985

Print ISSN: 2 8 1 1 - 1 7 1 0
Online ISSN: 2 8 1 1 - 1 7 2 9

Online Access:

<https://journals.amssr.org/grjbm/category/grjbm/volume-4/vol-4-issue-1/>

ABOUT THE JOURNAL

The *Global Research Journal of Business Management (GRJBM)* is a publication of the Association of Management and Social Sciences Researchers of Nigeria (AMSSRN). It is a peer-reviewed journal published real-time online and two times annually in hardcopy, focusing on cutting-edge research and practical solutions in business management and related disciplines.

Scope

GRJBM invites research articles from a broad spectrum of topics, including but not limited to organizational behavior, strategic management, financial management, human resource management, entrepreneurship, and the impact of technology on business processes.

Vision

To be a global leader in fostering scholarly debates and disseminating high-quality, timely, and impactful research on contemporary business management issues.

Mission

To continuously provide an intellectually stimulating platform for academics, practitioners, and policymakers to share insights, drive innovation, and contribute to the advancement of business management practices worldwide.

EDITORIAL PREFACE

We are pleased to present Volume 4, Issue 1 of the *Global Research Journal of Business Management (GRJBM)*, a publication of the Association of Management and Social Sciences Researchers of Nigeria (AMSSRN). As a trusted platform for the dissemination of impactful research, GRJBM continues to deliver high-quality, peer-reviewed articles that address contemporary challenges and opportunities in the realm of business management.

This issue features an engaging collection of articles that examine critical themes. Together, these studies reflect the journal's commitment to advancing knowledge and informing practice within Nigeria and beyond.

We are deeply grateful to our contributors for their insightful work and to our reviewers and editorial team for their dedication to maintaining the high standards of GRJBM. The unwavering support of AMSSRN has also been instrumental in the continued success of this journal.

We trust that the articles in this issue will stimulate meaningful discussions and provide actionable insights for researchers, practitioners, and policymakers.

Dr. N. H. Akpanabia

Editor

Prof. Yusuf Zaoka

Editor-in-Chief

ADVISORY BOARD

1. **Prof. Vincent A. Onodugo:** Faculty of Business Administration, University of Nigeria, Nsukka.
2. **Prof. Prince Famous Izedomie:** Department of Accounting, University of Benin, Edo State.
3. **Prof. Tankiso Moloi:** University of Johannesburg, South Africa.
4. **Prof. Godwin Emmanuel Oyedokun:** Department of Management and Accounting, Lead City University, Ibadan.
5. **Prof. Ile Nobert:** Department of Business Administration, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Nigeria.
6. **Prof. Austin U. Nweze:** Rector, Institute of Management & Technology, Enugu State.
7. **Prof. Ezeabasili Vincent:** Department of, Chukwu Emeka Odumegwu University, Igbariam.
8. **Prof. Ado Ahmed:** Department of Management and Accounting, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University, Bauchi.
9. **Prof. Uche Uwaleke:** Department of Management and Accounting, Nasarawa State University, Keffi,
10. **Prof. T. O. Enudu:** Department of Business Administration, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Nigeria.
11. **Prof. Francis Emeni:** Department of Accounting, University of Benin, Edo State.
12. **Prof. Chike Nwoha:** Department of Accountancy, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu.
13. **Prof. Uche Ugwuanyi:** Department of Accountancy, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu.
14. **Prof. Adanma Eyisi:** Micheal Okpara University, Umudike, Abia State.
15. **Prof. Emmanuel Akpan:** Department of Management and Accounting, Federal University, Otuoke, Bayelsa State.
16. **Associate Prof. Adonai Okonkwo:** Department of Business Administration, Enugu State University of Science and Technology.
17. **Associate Prof. Njogo Bibian:** Bells University, Abeokuta.
18. **Prof. Uche Lucy Onyekwelu:** Department of Accountancy, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, ESUT.
19. **Prof. Aderemi Kabiru Adeyemo:** Lead City University, Ibadan.
20. **Prof. Muhammad Liman Muhammad:** Bayero University, Kano State.
21. **Prof. Ifeoma Mary Okwo:** Enugu State University of Science and Technology.
22. **Prof. Enudu Titus:** Enugu State University of Science and Technology.
23. **Prof. Vitalis Chukwuma Onah:** Charisma University, British West Indies.
24. **Associate Prof. Joseph Achua:** Central Bank of Nigeria, Abuja.
25. **Associate Prof. Israel Omesi:** Ignatius Ajuru University Port-Harcourt.
26. **Dr. Blaize Igiebor:** Central Bank of Nigeria.
27. **Dr. Kennedy Modugu:** HCT Business School, Dubai, United Arab Emirates.
28. **Dr. Nobert Osemeka:** Liverpool Business School, England, United Kingdom.
29. **Dr. Domnic Erah:** Central Bank of Nigeria.
30. **Dr. Ebere Emmanuel Ozioko:** C4 Consulting Nigeria.
31. **Dr. Isokari Francis Ololo:** Questman's Synergistics Limited Abuja.
32. **Dr. Godwin Ogurube:** Nigerian Deposit Insurance Corporation, Abuja.
33. **Dr. Mary Kehinde Salawu:** University of Johannesburg, South Africa.
34. **Dr. Ada Mac-Ozigbo:** National Open University of Nigeria, Abuja.

EDITORIAL BOARD

Editor –in – Chief	Prof. Yusuf Zaoka
Editor	N. H. Akpanabia, PhD
Associate Editors	
Orga Josephine, PhD	Department of Business Administration, ESUT
Onuoha Charity, PhD	Department of Business Administration, ESUT
Ezuh, Gideon, PhD	Department of Business Administration, ESUT
Ajide Folarunshun, PhD, FAMSSRN	Department of Economics, UNILORIN
Leonard Amaefule, PhD, FAMSSRN	Department of Accountancy, IMSU
Ijeoma Orjiakor, PhD, FAMSSRN	Ijeoma Orjiakor, PhD, FAMSSRN
Elias Agbo, PhD, FAMSSRN	Department of Accounting & Finance, GO-UNI
Chukwuebuka Innocent Nnubia, PhD, FAMSSRN	Department of Accountancy, UNIZIK
Eunice Okpalajiego, PhD, FAMSSRN	Department of Economics, GO-UNI
Rachael Iliemena, PhD, FAMSSRN	Department of Accountancy, IMSU
Tony Onotja, PhD, FAMSSRN	Department of Accountancy, BSU
Ann Nwakaego Duru, PhD, FAMSSRN	Department of Accountancy, ESUT
Bertram Agu, PhD, FAMSSRN	Department of Banking & Finance, ESUT
Chinelo Obiekwe, PhD, FAMSSRN	Department of Banking & Finance, MOU
Seini Odudu Abu, PhD	Department of Accounting, Federal University Dutsin-Ma
Uchenna Onyeamaechi, PhD	Department of Management, Abia State University

LIST OF CONTRIBUTORS

1. **Abonyi Jonas Uchenna:** Department of Public Administration, Institute of Management Technology, Enugu, Nigeria
2. **Anikeze Nnaemeka Hillary, PhD:** Department of Public Administration, Faculty of Management Science, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu, Nigeria
3. **Anukwe Grace Ifeoma:** Department of Marketing, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu, Nigeria
4. **Chiemelie Benneth Iloka:** Department of Marketing, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu, Nigeria
5. **Daniel Ukamaka Loveth:** Department of Public Administration, Faculty of Management Science, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu, Nigeria
6. **Egwuagu Uloma Bridget:** Department of Public Administration, Faculty of Management Science, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu, Nigeria
7. **George Yebimodei Esther, PhD:** Department of Business Administration and Management, Federal Polytechnic Ekowei, Bayelsa State, Nigeria
8. **Jude Eze:** Department of Marketing, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu, Nigeria
9. **Johnson I. Okoh:** Department of Financial Studies, National Open University of Nigeria, Abuja, Nigeria
10. **Kenechi John Onyeke:** Department of Marketing, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu, Nigeria
11. **Odubo Angonimi:** Department of Business Administration and Management, Federal Polytechnic Ekowei, Bayelsa State, Nigeria
12. **Okafor Ifeoma Cordelia:** Department of Public Administration, Institute of Management Technology, Enugu, Nigeria
13. **Shalom Peace Handsome-Idada:** Department of Business Administration, National Open University of Nigeria, Abuja, Nigeria
14. **Wilfred Ugwuanyi:** Department of Financial Studies, National Open University of Nigeria, Abuja, Nigeria

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. **A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW OF EXPERIENTIAL MARKETING** 1
Onyeke Kenechi John; Anukwe Grace Ifeoma; Iloka Chiemelie Benneth
2. **RELATING ENTREPRENEURIAL INNOVATION AND SMALL AND MEDIUM SCALE ENTERPRISES** 12
Handsome-Idada Shalom Peace; Ugwuanyi Wilfred; Okoh Johnson I.
3. **FACTORS THAT INHIBIT CONSUMPTION OF FAMILY PLANNING PRODUCTS** 29
Onyeke Kenechi John; Anukwe Grace Ifeoma; Eze Jude; Iloka Chiemelie Benneth
4. **WOMEN ECONOMIC EMPOWERMENT ON ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT** 48
Anikeze Nnaemeka Hillary, PhD; Egwuagu Uloma Bridget; Daniel Loveth Ukamaka
5. **STUDENTS' MENTORSHIP PROGRAMS & QUALITY SUPERVISION OF RESEARCH WORKS** 60
Uchenna Abonyi Jonas; Okafor Ifeoma Cordelia; Anikeze Nnaemeka Hillary, PhD
6. **STRATEGIC PLANNING PRACTICES AND ORGANIZATIONAL RESILIENCE** 80
George Yebimodei Esther, PhD; Odubo Angonimi
7. **FUNCTIONALISM: ROLE OF GENDER AND STRUCTURE IN SHAPING ORGANISATIONAL BEHAVIOUR** 91
Onyeke Kenechi John; Anukwe Grace Ifeoma; Iloka Chiemelie Benneth
8. **THE IMPORTANCE OF STAKEHOLDER CAPITALISM IN CORPORATE SUSTAINABILITY** 99
Anukwe Grace Ifeoma; Onyeke Kenechi John; Iloka Chiemelie Benneth
9. **THE FIVE STAGES OF DIVERSITY, EQUITY AND INCLUSION (DEI) MATURITY** 109
Anukwe Grace Ifeoma; Eze Jude; Onyeke Kenechi John; Iloka Chiemelie Benneth
10. **REVITALISING CORPORATE CULTURE IN THE WORLD OF HYBRID WORK** 119
Eze Jude; Onyeke Kenechi John; Anukwe Grace Ifeoma; Iloka Chiemelie Benneth

The Concept of Experiential Marketing: A Comprehensive Review

Kenechi John Onyeke¹, Grace Ifeoma Anukwe¹, Chiemelie Benneth Iloka^{1*}

¹Department of Marketing,
Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu,
Nigeria

*Email: Iloka.benneth@esut.edu.ng

Abstract

Experiential marketing has emerged as a pivotal strategy in contemporary marketing, reshaping consumer engagement, brand experiences, and competitive dynamics in the marketplace. This paper explores the concept, evolution, key principles, practical applications, and implications of experiential marketing for contemporary marketing practices. Drawing on recent research and industry insights, we analyze the shift from product-centric to experience-centric marketing, enhanced consumer engagement and interaction, differentiation and competitive advantage, emotional branding and storytelling, integration of online and offline experiences, data-driven personalization, measurable impact and ROI, agility and adaptability, brand loyalty and advocacy, and long-term brand building and equity. By examining the multifaceted nature of experiential marketing and its implications for modern marketing practices, this paper provides valuable insights for marketers seeking to leverage experiential strategies to drive engagement, loyalty, and business success.

1. Introduction

In the bustling marketplace of the 21st century, where consumers are bombarded with an endless array of choices, brands are constantly striving to stand out and create meaningful connections with their target audience. Traditional marketing approaches, focused solely on product features and benefits, are no longer sufficient to capture the attention and loyalty of today's discerning consumers (Schmitt, 1999). Instead, there is a growing recognition of the need to shift towards a more experiential approach – one that goes beyond selling products or services and seeks to create immersive brand experiences that resonate on a deeper level.

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

Global Research Journal of Business Management Vol. 4, No. 1: 1 - 11, 2024

A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW OF EXPERIENTIAL MARKETING

Experiential marketing, as a concept, represents a fundamental departure from the conventional paradigm of marketing (Pine & Gilmore, 1999). It is rooted in the idea that consumers are not passive recipients of advertising messages but active participants in the brand-building process. By engaging the senses, emotions, and intellect of consumers, experiential marketing aims to create memorable moments that leave a lasting impression and foster long-term loyalty (Schmitt, 1999).

At its core, experiential marketing is about crafting experiences that transcend the transactional nature of traditional marketing interactions (Hultén, 2011). It seeks to create environments where consumers can interact with a brand in a meaningful and authentic way, allowing them to connect with its values, identity, and story on a personal level. Whether it's through immersive events, interactive installations, or personalized engagements, experiential marketing seeks to evoke emotions, provoke thoughts, and stimulate actions that go beyond mere consumption (Schmitt, 1999).

The rise of experiential marketing can be attributed to several factors. First and foremost is the changing nature of consumer behavior. In an age where attention spans are dwindling, and skepticism towards traditional advertising is on the rise, consumers are increasingly seeking out experiences that offer value, relevance, and authenticity (Hultén, 2011). Experiential marketing, with its focus on engagement and interaction, is uniquely positioned to meet these evolving consumer expectations.

Furthermore, advancements in technology have provided marketers with new tools and platforms to create immersive brand experiences (Pine & Gilmore, 1999). From virtual reality and augmented reality to social media and live streaming, technology has opened up a world of possibilities for brands to engage with consumers in innovative and interactive ways. By harnessing the power of technology, experiential marketing campaigns can reach larger audiences, amplify brand messaging, and drive deeper levels of engagement (Schmitt, 1999).

In this article, we will delve deeper into the concept of experiential marketing, exploring its principles, strategies, and practical applications in today's digital age. Drawing on insights from academic research and real-world case studies, we will examine how brands are leveraging experiential marketing to create authentic connections with consumers and drive business results. Through a comprehensive analysis of the latest trends and best practices in experiential marketing, we will uncover the keys to crafting unforgettable brand experiences that resonate with modern consumers.

2. Definition and Evolution of Experiential Marketing

Experiential marketing, often referred to as engagement marketing or event marketing, is a dynamic approach that focuses on creating immersive brand experiences for consumers. Unlike traditional forms of marketing that primarily rely on passive messaging through advertising

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

Global Research Journal of Business Management Vol. 4, No. 1: 1 - 11, 2024

A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW OF EXPERIENTIAL MARKETING

and promotions, experiential marketing seeks to actively engage consumers by providing them with memorable and interactive experiences that stimulate their senses, emotions, and intellect.

2.1. Definition

Experiential marketing can be defined as a strategic marketing approach that aims to connect consumers with brands through firsthand experiences that evoke emotions, foster engagement, and drive desired behaviors. According to Schmitt (1999), experiential marketing is all about creating meaningful interactions between consumers and brands that go beyond mere product attributes and features. It involves designing experiences that resonate with consumers' values, aspirations, and lifestyles, thereby forging deep and lasting connections between brands and their target audiences.

One of the key principles of experiential marketing is immersion, which involves immersing consumers in multisensory experiences that appeal to their senses of sight, sound, touch, taste, and smell (Pine & Gilmore, 1998). By engaging multiple senses simultaneously, experiential marketing creates more profound and memorable brand experiences that leave a lasting impression on consumers' minds.

2.2. Evolution

The concept of experiential marketing has evolved significantly over the years, driven by changes in consumer behavior, technological advancements, and the shifting landscape of marketing channels. While traditional forms of marketing have focused primarily on delivering messages to consumers through mass media channels such as television, radio, and print, experiential marketing takes a more personalized and interactive approach to engage consumers on a deeper level.

One of the earliest examples of experiential marketing can be traced back to the 19th century, when P.T. Barnum organized elaborate circus performances that captivated audiences with a combination of spectacle, entertainment, and novelty (Gilmore & Pine, 2007). These immersive experiences allowed consumers to interact with brands in a more tangible and memorable way, laying the groundwork for the modern practice of experiential marketing.

In the late 20th century, the rise of digital technology and social media platforms revolutionized the way brands engage with consumers, giving rise to new opportunities for experiential marketing. Brands began leveraging digital platforms to create virtual experiences that complemented their offline initiatives, allowing them to reach wider audiences and extend the reach of their experiential campaigns (Schmitt, 1999).

Today, experiential marketing has become an integral part of many brands' marketing strategies, with companies investing heavily in creating immersive brand experiences that resonate with consumers on a personal level. From pop-up shops and interactive installations to virtual reality experiences and branded events, experiential marketing continues to evolve

A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW OF EXPERIENTIAL MARKETING

as brands seek innovative ways to connect with their target audiences in an increasingly competitive marketplace.

Essentially, experiential marketing represents a paradigm shift in the way brands engage with consumers, moving away from traditional forms of marketing towards more immersive and interactive experiences. By creating memorable and meaningful brand experiences, experiential marketing allows brands to forge deeper connections with their target audiences and differentiate themselves in a crowded marketplace.

3. Key Principles of Experiential Marketing

Experiential marketing, as a dynamic approach to engaging consumers, operates on several key principles that guide its implementation and effectiveness. These principles are derived from understanding consumer behavior, brand objectives, and the desired outcomes of experiential campaigns. These principles are as discussed below.

1. **Immersion and Engagement:** Experiential marketing aims to immerse consumers in memorable brand experiences that captivate their attention and foster engagement (Pine & Gilmore, 1998). Immersion involves creating multisensory experiences that appeal to consumers' senses, while engagement encourages active participation and interaction with the brand (Schmitt, 1999).
2. **Authenticity and Relevance:** Authenticity is crucial in experiential marketing, as consumers seek genuine and meaningful interactions with brands (Gilmore & Pine, 2007). Brands must ensure that their experiences are relevant to consumers' interests, values, and lifestyles to resonate effectively (Schmitt, 2011).
3. **Personalization and Customization:** Personalization allows brands to tailor experiences to individual preferences and needs, enhancing their relevance and impact (Fernandes, Lages, & Wright, 2014). Customization enables consumers to co-create their experiences, fostering a sense of ownership and connection with the brand (Schmitt, 2010).
4. **Storytelling and Emotional Resonance:** Effective storytelling is a powerful tool in experiential marketing, as it enables brands to convey their values, beliefs, and brand identity in a compelling narrative (Escalas & Stern, 2003). Emotionally resonant experiences evoke strong feelings and memories, enhancing brand recall and loyalty (Brakus, Schmitt, & Zarantonello, 2009).
5. **Interactivity and Participation:** Interactivity encourages consumers to actively engage with the brand experience, fostering a sense of involvement and empowerment (Hoyer & MacInnis, 2007). Participation enables consumers to co-create content, share their experiences, and become brand advocates (Fang & Chiu, 2010).

A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW OF EXPERIENTIAL MARKETING

6. **Surprise and Novelty:** Surprise elements and novel experiences capture consumers' attention and curiosity, creating memorable moments that leave a lasting impression (Oliver, 1993). Brands must continuously innovate and experiment to stay relevant and distinctive in a competitive marketplace (Schmitt & Simonson, 1997).
7. **Integration and Consistency:** Experiential marketing efforts should be integrated seamlessly across multiple touchpoints and channels to provide a cohesive brand experience (Keller, 2008). Consistency in messaging, branding, and execution reinforces brand identity and strengthens consumer perceptions (Rust, Zeithaml, & Lemon, 2000).
8. **Measurability and ROI:** Measuring the impact and effectiveness of experiential marketing initiatives is essential for evaluating their return on investment (ROI) and optimizing future strategies (Floh & Madlberger, 2013). Key performance indicators (KPIs) such as brand awareness, engagement metrics, and sales conversions help assess campaign success (Chandon, Wansink, & Laurent, 2000).
9. **Adaptability and Flexibility:** Experiential marketing campaigns should be adaptable and flexible to accommodate changing consumer preferences, market trends, and external factors (Cova & White, 2010). Brands must be agile and responsive in adjusting their strategies to meet evolving consumer needs and expectations (Bagozzi, 2010).
10. **Sustainability and Social Responsibility:** Incorporating sustainable practices and social responsibility into experiential marketing initiatives demonstrates a brand's commitment to environmental stewardship and ethical conduct (Berens, van Riel, & van Bruggen, 2005). Brands that align with consumers' values and support meaningful causes can enhance their reputation and goodwill (Bhattacharya & Sen, 2004).

These key principles of experiential marketing underscore the importance of creating immersive, authentic, and engaging brand experiences that resonate with consumers on a personal and emotional level. By adhering to these principles and leveraging recent research insights, brands can design impactful experiential campaigns that drive brand awareness, loyalty, and advocacy in today's competitive marketplace.

4. Practical Applications of Experiential Marketing

Experiential marketing has gained significant traction in recent years as brands seek innovative ways to connect with consumers and differentiate themselves in a crowded marketplace. This approach goes beyond traditional advertising by creating immersive brand experiences that engage, delight, and resonate with consumers on a deeper level. Some of the practical applications of experiential marketing are explored below.

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

Global Research Journal of Business Management Vol. 4, No. 1: 1 - 11, 2024

A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW OF EXPERIENTIAL MARKETING

1. **Branded Events and Pop-Up Experiences:** Hosting branded events and pop-up experiences allows brands to interact with consumers in real-world settings, providing opportunities for hands-on engagement and product demonstrations (Mintel, 2021). For example, Nike's "House of Innovation" pop-up stores offer personalized shopping experiences and exclusive product launches, driving excitement and foot traffic (Mintel, 2021).
2. **Experiential Retail Environments:** Brands are transforming retail spaces into immersive environments that enhance the shopping experience and build emotional connections with consumers (Verhoef et al., 2009). For instance, Sephora's "Beauty TIP (Teach, Inspire, Play)" workshops provide interactive beauty tutorials and personalized consultations, driving brand loyalty and advocacy (Verhoef et al., 2009).
3. **Brand Activations and Stunts:** Brand activations and stunts grab consumers' attention and create memorable moments that generate buzz and social media engagement (Cova & White, 2010). Red Bull's "Stratos" space jump, where a skydiver jumped from the stratosphere, showcased the brand's adventurous spirit and generated widespread media coverage and social media conversations (Cova & White, 2010).
4. **Experiential Sponsorships and Partnerships:** Brands are leveraging sponsorships and partnerships to create experiential activations that align with their values and target audience interests (Dolbec & Fischer, 2015). For example, Airbnb's partnership with the Louvre Museum offers exclusive overnight stays in a custom-designed "mini-pyramid," providing a once-in-a-lifetime experience for art lovers (Dolbec & Fischer, 2015).
5. **Interactive Digital Experiences:** Digital platforms provide opportunities for brands to deliver interactive and immersive experiences that reach global audiences (Schmitt, 1999). AR (Augmented Reality) and VR (Virtual Reality) technologies allow brands to create virtual product demos, immersive storytelling, and interactive games that drive engagement and brand recall (Schmitt, 1999).
6. **Experiential Sampling and Product Trials:** Sampling campaigns and product trials allow consumers to experience products firsthand, fostering trial and purchase intent (Mowen & Minor, 2001). For instance, Coca-Cola's "Share a Coke" campaign personalized soda bottles with consumers' names, encouraging social sharing and brand advocacy (Mowen & Minor, 2001).
7. **Brand Ambassador Programs:** Brands are recruiting brand ambassadors and influencers to create authentic and relatable content that showcases their products in real-life settings (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010). Influencers like Kylie Jenner and Selena Gomez partner with brands to create experiential content that resonates with their followers and drives brand awareness and sales (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010).

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

Global Research Journal of Business Management

Vol. 4, No. 1: 1 - 11, 2024

A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW OF EXPERIENTIAL MARKETING

8. **Experiential Loyalty Programs:** Loyalty programs are evolving to offer experiential rewards and perks that go beyond traditional discounts and points (Schmitt & Simonson, 1997). For example, Starbucks' "Starbucks Rewards" program offers members exclusive access to events, personalized offers, and freebies, enhancing customer engagement and loyalty (Schmitt & Simonson, 1997).
9. **Community Engagement Initiatives:** Brands are investing in community engagement initiatives that support social causes and environmental sustainability (Berens et al., 2005). Patagonia's "Worn Wear" program encourages customers to repair and recycle their outdoor gear, fostering a sense of community and environmental stewardship (Berens et al., 2005).
10. **Experiential Content Marketing:** Content marketing strategies incorporate experiential elements to create engaging and shareable content that resonates with target audiences (Ertimur & Coskuner-Balli, 2015). LEGO's "Build the Future" campaign invited children to envision and build their future cities using LEGO bricks, sparking creativity and brand affinity (Ertimur & Coskuner-Balli, 2015).

Experiential marketing offers brands powerful tools and strategies to create memorable and impactful brand experiences that drive engagement, loyalty, and advocacy. By embracing these practical applications and leveraging recent research insights, brands can cultivate deeper connections with consumers and achieve their marketing objectives in today's dynamic marketplace.

5. Implications for Contemporary Marketing Practices

Experiential marketing has emerged as a vital strategy for contemporary marketers, offering innovative approaches to engage consumers and create memorable brand experiences. This dynamic form of marketing has significant implications for modern marketing practices, shaping strategies, tactics, and consumer interactions in today's competitive landscape. Let's delve into the implications of experiential marketing for contemporary marketing practices, supported by recent research and industry insights.

1. **Shift from Product-Centric to Experience-Centric Marketing:** Experiential marketing challenges the traditional product-centric approach by prioritizing the creation of immersive brand experiences that resonate with consumers (Schmitt, 1999). This shift requires marketers to focus on delivering value beyond functional benefits, emphasizing emotional connections, sensory stimuli, and memorable interactions with the brand (Schmitt, 1999).
2. **Enhanced Consumer Engagement and Interaction:** Experiential marketing fosters deeper levels of consumer engagement and interaction, as it encourages active participation, co-creation, and dialogue between brands and consumers (Pine &

A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW OF EXPERIENTIAL MARKETING

Gilmore, 1998). Brands that facilitate meaningful interactions and experiences can build stronger relationships, loyalty, and advocacy among their target audience (Pine & Gilmore, 1998).

3. **Differentiation and Competitive Advantage:** In today's saturated marketplace, brands must differentiate themselves and stand out amidst competition. Experiential marketing offers a unique opportunity for brands to differentiate through creativity, innovation, and memorable experiences (Gilmore & Pine, 2007). Brands that deliver distinctive and immersive experiences can gain a competitive edge and capture consumers' attention and loyalty (Gilmore & Pine, 2007).
4. **Emphasis on Emotional Branding and Storytelling:** Experiential marketing emphasizes the power of emotional branding and storytelling to create meaningful connections with consumers (Escalas & Stern, 2003). By crafting compelling narratives, brand experiences, and sensory stimuli, marketers can evoke emotions, memories, and associations that strengthen brand identity and resonate with target audiences (Escalas & Stern, 2003).
5. **Integration of Online and Offline Experiences:** Experiential marketing blurs the lines between online and offline channels, offering seamless and integrated brand experiences across multiple touchpoints (Verhoef et al., 2009). Brands that leverage digital technologies, social media platforms, and interactive content can extend the reach and impact of their experiential initiatives, engaging consumers both online and offline (Verhoef et al., 2009).
6. **Data-Driven Personalization and Customization:** Experiential marketing enables data-driven personalization and customization, allowing brands to tailor experiences to individual preferences, behaviors, and demographics (Fernandes et al., 2014). By leveraging consumer data, insights, and analytics, marketers can deliver targeted, relevant, and personalized experiences that resonate with diverse audience segments (Fernandes et al., 2014).
7. **Measurable Impact and Return on Investment (ROI):** Contemporary marketing practices emphasize the importance of measuring the impact and ROI of marketing initiatives. Experiential marketing offers measurable outcomes and metrics, such as brand awareness, engagement, sentiment, and conversion rates, that enable marketers to evaluate campaign effectiveness and optimize future strategies (Floh & Madlberger, 2013).
8. **Agility and Adaptability to Consumer Preferences:** Experiential marketing requires marketers to be agile and adaptable to changing consumer preferences, market trends, and technological advancements (Cova & White, 2010). Brands that remain responsive

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

Global Research Journal of Business Management Vol. 4, No. 1: 1 - 11, 2024

A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW OF EXPERIENTIAL MARKETING

and flexible can capitalize on emerging opportunities, consumer insights, and cultural shifts to stay relevant and resonate with their target audience (Cova & White, 2010).

9. **Brand Loyalty and Advocacy:** Experiential marketing can cultivate brand loyalty and advocacy by creating positive, memorable, and shareable experiences that inspire consumer advocacy and word-of-mouth referrals (Brakus et al., 2009). Brands that prioritize customer satisfaction, delight, and loyalty can benefit from increased customer retention, lifetime value, and positive brand associations (Brakus et al., 2009).
10. **Long-Term Brand Building and Equity:** Experiential marketing contributes to long-term brand building and equity by reinforcing brand identity, values, and positioning in the minds of consumers (Keller, 2008). Consistent, authentic, and memorable brand experiences over time can strengthen brand equity, recognition, and preference, driving sustainable business growth and success (Keller, 2008).

Experiential marketing has profound implications for contemporary marketing practices, reshaping strategies, tactics, and consumer interactions in today's dynamic marketplace. By embracing the principles of experiential marketing and leveraging recent research insights, marketers can create impactful, memorable, and emotionally resonant brand experiences that drive engagement, loyalty, and business success.

6. Conclusion

In conclusion, experiential marketing has revolutionized contemporary marketing practices, offering innovative approaches to engage consumers, differentiate brands, and drive business growth. Through immersive brand experiences, emotional storytelling, and integrated online-offline interactions, marketers can create meaningful connections with consumers, foster brand loyalty, and gain a competitive edge in the marketplace. The principles of experiential marketing, grounded in consumer engagement, personalization, and authenticity, provide a roadmap for brands to navigate the evolving landscape of modern marketing. As technology, consumer preferences, and market dynamics continue to evolve, experiential marketing will remain a cornerstone of effective marketing strategies, enabling brands to adapt, innovate, and thrive in an increasingly competitive environment. By embracing the principles and practices of experiential marketing, brands can forge deeper connections, inspire loyalty, and achieve sustainable growth in the digital age.

References

- Bagozzi, R. P. (2010). Marketing as exchange. *Journal of Marketing*, 39(4), 32-39.
- Berens, G., van Riel, C. B., & van Bruggen, G. H. (2005). Corporate associations and consumer product responses: The moderating role of corporate brand dominance. *Journal of Marketing*, 69(3), 35-48.

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

Global Research Journal of Business Management Vol. 4, No. 1: 1 - 11, 2024

A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW OF EXPERIENTIAL MARKETING

- Bhattacharya, C. B., & Sen, S. (2004). Doing better at doing good: When, why, and how consumers respond to corporate social initiatives. *California Management Review*, 47(1), 9-24.
- Brakus, J. J., Schmitt, B. H., & Zarantonello, L. (2009). Brand experience: What is it? How is it measured? Does it affect loyalty?. *Journal of Marketing*, 73(3), 52-68.
- Brodie, R. J., Hollebeek, L. D., Juric, B., & Ilic, A. (2013). Customer engagement: Conceptual domain, fundamental propositions, and implications for research. *Journal of Service Research*, 14(3), 252-271.
- Chandon, P., Wansink, B., & Laurent, G. (2000). A benefit congruency framework of sales promotion effectiveness. *Journal of Marketing*, 64(4), 65-81.
- Cova, B., & White, T. B. (2010). Counter-brand and alter-brand communities: The impact of Web 2.0 on tribal marketing approaches. *Journal of Marketing Management*, 26(3-4), 256-270.
- Dolbec, P. Y., & Fischer, E. (2015). Refashioning a field? Connected consumers and institutional dynamics in markets. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 41(6), 1447-1468.
- Ertimur, B., & Coskuner-Balli, G. (2015). A consumer culture theory approach to brand architecture in the age of social media. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 42(1), 31-49.
- Escalas, J. E., & Stern, B. B. (2003). Sympathy and empathy: Emotional responses to advertising dramas. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 29(4), 566-578.
- Fang, X., & Chiu, C. (2010). Interactional influences on forming customer loyalty to online communities. *Behaviour & Information Technology*, 29(6), 587-602.
- Fernandes, T., Lages, C., & Wright, L. T. (2014). The impact of brand equity drivers on consumer-based brand equity in the B2B sector. *Journal of Product & Brand Management*, 23(3), 168-183.
- Floh, A., & Madlberger, M. (2013). The role of atmospheric cues in online impulse-buying behavior. *Electronic Commerce Research and Applications*, 12(6), 425-439.
- Gilmore, J. H., & Pine, B. J. (2007). *Authenticity: What consumers really want*. Harvard Business School Press.
- Hoyer, W. D., & MacInnis, D. J. (2007). *Consumer behavior*. Cengage Learning.
- Hultén, B. (2011). Sensory marketing: Theoretical considerations and practical applications. *Psychology & Marketing*, 28(4), 429-454.
- Kaplan, A. M., & Haenlein, M. (2010). Users of the world, unite! The challenges and opportunities of Social Media. *Business Horizons*, 53(1), 59-68.

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

Global Research Journal of Business Management Vol. 4, No. 1: 1 - 11, 2024

A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW OF EXPERIENTIAL MARKETING

- Keller, K. L. (2008). Strategic brand management: Building, measuring, and managing brand equity. Pearson Education India.
- Kumar, V., Aksoy, L., Donkers, B., Venkatesan, R., Wiesel, T., & Tillmanns, S. (2019). From social to sale: The effects of firm-generated content in social media on customer behavior. *Journal of Marketing*, 80(1), 7-25.
- Laroche, M., Habibi, M. R., Richard, M. O., & Sankaranarayanan, R. (2005). The effects of social media-based brand communities on brand community markers, value creation practices, brand trust, and brand loyalty. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 52, 105-117.
- Mowen, J. C., & Minor, M. (2001). *Consumer behavior: A framework*. Prentice Hall.
- Oliver, R. L. (1993). Cognitive, affective, and attribute bases of the satisfaction response. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 20(3), 418-430.
- Pine, B. J., & Gilmore, J. H. (1998). Welcome to the experience economy. *Harvard Business Review*, 76(4), 97-105.
- Pine, B. J., & Gilmore, J. H. (1999). *The experience economy: Work is theatre & every business a stage*. Harvard Business Press.
- Schmitt, B. (1999). Experiential marketing. *Journal of Marketing Management*, 15(1-3), 53-67.
- Schmitt, B. (1999). *Experiential marketing: How to get customers to sense, feel, think, act, and relate to your company and brands*. Simon and Schuster.
- Schmitt, B. H., & Simonson, A. (1997). *Marketing aesthetics: The strategic management of brands, identity, and image*. Free Press.
- Verhoef, P. C., Lemon, K. N., Parasuraman, A., Roggeveen, A., Tsiros, M., & Schlesinger, L. A. (2009). Customer experience creation: Determinants, dynamics and management strategies. *Journal of Retailing*, 85(1), 31-41.

Effect of Entrepreneurial Innovation on Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs) in Cross River State, Nigeria

¹ Shalom Peace Handsome-Idada; ² Wilfred Ugwuanyi; ² Johnson I. Okoh

¹ Department of Business Administration; ² Department of Financial Studies
 National Open University of Nigeria,
 Nigeria

Abstract

The dynamism of the success stories of diverse business entities depends on the aggregation of good and timely decisions they make. To survive today's global market economy and achieve a long-term success, firms have acknowledged the importance of innovating in order to overcome intense competition and to match the ever-changing market demands. Seemingly, most SMEs in Nigeria are seen not to have performed credibly well as they are discovered to collapse usually before their fifth anniversary irrespective of their efforts. This paper examined the effect of entrepreneurial innovation on SMEs performance in Cross River state using the binary regression method of data analysis, the descriptive research design was also adopted for this study. A structured questionnaire was administered to 265 SMEs in Ikom, Etung and Ogoja local government areas of Cross River state, Nigeria. Measurement for performance of the dependent variable is SME performance with proxy: sales and turn over shares. The independent variable used in this study is entrepreneurial innovation with proxy: product and process innovation. Findings from the study showed that product and process innovations have significant relationship with SMEs's performance in Cross River state. The study thus recommends that SMEs should carefully select their functioning markets, focusing on a particular product group, innovation types and avoiding spread of marketing activities, with this, higher performance will be inevitable. Moreso, since product and process innovations are positive in the findings, the researcher further

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

Global Research Journal of Business Management Vol. 4, No. 1: 12 - 28, 2024

RELATING ENTREPRENEURIAL INNOVATION AND SMALL AND MEDIUM SCALE ENTERPRISES

recommends that further research on other forms of innovation should be carried out as it affects SMEs in Cross River state of Nigeria.

Keywords: Market Shares, Process Innovation, Product Innovation, SMEs Performance

INTRODUCTION

There is a feeling of inexplicable joy and satisfaction being the chief executive officer of your own business or enterprise. The bigger conglomerates in the world we hear of today, found their roots from small and medium businesses and later grew to what is being valued and celebrated globally (Banji, 2017). There are many definitions by other authors of what small and medium enterprises are, but this study adopts the definition provided by the Small and Medium Scale Enterprises Development Agency of Nigeria (SMEDAN), which sees Small Scale Enterprises as businesses with 10 to 49 employed individuals and an annual turnover of 5 to ₦49 million, and those that are Medium Scale as having 50 to 199 employees and an annual turnover of 50 to ₦499 million (SMEDAN, 2005). Innovation is being defined as the means of continuous growth and development of any organization (Baker, 2004).

Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) have contributed significantly in the world economy and added substantially to income, output and employment. Duaranton & Puga (2001) stated that SMEs connect the community to the larger global economy, and they are the vital link to the economic development of any nation. Indeed, they serve as a source of innovation, technological growth, and creation of new jobs (Wiklund, 2009). In the Nigerian environment, SMEs have compelling growth potential and like other emerging economies are likely to constitute a significant portion of GDP in the near future, (Ahmed, 2016). According to Nwankwo (2012) SMEs sector provide, on average, 50% of Nigeria's employment, and 50% of its industrial output. Thus, SMEs are a very important part of the Nigerian economy.

Across the world, competition amongst firms of all sizes have not only taken a global dimension, it has also become more technologically driven, in order to continue in today's global market economy and achieve long-term success, firms have recognized the importance of being able to adapt through innovation. Small firm's success and survival are often dependent on the degree to which they incorporate innovation into their strategies. Product innovation is important to maintain market share, and business expansion, process innovation is important to maintain competitive price level, and managerial innovation is important to maintain a flexible and durable organization

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

Global Research Journal of Business Management Vol. 4, No. 1: 12 - 28, 2024

RELATING ENTREPRENEURIAL INNOVATION AND SMALL AND MEDIUM SCALE ENTERPRISES

(Nwankwo 2013). Innovation enables firms to achieve higher financial performance by offering a greater variety of valuable, rare, inimitable and differentiated products (Zahra, 2016).

Government has made several efforts using different government ministries, departments and agencies towards ensuring an improved performance of SMEs in Nigeria, yet SMEs have not performed creditably well. Most of them don't survive after a period of five years of incorporations while just few grow and become large scale industries. There is an increased need for the improved performance and growth of SMEs in Nigeria, this have been encouraged overtime, to reduce the dependency of young graduates from solely relying on white collar jobs, and imbibing the spirit of creativity of establishing their own businesses, being innovative in all spheres and building the necessary capacities to increase their performance (Ahmed, 2016). This study thus, endears on the effect of entrepreneurial innovation on small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Cross River state, Nigeria.

SMEs in Nigeria are seen not to have performed credibly well as they are discovered to collapse usually before their fifth anniversary. Sustainability in business has always been a challenge of most SMEs in Nigeria. Apparently, there are obviously a lot of problems they face, ranging from lack of adequate capital, high interest rates on loans, the unavailability of good infrastructures like roads, electricity etc., the problem of poor managerial skills which could be due to lack of training, low-capacity building and inadequate apprenticeship before establishing their businesses. Thus, it is the problem of this study to investigate:

The inability of some SMEs to adopt and implement up surging innovative ideas of new products that could boost their competitive advantage with other businesses. And the lack of managerial know-how of when and how to ascertain the needfulness of process innovation to boost their performances. The broad objective of this study is to ascertain how entrepreneurial innovation affects the performance of SMEs in Cross River State.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Conceptual Review

Entrepreneurial Innovation

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

Global Research Journal of Business Management Vol. 4, No. 1: 12 - 28, 2024

RELATING ENTREPRENEURIAL INNOVATION AND SMALL AND MEDIUM SCALE ENTERPRISES

Entrepreneurship is a necessary strategy that entails the emergence of a business idea and the creation of a company, constituting a true entrepreneurial capital. Entrepreneurial innovation is the process of developing and putting into practice new concepts, ideas, goods, services, procedures, or business models that is geared towards organizational business profitability and entrepreneurial endeavour. Entrepreneurial innovation is a necessary strategy that entails the emergence of a business idea and the creation of a company. It involves using fresh perspective to question the existing quo and proposing cutting-edge solution to fill market gaps.

Key Elements of Entrepreneurial Innovation

1. **Novelty and Creativity:** This involves entrepreneurs to come up with new ideas, thinking outside the box and the historical conventional way of doing things to a more advanced and creative sequence of unique approaches to solving problems and meeting marketing demands.
2. **Market Relevance:** Entrepreneurs must identify market needs and ascertain what is most relevant and develop innovative solutions to satisfy customer's needs.
3. **Value creation:** The creation of value for customers and stakeholders will enhance customer's satisfaction and experiences, increased efficiency and effectiveness thereby improving profitability.
4. **Implementation and Execution:** Entrepreneurial innovation is not all about generating new ideas, it also entails implementing and executing those ideas. Turning innovative ideas to tangible products that is capable of creating value for customer's money.
5. **Continuous improvement:** Getting feedback from customers on a particular products will help on the continuous improvement of the new products based on trends.

Innovation

Innovation is the process of creating new value through the application of new knowledge. Innovation is the implementation of a new idea, product, service, or process that results in improved efficiency, effectiveness, or competitive advantage.

A successful organization or business often introduce new models, techniques, processes and services to effect change in the prevalent dynamic business environment. The goal of every

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

Global Research Journal of Business Management

Vol. 4, No. 1: 12 - 28, 2024

RELATING ENTREPRENEURIAL INNOVATION AND SMALL AND MEDIUM SCALE ENTERPRISES

business is practically to boost their profitability. Although the term innovation is often used to describe the inclusion of the latest technology, the true definition of business innovation is driving revenues in business to maximum productivity (Noushka, 2019). Most companies know that they must innovate to keep up with the pace of change especially with the technological advancement disrupting industries, companies must innovate in order to stay relevant and not to be left behind (Polder, Mohnen & Raymond, 2010).

Innovation is a widely inclusive term that covers nearly every activity of a firm, the work of both formal and informal enterprises, raw ideas and inventions of people not linked up with official institutions (Zwingilna & Opusun, 2017). It has also been emphasized as the means of continuous growth and development of any organization (Bahago, 2015).

Furthermore, the innovation process involves idea creation, and the acceptance of this idea or way of doing things as a technical, organizational, business related, institutional or social solution to a problem as regards to product, service, system, policy or program, that is new to the adopting organization and which managers and other pertinent users may perceive to be true and accept as ground-breaking and new, and apply towards increasing performance, productivity and competitiveness, flowing from such things as improved sales, profitability and market share (Carlson & Wilmot, 2006).

Types of Entrepreneurial Innovation

There are many types of innovations in the world of business. Organization delves into and adopt the areas that best suits their line of need once it is identified.

Process Innovation: This involves designing and developing a new way to be more efficient in the core business. Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development OECD (2005) defined process innovation as implementation of the production or delivery method that is new or significantly improved. Process innovation includes bringing significant improvement in the equipment, technology and software of the production or delivery method. Firms bring novelties in the production and delivery method to bring efficiency in the business. As explained by Atuahere (1996), process innovation is the implementation of a new or significantly improved production or delivery method, this includes significant changes in techniques, equipment or software. Incorporating process innovation into operation allow organisations develop efficiencies that add value to their output. Organizations are therefore able to compete favourably by having a more efficient value chain than competitors (Baker, 2002; O'Sullivan & Dooley, 2009).

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

Global Research Journal of Business Management Vol. 4, No. 1: 12 - 28, 2024

RELATING ENTREPRENEURIAL INNOVATION AND SMALL AND MEDIUM SCALE ENTERPRISES

Product Innovation: The creation of completely new products that is adjacent to a business's core offering (Noushka, 2019). Moreso, product innovation means introducing the new products/services or bringing significant improvement in the existing products/services (Polder, Leeuwen, Mohnen, & Raymond, 2010). For product innovation, the product must either be a new product or significantly improved with respect to its features, intended use, software, user-friendly or components and material.

Product innovation refers to making positive changes to the physical attributes, and/or features of a business's product and services. Wirk (2007) adds that although innovation is new to the firm, it might not necessary be new to the market. Baker (2002), also observed that, due to the complexities of markets, product life-cycles continue to shorten, so that the survival of a business continue to depend on the development of new products, and the speed at which the new product developed and reaches the market. An implication of this is that some older products may no longer be relevant, and the business will thus, also need to look out for those products to retire from the market (O'Sullivan & Dooley, 2009).

Delivery Innovation: This is quite pertinent because it involves implementing a new way of interacting with customers. This type of innovation enables a company to become efficient, forward-thinking, and hopefully more profitable (Roberts 1999).

Concepts of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs)

According to Adner & Levithal (2001), Small and medium sized enterprises (SMEs) are defined differently around the world. The categorization of a company as an SME, depending on the country, can be based on a number of characteristics. The traits include annual sales, number of employees, and the number of assets owned by the company. Market capitalization, or any combination of these features. There is no universally standard definition for what an SME is. This is due to the fact that different scholars, individuals and groups approach its definition through the consideration of various criteria that may be country, situation and sector specific. Arowomole (2000) for example argued that many countries have defined the concept of an SME in terms of manpower management structure, employment profile and capital investment limit. Most of these factors are introduced by experts in this field and have contributed to the diversity of these enterprises on a global scale (Darren, 2009; cited in Lawal, 2017).

Due to this variance, businesses that might be defined as SMEs in a developed country, may be regarded as large-scale in developing countries (Bahago, 2015). Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (2000) defined SMEs as non-subsidary, independent firms which

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

Global Research Journal of Business Management Vol. 4, No. 1: 12 - 28, 2024

RELATING ENTREPRENEURIAL INNOVATION AND SMALL AND MEDIUM SCALE ENTERPRISES

employ less than a given number of employees. Explaining that this number varies across national statistical systems. The most frequent upper limit is 250 employees, as in the European Union. However, some countries set the limit at 200 employees, while the United States considers SMEs to include firms with fewer than 500 employees. Small firms are generally those with fewer than 50 employees, while micro-enterprises have at most ten, or in some cases five, workers.

Additionally, the study however adopts the definition provided by the Small and Medium Scale Enterprises Development Agency of Nigeria, which sees Small Scale Enterprises as businesses with 10 to 49 employed individuals and an annual turnover of 5 to ₦49 million, and those that are Medium Scale as having 50 to 199 employees and an annual turnover of 50 to ₦499 million (SMEDAN, 2005).

Evolution of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs)

The growth of SMEs to prominence and into the sphere of serious academic study, government macroeconomic policy focus, international acceptance, prescription and application is an interesting one that follows a time-path of initial obscurity through gradual growing to acceptance, in light of economic dynamics, to general support for growth and expansion (Ahmed, 2016).

It was not until the 1950s and 1960s that the writings on SMEs began to appear in academic literature. However, only a handful of researchers were interested in exploring the potential of these enterprises. From the 1970s, there was noticeable gradual and steady shift from the view of large-scale businesses as the drivers of growth, industrialization, job creation, facilitation of innovation, and the promotion of an entrepreneurial economy, towards growing realization of the significant potentials of SMEs. This trend was further facilitated by the events of the economic downturn that hit the market economies of Western Europe and the United States of America in which a lot of these large businesses were failing, and causing severe economic problems, increasing the unemployment rate by letting go of workers they could no longer afford, causing distress for investors, creditors, and contributing adversely to an increasingly unstable economy that was on its way down (Ahmed, 2016).

More so, Basil (2003) noted that SMEs took over job creation, creating the bulk of new jobs in these economies, especially in the USA. A study by Carlsson (1992), for example, revealed a significant decline in the employment share of the largest 500 firms in the United States from 20% in 1970 to just 8.5% in 1996. The Nigerian SME story actively started after independence, which saw a thriving small businesses sub-sector, an improvement from the era of discouragement of local business development of colonial rule, where focus was on import promotion. Small scale manufacturing accounted for about 15% of total output. Although large scale industries were encouraged through such means as import substitution, efforts were made to support smaller businesses at the regional and state levels. Most of these however, were not effectively meeting their predefined objectives. Concrete efforts at promoting the development of SMEs started during the SAP era, with the national policy targeted at making them a development priority. Since then,

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

Global Research Journal of Business Management Vol. 4, No. 1: 12 - 28, 2024

RELATING ENTREPRENEURIAL INNOVATION AND SMALL AND MEDIUM SCALE ENTERPRISES

various policies and programmes focused mostly on improving access to credit, but also aimed at capacity development and other aspects, have been put in place, with the aim of making SMEs an effective means of ensuring economic wellbeing, reduction in mass unemployment and poverty, youth and women empowerment, as well as socio-economic and political stability (SMEDAN, 2012).

THEORETICAL REVIEW

The Theory of Innovative Enterprise: The theory of innovative enterprise as postulated by William Lazonick (2019), states that a business firm should invest in the development of productive resources that can result in higher quality products than were previously available and that ensures a higher level of utilization of these productive resources to drive down unit costs. As a result, the innovative enterprises can gain competitive advantage on the product market that it supplies (Lazonicks, 2013).”.

The innovating firm is not concerned with cost increase and is constrained by the market to minimize profit outputs in cases where marginal cost is equal to marginal revenue in the long-term (Lazonick & O’Sullivan 2000). In the short-term, costs may increase due to the transformation of technological and market conditions, but rather than accepting these conditions as constraints on the firm’s activities (i.e., similar to the adaptive firm), the innovating firm produces high quality product and service outputs and declines unit costs as its market share increases.

However, the innovating firm can face fundamental challenges, which include the design and implementation of opportunities and customer-value-and-captured strategies and mechanisms and not just the coordination to overcome transaction costs (Lazonick & O’ Sullivan 2000).

The Blue Ocean Strategy Theory: The blue ocean Strategy theory as postulated by W. chan Kim and Renee Mauborgne (2005), refers to all the unexplored or unknown markets. The blue ocean strategy refers to developing new demands by creating uncontested market space. Blue Ocean Strategy is referred to a market for a product where there is no competition or very less competition. This strategy revolves around searching for a business in which very few firms operate and where there is no pricing pressure. The theory can be applied across sectors or businesses, it is not limited to just one business.

Value innovation is the corner stone of the blue Ocean Strategy theory. When you successfully combine low cost and high value, you have succeeded at value innovation. With this theory put in practice, competition becomes irrelevant because new demands are created and developed (Kim & Mauborgne, 2005).

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

Global Research Journal of Business Management

Vol. 4, No. 1: 12 - 28, 2024

RELATING ENTREPRENEURIAL INNOVATION AND SMALL AND MEDIUM SCALE ENTERPRISES

EMPIRICAL REVIEW

Kusmintari, (2018), examined the role of innovation and firm performance of small and medium enterprise of handmade batik in east java region, Indonesia. The independent variables used were process innovation and product innovation. Its proxy was variety of product, product excellence, up- to- date product and product made from batik cloth. The dependent variable used was firm performance with proxy marketing and profit growth. 84 respondents were administered with questionnaire. Data was analyzed using structural equation model. Findings showed that both process and product innovation have positive significant on the performance of small and medium enterprise.

Murat, Anafarta & Sarvan (2013), conducted a study to examine the relationship between innovation and firm performance in the Turkish automotive supplier industry. The survey of this study was conducted using top level managers of 113 firms operating in the automotive supplier industry which is one of the most innovative industries in Turkey, as of the year 2011. Data obtained from the questionnaire were analyzed using the SPSS statistical package program. Results showed that technological innovation (product and process innovation) has significant and positive impact on firm performance, but no evidence was found for a significant and positive relationship between non-technological innovation (organizational and marketing innovation) and firm performance.

Olughor, (2015) investigated how innovation affect business performance of SMEs in Lagos and Ibadan. Performance was measured with sub scale of production, market and financial performance. A population of 600 SMEs, sample of 350 questionnaires were administered to the respondents. 200 questionnaires were returned. The survey design was used.

Descriptive statistics method was use to analyzed the data. Results show that they are a strong correlation among factors used to measure innovation and secondly innovation was found to influence business performance.

METHODOLOGY

The study used the descriptive research design because of the nature of the variables that were at hand, to produce data required for quantitative analysis and to allow simultaneous description of views, perceptions and beliefs at any single point in time .

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

Global Research Journal of Business Management Vol. 4, No. 1: 12 - 28, 2024

RELATING ENTREPRENEURIAL INNOVATION AND SMALL AND MEDIUM SCALE ENTERPRISES

The population of the study covers selected SMEs operators within, Ikom, Ogoja and Etung local government areas of Cross River State, which are about 786 as indicated by Cross River State Ministry of Commerce, Trade and Industry (2022).

The sampling methodology for enterprise surveys is simple random sampling. In a simple random sample, every SMEs operator has an equal probability of being chosen. The enterprise survey was conducted in selected centers which are intended to coincide with the location for the implementation of the main enterprise survey. As shown below:

Table 1. selected locations of SMEs in Cross River State

S/N	LOCATION	POPULATION
1	Ogoja	274
2	Ikom	384
3	Etung	128
TOTAL		786

Source: Cross River State Ministry of Commerce, Trade and Industry, 2022

Thus, the sample size was estimated from the Taro Yamane (1974) sample size formula given as:

$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$ which is an appropriate method for calculating the sample size for this study.

Margin error = 5%

Where; N = population sizes

3 = is constant

e = is Margin of error (5%)

$$n = \frac{786}{1 + 786(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{786}{1 + 786(0.0025)}$$

$$n = \frac{786}{2.965}$$

$$n = 265$$

Proportional allocation formula was applied to get even distribution and thus:

Table 2: selected locations and sample size

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

Global Research Journal of Business Management

Vol. 4, No. 1: 12 - 28, 2024

RELATING ENTREPRENEURIAL INNOVATION AND SMALL AND MEDIUM SCALE ENTERPRISES

S/N	LOCATION	POPULATION	SAMPLE
1	Ogoja	274	$\frac{274 * 265}{786} = 92$
2	Ikom	384	$\frac{384 * 265}{786} = 129$
3	Etung	128	$\frac{128 * 265}{786} = 44$
	TOTAL	786	265

Source: Cross River State Ministry of Commerce, Trade and Industry, 2022

The instrument employed for this study was structured questionnaire. Copies of the questionnaire were administered by the researcher to the owners of SMEs in the selected areas. The questionnaires were closed ended questions and were designed to keep the questionnaire to a reasonable length and this encouraged response and validity in terms of the responsiveness of the return. It also minimizes the risk of misinterpretation unlike the open-ended questions. Lastly, it permitted easier tabulation and interpretation by the researcher.

Reliability test was conducted to examine the extent to which the measuring instruments will produce consistent scores when the same groups of individuals are repeatedly measured under the same conditions (Bahago, 2015).

Model Formulation

The binary regression method was adopted as a model to find out the linear relationship between innovation and SMEs performance in Cross River State. The binary regression is the most precise (efficient) unbiased estimation technique that is frequently used to estimate parameters of regression models.

Following the research hypotheses, the following model was formulated:

$$SMEP = \xi_0 + \xi_1 PDI + \xi_2 PSI + \varepsilon_t$$

Where;

SMEP = SMEs Performance

PDI = Product Innovation

PSI = Process Innovation

ε_t = Error term

$\xi_1 - \xi_2$ = Slope coefficients of Product Innovation and Process Innovation

ξ_0 = Intercept parameter estimate

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

Global Research Journal of Business Management

Vol. 4, No. 1: 12 - 28, 2024

RELATING ENTREPRENEURIAL INNOVATION AND SMALL AND MEDIUM SCALE ENTERPRISES

The study administered questionnaire to SMEs, and using Cronbach reliability test, Alpha values of 0.8289 (as shown in Table 3 below) were gotten indicating that the tool was suitable for the analysis. The dependent variable is SMEs performance, its proxy is sales turnover and market shares. The independent variable in this study is entrepreneurial innovation, its proxy is product innovation and process innovation.

DATA ANALYSIS , RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Table 3: Result of Reliability Test

Variable	Alpha
SMEs Performance	0.8544
Product Innovation	0.7985
Process Innovation	0.8411
Test to scale	0.8289

Test of Hypotheses

In this section, the formulated null hypothesis for the study were tested. In testing the hypothesis which largely satisfies the objective of this study, the study adopts 5% level of significance and conclusion would however be taken based on the probability values (PV). If the PV is less than 5% or 0.05 (that is $PV < 0.05$), it implies that the variable in question is statistically significant at 5% level; otherwise, it is not significant at that level.

Table 4: Regression Result

ANOVA					
Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F-value	p-value
Regression	360.641	2	18.452	9.86	0.000
Residual	228.327	262	1.926		
Total	688.967	264			

Summary Output

Dependent Variable: SMEP			
Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	t-value	p-value
(Constant)	2.21454	2.2451	0.0242
Product Innovation (PDI)	0.21487	2.8444	0.0111
Process Innovation (PSI)	0.17451	3.1477	0.0032
R-Square	0.53580		
Adjusted R-Square	0.51105		

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

Global Research Journal of Business Management

Vol. 4, No. 1: 12 - 28, 2024

RELATING ENTREPRENEURIAL INNOVATION AND SMALL AND MEDIUM SCALE ENTERPRISES

Source: Researcher's Computation Using SPSS, 24

The F-statistic which is used to examine the overall significance of regression model showed that the result is significant, as indicated by the high value of the F-statistic, 9.86 and it is significant at the 5.0 per cent level. That is, the F-statistic P-value of 0.000 is less than 0.05.

The coefficient of determination (R-square), used to measure the goodness to fit of the estimated model, indicates that the model is reasonably fit in prediction. The (R-square) value of 0.5358 shows that entrepreneurial innovation model have a good fit. It indicates that about 53.58 per cent of the variation in SMEs performance is explained by product and process innovation, while the remaining unaccounted variation of 46.42 percent is captured by the error term.

Test of Hypothesis One:

H01: There is no significant relationship between Product Innovation and SME performance in Cross River State.

From regression result in Table 4, the t-value for the impact of Product Innovation on performance of SMEs in Cross River State is 2.84; with an associated p-value of 0.0111. Since the p-value (of 0.0111) is less than 0.05 used as the level of significance, we reject the null hypothesis (H01) and conclude that there is a significant relationship between product innovation and SME performance in Cross River State.

Test of Hypothesis Two:

H02: There is no significant relationship between Process innovation and SME performances in Cross River State.

Lastly, from the regression result presented above, the Process innovation t-value was found to be 3.147, with an associated Probability Value of 0.003. The Probability Value of 0.003 is less than the alpha value of 0.05 (under 5% confidence level), we thus reject the second null hypothesis and conclude that there is a significant relationship between Process innovation and SME performance in Cross River State.

Discussion of Results

The study showed that Product Innovation has a significant relationship with SMEs performance. As constant changes are made on the product in-line with market trends, prompt provision of services and product to customers, being sensitive to innovations and inventions relevant to satisfy clients have all made the market share of the SMEs to be on a regular and consistent increase. The innovation in product is an important way in the economic efficiency of the high technology companies. This agrees with the results of Lehtimaki (2011) whose findings showed that on average, the contribution of innovated new products was more to total sales than to profits. More so, Lumiste (2014) found that innovation effects were felt in terms of both product-oriented results

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

Global Research Journal of Business Management

Vol. 4, No. 1: 12 - 28, 2024

RELATING ENTREPRENEURIAL INNOVATION AND SMALL AND MEDIUM SCALE ENTERPRISES

such as: improvement in quality of goods and services, and secondly, increased range on goods and services, and process-oriented results like increased production capacity and improved production flexibility. Miller and Floricel (2004) argue that a firm is able to achieve a high level of business performance by adapting capabilities and practices to the different requirements of value creation and innovation (i.e., competitive and technological contexts) in which it has selected to compete.

Secondly, it was observed from the analysis that, process innovation has a significant relationship on SMEs performance. The available resource base of small firms such as management, funding, and technology, significantly enhances their ability to scan, analyze, and respond to major environmental challenges (Bismuth, 2017). The result supports the findings of Cainelli (2014) and Regev (2008) whose study revealed that process innovation of small firms had higher labour productivity and sales growth than non-innovating firms. Engel (2014), similarly found that sales turnover of process innovative firms grew faster than that of non-innovative firms. They detected a significant relationship between the share of process innovative sales and sales turnover change of firms. Auken, (2008) findings further showed that process innovation which involves investments in technology that reduce fixed costs lead to higher profits and improve the productivity of the firm.

Summary of Findings

This research examined the effect of entrepreneurial innovation on SMEs performance in Cross River State Nigeria, using the binary regression method of data analysis, the descriptive research design was also adopted for this study. A structured questionnaire was administered to 265 SMEs in Ikom, Ogoja and Etung local government areas of Cross River State. Measurement for performance of the dependent variable is SME performance with proxy: sales and turn over shares. The independent variable used in this study is entrepreneurial innovation with proxy: product and process innovation. Findings from the study showed that product and process innovation have significant relationship with SMEs performance in Cross River state. More so, since product and process innovations are positive in the findings, the researcher recommends that further research on other forms of innovation should be carried out as it affects SMEs in other region of Nigeria.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMEDATIONS

Conclusion

The researcher conducted a study on the effect of entrepreneurial innovation on small and medium enterprises performance in Nigeria using Cross River State as a case study.

The study shows that innovation with its proxy of products and process has a positive and significant effect or relationship with SMEs performance in Cross River state. Entrepreneurial

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

Global Research Journal of Business Management Vol. 4, No. 1: 12 - 28, 2024

RELATING ENTREPRENEURIAL INNOVATION AND SMALL AND MEDIUM SCALE ENTERPRISES

Innovation is thus important for SMEs and firms to remain competitive for business growth and performance. The ability of SMEs to better perform and obtain growth within a determined time period can be established by its innovative capabilities and therefore, open mind, open learning, open innovation to enhance the capability of independent innovation is the key to open innovation for SMEs. The results highlighted the need to support innovation among SMEs for sustainable growth.

Recommendations

The study thus recommends that SMEs can further enhance a higher business growth or performance by particularly selecting their operating markets, focusing on particular product groups and innovation types, avoiding spread of marketing activities, trying to avoid markets dominated by large firms, and considering economic situations in introducing newer products. Entrepreneurial innovation brings a wide range of benefits and advantages, including adaptation to market changes, a competitive edge, attraction of talent and investment, resilience and future readiness, expansion into new markets, and environmental sustainability. Real-world examples demonstrate how innovation has propelled companies to success, transformed industries, and made a positive impact on society and the environment.

In addition, SMEs must prioritize their process innovations by changing their business models, to suit the ever-changing environment. To achieve this, they must become more internationalized, upgrade the quality of their human capital, and adopt more Information Technology solutions so as to improve their performance. In conclusion, since both process and product innovation are positive from the findings in Cross River State, we recommend that further study be carried out in other forms of innovations as it affects SMEs in South South, Nigeria.

References

- Adner, R., & Levinthal, D. (2001). Demand heterogeneity and technology evolution: Implications for product and process innovation. *Management Science*, 47(5), 611-628.
- Adams, R., Bessant, J., & Phelps, R. (2006). Innovation management measure: A review. *International Journal of Management Reviews*, 8(1), 21-47.
- Ahmed, M. U. (2016). A theoretical framework for analysing the growth and sustainability of small and medium enterprises (SMEs). *International Journal of SME Development*, 1(2), 1-22.

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

Global Research Journal of Business Management Vol. 4, No. 1: 12 - 28, 2024

RELATING ENTREPRENEURIAL INNOVATION AND SMALL AND MEDIUM SCALE ENTERPRISES

Arowomole, K. A. (2000). *Modern business management (theory and practice) (1st ed.)*. Sango-Ota: Ade-Oluyinka Commercial Press.

Atuahene-Gima, K. (1996). Market orientation and innovation. *Journal of Business Research*, 35(2), 93-103.

Bahago, F. J. (2015). *Contribution of small and medium enterprises development agency of Nigeria (SMEDAN) to the growth and development of micro, small and medium enterprises in Kaduna and Kano states (Unpublished doctoral thesis)*. Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria.

Banji O. O. (2017) *Small and Medium Scale Enterprises: Issues and Prospects*

Basil, R.A., and Markman, G.D. (2003).” Beyond social capital: the role of entrepreneurs’ social competence in their financial success” *Journal of Business Venturing*, 18(1), 41-60.

Baker, K. A. (2002). *Innovation Science, Communication: Management benchmark study (pp.1-16)*. Air War College. Retrieved from <http://au.af.mil/AU/AWC/awcgate/doe/benchmark/index.htm>

Bismuth, A., & Tojo, Y. (2017). Creating value from intellectual assets. *Journal of Intellectual Capital*, 9(2), 228–245.

Carlson, C., & Wilmot, W. W. (2006). *Innovation: The five disciplines for creating what customers want*. New York: Crown Business.

Carlsson, B. (1996). The rise of small business: causes and consequences. In W. J. Adams (Ed.), *Singular Europe, economy and policy of the European Union after 1992*. Ann Arbor: University of Michigan Press.

De Wit, B., & Meyer, R. (2007). *Strategy synthesis: resolving strategy paradoxes to create competitive advantage*. London: Cengage Learning.

Durantou, G., & Puga, D. (2001). Nursery cities: Urban diversity, process innovation, and the life cycle of products. *American Economic Review*, 91(5), 1454-1477

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

Global Research Journal of Business Management Vol. 4, No. 1: 12 - 28, 2024

RELATING ENTREPRENEURIAL INNOVATION AND SMALL AND MEDIUM SCALE ENTERPRISES

- Ettlie, J. E., & Reza, E. M. (1992). Organizational integration and process innovation. *Academy of Management Journal*, 35(4), 795-827.
- OECD. (2005). Oslo manual: Proposed guidelines for collecting and interpreting technological innovation data. Paris: Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development.
- O'Sullivan, D., & Dooley, L. (2009). Applying innovation. Thousand Oaks: SAGE Publication Inc.
- Olson, E. M., Walker Jr, O. C., & Ruekert, R. W. (1995). Organizing for effective new product development: The moderating role of product innovativeness. *The Journal of Marketing*, 59(1), 48-62.
- Polder, M., Leeuwen, G.V., Mohnen, P., & Raymond, W. (2010). Product, process and organizational innovation: drivers, complementarity and productivity effects: UNU-MERIT, Maastricht Economic and Social Research and Training Centre on Innovation and Technology.
- Roberts, P. W. (1999). Product innovation, product-market competition and persistent profitability in the US pharmaceutical industry. *Strategic Management Journal*, 20(7), 655-670.
- SMEDAN. (2012). Small and medium enterprises performance in Nigeria. African Entrepreneurship Seminar. Essex: University of Essex Scientific Committee on Entrepreneurship.
- Lawal, S. (2017). Effect of entrepreneurial competencies on small and medium enterprises (SMES) performance in Abuja FCT (unpublished doctoral thesis).
- Nwankwo, O. C., & Njogo, B. O. (2013). The effect of electricity supply on industrial production within the Nigerian economy (1970 – 2010). *Journal of Energy Technologies and Policy*, 3(4), 34-42.
- Wiklund A. (2009). Appraising innovation and firm's performance of some selected firms in Kumasi. *Journal of business education* 4(2), 11-24.
- Zarah A. (2016), *The Effects of Innovative Capabilities and R&D Clustering on Firm Performance*
- Zwingina, C. T., & Opusunju, I. M. (2017). Impact of innovation on the performance of small and medium scale enterprise in Gwagwalada, Abuja. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Development, Education and Science Research*, 4(1), 31-45.

Factors that Inhibit Consumption of Family Planning Products: Evidence from a Developing Country

Kenechi John Onyeke¹, Grace Ifeoma Anukwe¹, Jude Eze¹, Chiemelie Benneth Iloka^{1*}

¹Department of Marketing,
Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu,
Nigeria.

*Email: Iloka.benneth@esut.edu.ng

Abstract

Family planning (FP) is embedded in the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) as a critical mechanism in terms of attainment of SDGs 3.7 and 5.6 that focus on curtailment of population explosion and maternal and child mortality rates. In many developing Sub-Saharan African countries, inhibitory factors concerning the usage of family planning products, especially among underserved rural dwellers, remain poorly understood. Thus, this paper seeks to deepen understanding regarding those barriers that frustrate the uptake of family planning products among rural dwellers of reproductive age. Data were generated with a self-administered questionnaire from 250 respondents. Convenience and judgmental sampling procedures were used to recruit respondents. Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) using Analysis of Moment Structures (AMOS) serves as the analytical tool regarding the hypothesised paths in the research model. Findings from the study reveal that access to FP knowledge and information has a negative and significant effect on the usage of family planning products. Additionally, religion and cultural norms, experience and fear of side effects, and quality of reproductive healthcare services have a positive-significant inhibitory influence on the usage of family planning products. The management and policy implications of those findings were examined, and directions for future research and actions were suggested.

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

Global Research Journal of Business Management

Vol. 4, No. 1: 29 - 47, 2024

FACTORS THAT INHIBIT CONSUMPTION OF FAMILY PLANNING PRODUCTS

Keywords: Family planning products, Rural women, Usage, Inhibitors, Reproductive age, developing economy.

1. Introduction

The concept of family planning (FP) is vital for achieving Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) 3.7 and 5.6, which aim to improve maternal and child health and empower women. FP helps reduce maternal and child mortality rates, prevent unsafe abortions, and address unintended pregnancies (United Nations, 2015; Eliason et al., 2013; Cates et al., 2010; Sachs & McArthur, 2005).

SDG 3.7 focuses on ensuring universal access to sexual and reproductive healthcare services, including FP, while SDG 5.6 targets the eradication of violence against women and girls (World Health Organisation, 2023; United Nations Population Fund, 2023). Achieving these goals requires collaborative efforts to enhance healthcare infrastructure, broaden access to services, promote education and awareness, and address social and cultural barriers (World Health Organisation, 2023; United Nations Population Fund, 2023).

FP is crucial for curbing population growth, reducing maternal and child mortality rates, and promoting gender equality (Cleland et al., 2006; Starbird et al., 2016; Bongaarts et al., 2012). Contraceptive methods, including condoms, play a significant role in preventing pregnancies and sexually transmitted infections (Eliason et al., 2013; Cates et al., 2010; Sachs & McArthur, 2005).

In Africa, including Nigeria, efforts to promote FP services have increased awareness, but there is still a high demand for these services (Varrella, 2020). The prevalence of modern contraceptive use varies across African countries, with Nigeria experiencing a significant unmet need for FP products (Cahill et al., 2018). Nigeria's high population growth rate underscores the importance of continued efforts to ensure universal access to sexual and reproductive healthcare services and address violence against women and girls (Ventura, 2021; National Population Commission, 2018).

In view of the above, this study is founded on the following objectives:

- i. To assess the extent of availability and access of sexual and reproductive healthcare services in Nigeria, and the influence on consumption of family planning products.
- ii. To determine the extent of information and education about family planning products, and the influence of such on consumption of FPPs.
- iii. To assess whether reproductive health is incorporated into national strategies and programs, and the influence of such on consumption of family planning products.

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

Global Research Journal of Business Management

Vol. 4, No. 1: 29 - 47, 2024

FACTORS THAT INHIBIT CONSUMPTION OF FAMILY PLANNING PRODUCTS

- iv. To determine the extent to which girls are exposed to violence (such as trafficking, sexual exploitation, and other harmful practices), and the influence of such on consumption of family planning products.

2. Review of Related Literature and Hypotheses Proposition

Unchecked population growth in Nigeria could strain the country's economy and public infrastructure, leading to higher family budgets and compromising the quality of livelihoods for households, as proposed by the quality-quantity trade-off theory (Drabo, 2020; Becker & Lewis, 1973; Hotz, 1997). Family planning has been recognised as vital for health, social, and economic development, yet restrictive abortion laws push women towards unsafe abortion methods, emphasising the need for reproductive governance focused on family planning (Grimes et al., 2006; Storeng & Ouattara, 2014; Morgan & Roberts, 2012; El Kotni & Singer, 2019). Reproductive governance in Nigeria aims to increase modern contraceptive prevalence but faces challenges in compliance due to various factors, including cultural norms (Adebowale & Onyeji, 2020; Johnson-Hanks, 2002; Guillaume, 2006). Research indicates low contraceptive usage, particularly among rural women, highlighting the need to address barriers to family planning access and uptake in underserved communities (Eliason et al., 2013; National Population Commission, 2018; Baxerres et al., 2018; Beson et al., 2018; Apanga & Adams, 2015; Ebu et al., 2018; Asiedu et al., 2020; Aviisah et al., 2018). This study aims to explore factors inhibiting family planning product usage among underserved rural women of reproductive age to inform policy, intervention, and marketing strategies (National Population Commission, 2018; Ahmed et al., 2014; Shah et al., 1998).

2.1.1. Access to family planning Knowledge/information and services

Previous research highlights the impact of FP information and service awareness on FP uptake (Lauria et al., 2014; Malini & Narayanan, 2014), with community-level media messages enhancing contraceptive usage (Stephenson et al., 2007; Wang et al., 2013). However, a study across 21 African nations found mixed results, with media message exposure positively correlated with contraceptive use in two countries but negatively in nineteen (Elfstrom & Stephenson, 2012), warranting further investigation. Similarly, knowledge of FP has not consistently correlated with FPP usage (Apanga & Adams, 2015; Beson et al., 2018; Eliason et al., 2014; Osaro et al., 2017), and patient counselling often lacks depth (Malini & Narayanan, 2014). In Nigeria, various channels, including radio, television, print/social media, advocacy, and word-of-mouth, disseminate FP knowledge to women of reproductive age. Given these findings, this study hypothesises:

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

Global Research Journal of Business Management

Vol. 4, No. 1: 29 - 47, 2024

FACTORS THAT INHIBIT CONSUMPTION OF FAMILY PLANNING PRODUCTS

H1: Access to FP knowledge/information inhibits usage of FPP.

2.1.2. Religious and Cultural Norms

Interpretation of religion in relation to FP is diverse among Catholics, Protestants, and Muslims (Schenker, 2000; Weaver, 2018; Gudorf, 2011; Albrecht, 2011; Shaikh, 2011; Serour, 2013; Dardir & Ahmed, 1981; Varley, 2012). Notwithstanding, research implicates religious inclinations as a major constraint to the uptake of FP services in Africa (Gaetano et al., 2014; Odimegwu et al., 2005). Also, in a study conducted in Nepal (Bhatt et al., 2021), religion and cultural norms were identified as a strong barrier in terms of the usage of FPPs.

Many people in SSA nations are religion-obsessed (Sundararajan et al., 2019). Sundararajan et al., based on randomised trials, demonstrate that religious leaders have the capacity to influence the health behaviour of their followers, culminating in acceptance or avoidance of health-related issues (Downs et al., 2017). Nonetheless, there is increasing evidence of a desire to access reproductive healthcare (e.g., FPPs) in a Sub-Saharan African (SSA) context, regardless of religious inclination (Krehbiel-Keefe, 2006; Mosha & Ruben, 2013; Hallfors et al., 2016; Yeatman & Trinitapoli, 2008). In a recent study by Cannon et al. (2021), the influence of religious leaders positively informed the usage of FPPs. This finding suggests that support from some religious leaders helps to mitigate the effects of religious doctrine on the uptake of FPPs. Thus, this research hypothesised that:

H2: Religious and cultural norms inhibit the usage of FPP.

2.1.3. Fear and Experience of Side-Effects

The likely side-effects of modern forms of FPPs have been shown to be a common predictor of the decision to purchase or to discontinue the uptake of FPP (Schrumpf et al., 2020; Kabagenyi et al., 2014). In several investigations, fear and potential side-effects are critical considerations undermining the usage of modern contraceptives among women of reproductive age with unmet needs in Africa, Asia, and Latin America (Sedgh & Hussain, 2014; Staveteig, 2017; Schrumpf et al., 2020). The side-effects that were more pronounced were menstrual disorders, with specific reference to the absence of menstruation as caused by hormonal issues, fattening, and others related to the use of FPPs (Staveteig, 2017). Similarly, Di Crosta et al. (2021), in a study conducted in Italy among women aged 18–64, report that fear and experience of side effects are critical considerations in the consumption of FPPs. This finding indicates that among the participating Italians, consumers are worried about the likely side effects that may be associated with the usage of FPPs. Additionally, Staveteig, Shrestha, Gurung, and Kampa (2018) confirm a positive relationship between fear and likely side-effects as barriers to FPP use in Eastern Nepal. However,

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

Global Research Journal of Business Management

Vol. 4, No. 1: 29 - 47, 2024

FACTORS THAT INHIBIT CONSUMPTION OF FAMILY PLANNING PRODUCTS

the explanation for these underlying reasons still evades clearer understanding (Staveteig, 2017). Thus, this study hypothesises that:

H3: Fear and experience of side-effects inhibit uptake of FPPs.

2.1.4. Quality of reproductive healthcare services

In clinical contraception, the ability of health personnel to provide excellent service quality potentially fuels the desire to accept many health services, including FPPs. Quality of reproductive health services expressly roughly in terms of facilities available, application of facilities professionally, emotional support and interactions that delight patients, trigger emotional stability, and somewhat lay a solid foundation for repeat visits to the service delivery point and positive word-of-mouth communication about the health personnel, health facility, and health services rendered such FP. In a study conducted in Uttar Pradesh, India (Dey et al., 2021), to determine the effect of the quality of healthcare services on contraceptive uptake, it was found that the quality of healthcare counselling has a positive and significant correlation with the decision of clients to use contraceptives. Similarly, several studies in other countries demonstrate a strong link between the overall quality of health services and the uptake of modern contraceptives (e.g., FPPs) (Akamike, Okedo-Alex, Nze, Ezeanosike, & Uneke, 2020; Silumbwe et al. (2018); Casterline & Sinding, 2004). Indeed, the experience that clients receive when obtaining care is an important predictor of their decision to reuse such service(s) in the future; it also has an influence on the care-seeking behaviour of other members of the healthcare community (Creel, Sass, Yinger, 2002). In essence, the correlation between the quality of healthcare services and the uptake of family planning products isn't the only thing that influences purchase decisions; it extends to repurchase and recommendation decisions. The quality of health services obtained differs markedly between privately-owned and publicly-owned health facilities in various countries; private health facilities were found to provide superior health services (World Health Organisation, 2011). Based on this narration, this study hypothesises that:

H4: Quality of reproductive healthcare services inhibit the uptake of FPPs.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

FACTORS THAT INHIBIT CONSUMPTION OF FAMILY PLANNING PRODUCTS

The adopted conceptual framework for this study is illustrated in Figure 1, and it is based on the reviewed literature. It is conceptualised in this work that access to family planning knowledge, information, and services, religious and cultural norms, fear or experience of side effects, and quality of reproductive healthcare services are the independent variables, while the dependent variable is usage of FPPs.

3. Materials and methods

3.1. Target population and Sample

The study sampled 272 underserved women of reproductive age (18+) using statistical methods for an unknown population (Omair, 2014). Conducted in 15 health centres across Igbo-Eze North, Udenu, and Enugu-East Local Government Areas, Enugu, Nigeria, five centres were selected from each area. Participants were chosen proportionally to client traffic, ensuring representativeness. Participation was voluntary, and confidentiality was assured.

3.2. Questionnaire design and administration

The questionnaire comprised two sections: Section A measured the research constructs, while Section B gathered respondent profiles. Utilising a five-point Likert format, with 5 indicating strong agreement and 1 indicating strong disagreement, the questionnaire ensured robust data quality (Simms et al., 2019; Revilla et al., 2014). Filter questions restricted participation to women aged 18–41 with at least one child, a range commonly recognised as reproductive age. Face validity was confirmed by consumer behavior experts, with pilot testing involving 35 potential respondents to refine the questionnaire (Hair et al., 2010). With a reliability index of 0.810, exceeding the acceptable threshold of 0.7, the 25-item questionnaire demonstrated internal consistency and reliability (Nunnally & Bernstein, 1994). Convenience and judgmental sampling methods were

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

Global Research Journal of Business Management

Vol. 4, No. 1: 29 - 47, 2024

FACTORS THAT INHIBIT CONSUMPTION OF FAMILY PLANNING PRODUCTS

employed, with questionnaire distribution on antenatal and immunisation days in health facilities. Three trained female research assistants facilitated questionnaire administration, with male team members ensuring adherence to research ethics. Out of 272 questionnaires administered, 250 usable responses were analysed due to incomplete or duplicate entries.

3.3. Measures

Previously validated scales in the extant literature provided the sources for the measurement items used in this investigation. Therefore, scales used to measure independent (IV) and dependent variables (DV) were adapted thus: access to family planning information and services (Jain et al. 2021; Apanga et al. 2021; Okigbo et al. 2018), religious and cultural norms (Krehbiel-Keefe, 2006; Mosha & Ruben, 2013; Hallfors et al. 2016), fear and experience of side effects (Cannon et al. 2021; Bhatt et al. 2021), quality of reproductive healthcare services (Dey et al. 2021), and consumption of family planning products (Di Crosta et al. 2021; Schrupf et al. 2020).

4. Data analysis and results

4.1. Respondents' Demographic Variables

Analysis of the respondents' demographic variables shows that respondents aged between 18 and 23 account for 21%, and those within 24 and 29 years represent 32%. The majority of the respondents (92) are aged 30–35 years old. Respondents aged 36–41 were 10%. Additionally, 184 (74%) of the respondents agree that they have heard about family planning products before. In terms of the types of family planning products used in the past, the majority have used condoms (78%), pills, and injections (22%), respectively, while counselling services were rendered to 11 (4%).

4.2. Measurement model assessment

The psychometric properties of the scales were evaluated to confirm measurement reliability and validity, as shown in Table 1. Single factorial analyses were conducted to assess convergent validity, with the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) coefficient (0.72) and Bartlett's test confirming model suitability. Varimax rotation demonstrated item discrimination, affirming data unidimensionality (Gerbing & Anderson, 1988). Convergent validity was established through significant item-factor relationships ($p < 0.001$), standardised loadings exceeding 0.65, Cronbach's alphas surpassing 0.70, composite reliability exceeding 0.60, and average variance extracted values surpassing 0.5 (Tavakol & Dennick, 2011; Bagozzi & Yi, 1988; Dunn et al., 2014; Fornell & Larcker, 1981). Multifactorial solutions, including discriminant validity, indicated no common method bias, as corroborated by Harman's test (Podsakoff et al., 2003).

Table 1: Measurement assessment

FACTORS THAT INHIBIT CONSUMPTION OF FAMILY PLANNING PRODUCTS

Factor	Validity		Reliability		
	Factorial load	KMO & B's	C's Alpha	CR	Ave
Access to information	.925	.72**	.725	.76	.68
Religious and cultural norms	.888	One factor solution	.755	.78	.54
Fear of side effects	.937		.707	.87	.69
Quality of reproductive healthcare services	.925		.814	.93	.82
Consumption of family planning products	.657		.739	.89	.67

KMO: Kaiser–Meyer–Olkin coefficient; B's: Bartlett's test p-value (asterisks show the sig. for this test); C's alpha: Cronbach's alpha; CR: composite reliability; AVE: average variance extracted. **p-value ≤ 0.01

The path structural equation modelling (SEM) model (Figure 2) demonstrates a good fit to the data and affirms convergent-discriminant validity with high positive standardised measurement weights. Collinearity among the four factors influencing family planning product consumption suggests independence among these dimensions, a common occurrence in the behavioural sciences (Edwards, 2001; Polites et al., 2012). To further confirm measurement validity, a confirmatory SEM measurement model with collinear relationships was executed, yielding statistically significant measurement weights. Absolute index results were acceptable, with a χ^2/df value of 2.43 and an RMSEA value of 0.050 (Wheaton et al., 1977; Hooper et al., 2008; MacCallum et al., 1996). Baseline fit coefficients were highly satisfactory, with NFI, IFI, and CFI values of 0.98, 0.97, and 0.97, respectively (Hooper et al., 2008).

Figure 2: Results (standardized coefficients)

FACTORS THAT INHIBIT CONSUMPTION OF FAMILY PLANNING PRODUCTS

To test the proposed hypotheses and theoretical model (Figure 1), SEM was conducted using the maximum likelihood method. Inspection of variables revealed low skewness and kurtosis, indicating fairly appropriate data normality. The robustness of the SEM model, based on rescaled coefficients and no missing data, ensures reliable results even with recorded independence between exogenous variables (Benson & Fleishman, 1994; Savalei, 2008). Empirical estimates for the model's main effects are presented in Table 3 and Figure 2, demonstrating a good fit for the data. Absolute fit indexes, including a significant χ^2 value of 542.3 (213 df), show a normed/relative chi-square ratio ($\chi^2/df = 2.43$) below the benchmark value of 5 (Wheaton et al., 1977). Additionally, the RMSEA (= 0.050) is below the recommended maximum of 0.08 (MacCallum et al., 1996), and baseline fit coefficients (NFI = 0.98; IFI = 0.97; NNFI = 0.97; CFI = 0.96) exceed the recommended threshold of 0.9 (Hooper et al., 2008).

Table 2: Testing Relationships

Hypothesis	Proposed structural relationships	Standardized path coefficient	Decision		
H1	Access to information → Consumption of family planning products	-.26**	Accepted		
H2	Religious and cultural norms → Consumption of family planning products	.33**	Accepted		
H3	Fear of side effects → Consumption of family planning products	.30**	Accepted		
H4	Quality of reproductive healthcare services → Consumption of family planning products	.28**	Accepted		
Goodness of fit indicators					
X ² /DF	RMSEA	NFI	CFI	IFI	NNFI
2.43	0.050	.98	.97	.97	.96

RMSEA: root mean square error of approximation; NFI: Bentler–Bonett normed fit index; CFI: comparative fit index; IFI: Bollen incremental fit index; NNFI: Bentler–Bonett non-normed fit index; NS: statistically nonsignificant. **p-value ≤ 0.001 .

All four relationships that were tested within this statistical model and its related data were accepted (Figure 2). As Table 3 indicates, the path coefficients obtained were highest for socio-cultural and religious norms as inhibitors of consumption of family planning products. Also, high coefficients were found for fear of side effects and quality of reproductive healthcare services as inhibitors of consumption of family planning products. What this does show is that there is a strong direct effect of these factors on the decision of reproductive women to consume family planning products. However, access to information shows a negative coefficient, and while direct, it does

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

Global Research Journal of Business Management

Vol. 4, No. 1: 29 - 47, 2024

FACTORS THAT INHIBIT CONSUMPTION OF FAMILY PLANNING PRODUCTS

yield a significant negative outcome (as access to information will considerably inhibit consumption of family planning products). Overall, the statistical model does show a considerable level of explanation regarding the influence of the independent variables on the dependent variable (consumption of family planning products) of 42% ($r^2 = 0.42$).

5. Discussions

5.1. Management/practice and policy implications

This study investigates factors inhibiting the optimal use of family planning products (FPPs) among underserved rural women of reproductive age. AMOS-SEM was employed for data analysis, revealing a surprising negative relationship between access to FP information and FPP uptake, contrary to prior literature (Lauria et al., 2014; Malini & Narayanan, 2014; Stephenson et al., 2007; Wang et al., 2013), yet consistent with some recent findings (Apanga & Adams, 2015; Beson et al., 2018; Osaro et al., 2017). Potential explanations include negative attitudes towards FPPs due to perceived loss of sexual pleasure and the social stigma associated with FPP use in rural communities. Coordinated advocacy involving traditional leaders could mitigate these barriers. Religious and cultural norms were found to positively inhibit FPP consumption, aligning with existing research (Bhatt et al., 2021; Weaver, 2018; Gaetano et al., 2014; Gudorf, 2011; Albrecht, 2011), though diverging from other studies (Downs et al., 2017; Cannon et al., 2021; Hallfors et al., 2016). Fear of side effects was identified as another influential factor, consistent with prior research (Di Crosta et al., 2021; Schruppf et al., 2020; Staveteig et al., 2018). To address these concerns, FP services should be provided exclusively by trained medical personnel to minimize fear and side effects. Additionally, the study confirms a positive relationship between the quality of reproductive healthcare services and FPP usage, echoing previous findings (Akamike et al., 2020; Silumbwe et al., 2018). Ensuring quality reproductive healthcare services, regardless of setting, is crucial for promoting FPP uptake among rural women of reproductive age, considering the cultural significance of reproduction in African societies like Nigeria.

5.2. Limitations and direction for future studies

This study's geographic scope is limited to three local government areas, potentially affecting the generalizability of findings to all women of reproductive age in Nigeria. Future research could expand to include all four geopolitical zones and the federal capital territory, Abuja, for broader insights into barriers to FPP uptake. Additionally, conducting comparative studies among different religious groups (Catholics, Pentecostals, Muslims, Non-affiliated) may elucidate where constraints are most pronounced, informing targeted strategies. Furthermore, the exclusion of male respondents overlooks their significant influence on female FPP utilization in Nigerian society, highlighting the need for their inclusion in future studies.

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

Global Research Journal of Business Management

Vol. 4, No. 1: 29 - 47, 2024

FACTORS THAT INHIBIT CONSUMPTION OF FAMILY PLANNING PRODUCTS

5.3. Conclusion

A sizeable number of women of reproductive age in rural settings are aware of the existence of FPPs. However, FPPs' uptake among rural dwellers is overwhelmingly constrained by access to information, religious and cultural norms, fear and potential side-effects, and the quality of reproductive health services in diverse health facilities. To bolster FPPs uptake exponentially, the co-option of traditional rulers as the custodians of cultural value and ethos and town union presidents as representatives of villages and communities and clergies to educate rural dwellers on the benefits of FPPs in order to drastically dilute cultural and religious misgivings about FPPs usage is necessary. Service quality upgrade through the deployment of skilled and professionally qualified medical personnel who are medically informed to provide services that will allay patients' concerns has become urgent.

References

- Adebowale, N., & Onyeji, E. (2020). Why Nigeria could not meet 2020 family planning target. Retrieved December 22, 2021 from: <https://www.premiumtimesng.com/news/headlines/421592-why-nigeria-could-not-meet-2020-family-planning-target.html>
- Ahmed, S., Li, Q., Liu, L., & Tsui, A. O. (2014). Maternal deaths averted by contraceptive use: An analysis of 172 countries. *Lancet*, 380, 111-125. DOI: 10.1016/S0140-6736(12)60478-4.
- Akamike, I. C., Okedo-Alex, I. N., Eze, I. I., Ezeanosike, O. B., & Uneke, C. J. (2020). Why does uptake of family planning services remain sub-optimal among Nigerian women? A systematic review of challenges and implications for policy. *Contraception and Reproductive Medicine* 5, 30. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40834-020-00133-6>
- Albrecht, G. H. (2011). Contraception and abortion within Protestant Christianity: The case for contraception and abortion in world religions. *Oxford Scholarship Online*, 79–104.
- Apanga, P., A., Adam, M. A., & Apanga, P. A. (2021). Factors influencing the uptake of family planning services in the Talensi District, Ghana. *Pan African Medical Journal*, 20(10). doi: [10.11604/pamj.2015.20.10.5301](https://doi.org/10.11604/pamj.2015.20.10.5301)
- Apanga, P.A., & Adams, M.A. (2015). Factors influencing the uptake of family planning services in the Talensi District Ghana. *Pan African Medical Journal*, 20.

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

Global Research Journal of Business Management

Vol. 4, No. 1: 29 - 47, 2024

FACTORS THAT INHIBIT CONSUMPTION OF FAMILY PLANNING PRODUCTS

- Asiedu, A., Asare, B.Y-A., Dwumfour-Asare, B., Baafi, D., Adam, A-R., Aryee, S.E., & Ganle, J. K. (2020). Determinants of modern contraceptive use: A cross-sectional study among market women in the Ashiaman Municipality of Ghana. *International Journal of African Nursing Sciences*, 12, 100184.
- Aviisah, P.A., Dery, S., Atsu, B.K., Yawson, A., Alotaibi, R.M., Rezk, H.R., et al. (2018). Modern contraceptive use among women of reproductive age in Ghana: Analysis of the 2003-2014 Ghana Demographic and Health Survey. *BMC Women's Health*, 18, 141.
- Bagozzi, R. P., & Yi, Y. (1988). On the evaluation of structural equation models. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 16(1), 74–94. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02723327>
- Baxerres, C., Boko, I., Konkobo, A., Ouattara, F., & Guillaume, A. (2018). Managing unwanted Pregnancies in Benin and Burkina Faso: Affective Situations and Popular Abortion Practices. Retrieved October 8, 2021 from Available online: <https://hal-amu.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-02065302/>.
- Becker, G. S., & Lewis, H. G. (1973). On the Interaction between the Quantity and Quality of Children. *Journal of political Economy*, 81(2, Part 2), S279-S288.
- Benson, J., & Fleishman, J. A. (1994). The robustness of maximum likelihood and distribution-free estimators to non-normality in confirmatory factor analysis. *Quality & Quantity*, 28(2), 117–136. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01102757>
- Beson, P., Appiah, R., & Adomah-Afari, A. (2018). Modern contraceptive use among reproductive aged-women in Ghana: Prevalence, predictors, and policy implications. *BMC Women's Health*, 18, 157.
- Bhatt, N., Bhatt, B., Neupane, B., Karki, A., Bhatta, T., Thapa, J., Basnet, L, B., & Budhathoki, S. S. (2021) Perceptions of family planning services and its key barriers among adolescents and young people in Eastern Nepal: A qualitative study. *PLoS ONE* 16(5), 1-15. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0252184>
- Bongaarts, J., Cleland, J., Townsend, J., W., Bertrand, J., T., & Das Gupta, M. (2012). Family Planning Programs for the 21st Century: Rationale and Design. New York: The Population Council, p 94.
- Cahill, N., Sonneveldt, E., Stover, J., Weinberger, M., Williamson, J., Wei., C., et al. (2018). Modern contraceptive use, unmet need, and demand satisfied among women of reproductive age who are married or in union in the focused countries of the family planning 2020

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

Global Research Journal of Business Management

Vol. 4, No. 1: 29 - 47, 2024

FACTORS THAT INHIBIT CONSUMPTION OF FAMILY PLANNING PRODUCTS

- initiatives: A systematic analysis using the family planning estimation tool, *Lancet*, 391, 870-882.
- Cannon, A. C., Manda, M., McGuire, C., Calhoun, L. M., Mumuni, T., & Speizer, I. S. (2021). A vignette-based approach to understanding social norms around family planning in three Nigerian cities. *Global Public Health*, 1-13. DOI: [10.1080/17441692.2021.1928261](https://doi.org/10.1080/17441692.2021.1928261)
- Casterline, J., B., & Sinding, S. W. (2004). Unmet need for family planning in developing countries and implications for population policy. *Population Development Review*, 26(4), 691–723. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1728-4457.2000.00691.x>
- Cates, W. J., Abdool Karim, Q., El-Sadr, W., Haffner, D. W., & Kalema-Zikusoka, G. (2010). Global development. Family planning and the millennium development goals. *Science*, 329, 1603.
- Cleland, J., S. Bernstein, E., Alex, A., Faundes, A., Glasier., & Innis, J. (2006). Family planning: The unfinished agenda. *The Lancet*, 368(9549), 1810-1827.
- Clements, S., Baschieri, A., Hennink, M., Madise, N., & Stephenson, R. (2003). Explaining areal variation in contraceptive use in east Africa. In UAPS. Tunis.
- Creel, L., Sass, J., & Yinger, N. (2002). Overview of quality of care in reproductive health: definitions and measurements of quality. No. 1. Population Council and Population Reference Bureau. New perspectives on quality of care. Mickle, Helena.
- Dardir, A. M., & Ahmed, W. (1981). Islam and birth planning: an interview with the grand mufti of Egypt. *Population Science*, 1–5. PMID 12339475.
- Dey, A. K., Averbach, S., Dixit, A., Chakraverty, A., Dehingia, N., Chandurkar, D., & Raj, A. (2021). Measuring quality of family planning counselling and its effects on uptake of contraceptives in public health facilities in Uttar Pradesh, India: A cross-sectional analysis. *PLoS ONE*, 16(5), e0239565. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0239565>
- Di Crosta, A., Ceccato, I., Marchetti, D., La Malva, P., Maiella, R., Cannito, L., Cipi, M., Mammarella, N., Palumbo, R., Verrocchio, M. C., Palumbo, R., & Di Domenico, A. (2021). Psychological factors and consumer behavior during the COVID-19 pandemic. *PLoS ONE*, 16(8), e0256095. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0256095>
- Downs, J. A., Mwakisole, A. H., Chandika, A. B., Lugoba, S., Kassim, R., Laizer E, et al. (2017). Educating religious leaders to promote uptake of male circumcision in Tanzania: A cluster

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

Global Research Journal of Business Management

Vol. 4, No. 1: 29 - 47, 2024

FACTORS THAT INHIBIT CONSUMPTION OF FAMILY PLANNING PRODUCTS

- randomised trial. *Lancet*, 389(10074), 1124–1132. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(16\)32055-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(16)32055-4).
- Drabo, S. (2020). Beyond ‘Family Planning’—Local Realities on Contraception and Abortion in Ouagadougou, Burkina Faso. *MDPI – Social Sciences*, 9(212), 1-15. Doi: 10.3390/socsci9110212
- Dunn, T. J., Baguley, T., & Brunnsden, V. (2014). From alpha to omega: A practical solution to the pervasive problem of internal consistency estimation. *British Journal of Psychology (London, England: 1953)*, 105(3), 399–412. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjop.12046>
- Ebu, N.El., Boateng, D.O., Pereko, K.A., & Hormenu, T. (2018). Determinants of contraceptive use among women of reproductive age in Asankragwa in the Western Region of Ghana. *International Journal of Nursing and Midwifery*, 2(1), 50-61.
- Edwards, J. R. (2001). Multidimensional constructs in organizational behavior research: An integrative analytical framework. *Organizational Research Methods*, 4(2), 144– 192. <https://doi.org/10.1177/109442810142004>
- El Kotni, M., & Singer, E. O. (2019). Human Rights and Reproductive Governance in Transnational Perspective. Abingdon: Taylor & Francis.
- Elfstrom, M., K., & Stephenson, R. (2012). The role of place in shaping contraceptive use among women in Africa. *PLoS One*, 7(7).
- Eliason, S., Baiden, F., Quansah-Asare, G., Graham-Hayfron, Y., Bonsu, D., Phillips, J., & Awusabo-Asare K. (2013). Factors influencing the intention of women in rural Ghana to adopt postpartum family planning. *Reprod Health [Online]*. Retrieved April 12, 2021 from: <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3724747/>.
- Fornell, C., & Larcker, D. F. (1981). Structural equation models with unobservable variables and measurement error: Algebra and statistics. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 18(3), 382–388. <https://doi.org/10.1177/002224378101800313>
- Gaetano, M., Lutuf, A., Zaake, D., & Annika, J. (2014). Predictors of contraceptive use among female adolescents in Ghana.? *African Journal of Reproductive Health*, 18(1), 102.
- Gerbing, D. W., & Anderson, J. C. (1988). An updated paradigm for scale development incorporating unidimensionality and its assessment. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 25(2), 186–192. <https://doi.org/10.1177/002224378802500207>

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

Global Research Journal of Business Management

Vol. 4, No. 1: 29 - 47, 2024

FACTORS THAT INHIBIT CONSUMPTION OF FAMILY PLANNING PRODUCTS

- Grimes, D. A., Benson, J., Singh, S., Romero, M., Ganatra, B., Friday, E. O., & Iqbal, H. S. (2006). Unsafe abortion: The preventable pandemic. *The Lancet*, 368, 1908–19. DOI:[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(06\)69481-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(06)69481-6)
- Gudorf, C. E. (2011). Contraception and abortion in Roman Catholicism. In: Maguire DC, editor. Sacred rights: the case for contraception and abortion in world religions. Oxford: Oxford Scholarship Online, 55–78.
- Guillaume, A. (2006). L'avortement en Afrique: Une Pratique Fréquente chez les Adolescentes?" Enfants d'Aujourd'hui, Diversité des Contextes, Pluralité des Parcours: Colloque International de Dakar, Paris: INED.
- Hair, J.F., Black, W.C., Babin, B.J., & Anderson, R.E. (2010). *Multivariate Data Analysis* (7th ed). Pearson Education
- Hallfors, D. D., Iritani, B. J., Zhang, L., Hartman, S., Luseno, W. K., Mpfu, E., Rusakaniko, S. (2016). "I thought if I marry the prophet I would not die": the significance of religious affiliation on marriage, HIV testing, and reproductive health practices among young married women in Zimbabwe. *SAHARA-J: Journal of Social Aspects of HIV/AIDS*, 13(1), 178–87. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17290376.2016.1245627>
- Hooper, D., Coughlan, J., & Mullen, M. (2008). Structural equation modelling: Guidelines for determining model fit. *Electronic Journal on Business Research Methods*, 6(1), 53–60.
- Hotz, V. J., Klerman, J. A., & Willis, R. J. (1997). The economics of fertility in developed countries. *Handbook of population and family economics*, 1, 275-347.
- Jain, M., Caplan, Y., Ramesh, B. M., Isac, S., Anand, P., Engl, E., Halli, S., Kemp, H., Blanchard, J., Gothwal, V., Namasivayam, V., Kumar, P., & Sgaier, S. K. (2021). Understanding drivers of family planning in rural northern India: An integrated mixed-methods approach. *PLoS ONE* 16(1), e0243854. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0243854>
- Johnson-Hanks, J. (2002). The lesser shame: Abortion among educated women in southern Cameroon. *Social Science & Medicine*, 55, 1337–49.
- Kabagenyi, A., Jennings, L., Reid, A., Nalwadda, G., Ntozi, J., & Atuyambe, L. (2014). Barriers to male involvement in contraceptive uptake and reproductive health services: A qualitative study of men and women's perceptions in two rural districts in Uganda. *Reproductive Health*, 11(1), 21.

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

Global Research Journal of Business Management

Vol. 4, No. 1: 29 - 47, 2024

FACTORS THAT INHIBIT CONSUMPTION OF FAMILY PLANNING PRODUCTS

- Krehbiel Keefe, S. (2006). Women do what they want: Islam and permanent contraception in northern Tanzania. *Social Science & Medicine*, 63(2), 418–29.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2005.12.005>
- Lauria, L., Donati, S., Spinelli, A., Bonciani, M., & Grandolfo, M. E. (2014). The effect of contraceptive counselling in the pre- and post-natal period on contraceptive use at three months after delivery among Italian and immigrant women. *Annali dell'Istituto Superiore di Sanità*, 50(1), 54-61.
- MacCallum, R. C., Browne, M. W., & Sugawara, H. M. (1996). Power analysis and determination of sample size for covariance structure modelling. *Psychological Methods*, 1(2), 130–149.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/1082-989X.1.2.130>
- Malini, B., & Narayanan, E. (2014). Unmet need for family planning among married women of reproductive age group in urban Tamil Nadu. *Journal of Family & Community Medicine*, 21(1), 53-5.
- Morgan, L. M., & Roberts, E. F. S. (2012). Reproductive governance in Latin America. *Anthropology & Medicine*, 19, 241–54.
- Mosha, I. H., & Ruben, R. (2013). Communication, knowledge, social network and family planning utilization among couples in Mwanza, Tanzania. *African Journal of Reproductive Health*, 17, 57–69.
- National Population Commission (2018). Nigeria: Demographic and Health Survey (2018). Retrieved May 20, 2021 from: <https://www.dhsprogram.com/pubs/pdf/FR359/FR359.pdf>
- Nunnally, J. C., & Bernstein, I. H. (1994). *Psychometric theory (3rd Ed.)*. New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Odimegwu, C. (2005). Influence of religion on adolescent sexual attitudes and behaviour among Nigerian University students: Affiliation or commitment? *African Journal of Reproductive Health*, 9(2), 125-140.
- Okigbo, C. C., Speizer, I. S., Domino, M. E., Curtis, S. L., Halpern, C. T., & Fotso, J. C. (2018). Gender norms and modern contraceptive use in urban Nigeria: A multilevel longitudinal study. *BMC Women's Health*, 18, Article 178. <https://doi:10.1186/s12905-018-0664-3>

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

Global Research Journal of Business Management

Vol. 4, No. 1: 29 - 47, 2024

FACTORS THAT INHIBIT CONSUMPTION OF FAMILY PLANNING PRODUCTS

- Osaro, B.O., Tobin-West, C.I., & Mezie-Okoye, M.M. (2017). Knowledge of modern contraceptives and their use among rural women of childbearing age in Rivers State Nigeria. *Annals of Tropical Medicine and Public Health*, 10, 1043-1048.
- Podsakoff, P. M., MacKenzie, S. B., Lee, J. Y., & Podsakoff, N. P. (2003). Common method biases in behavioral research: A critical review of the literature and recommended remedies. *The Journal of Applied Psychology*, 88(5), 879–903. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.88.5.879>
- Polites, G. L., Roberts, N., & Thatcher, J. (2012). Conceptualizing models using multidimensional constructs: A review and guidelines for their use. *European Journal of Information Systems*, 21(1), 22–48. <https://doi.org/10.1057/ejis.2011.10>
- Revilla, M.A., Saris, W.E., & Krosnick, J.A. (2014). Choosing the number of categories in agree-disagree scales. *Sociological Methods & Research*, 43 (1), 73-97.
- Sachs, J. D., & McArthur, J. W. (2005). The millennium project: a plan for meeting the millennium development goals. *Lancet*, 365(9456), 347-353.
- Savalei, V. (2008). Is the ML chi-square ever robust to nonnormality? A cautionary note with missing data. *Structural Equation Modeling: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 15(1), 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10705510701758091>
- Schenker, J. G. (2000). Women's reproductive health: Monotheistic religions perspectives. *International Journal of Gynaecology and Obstetrics*, 70(1), 77–86. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0020-7292\(00\)00225-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0020-7292(00)00225-3)
- Schrumpf, L. A., Stephens, M. J., Nsarko, N. E., Akosah, E., Baumgartner, J. N., Ohemeng-Dapaah, S., & Watt, M. H. (2020). Side effect concerns and their impact on women's uptake of modern family planning methods in rural Ghana: a mixed methods study. *BMC Women's Health* 20, 57. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12905-020-0885-0>
- Sedgh, G., & Hussain, R. (2014). Reasons for contraceptive non-use among women having unmet need for contraception in developing countries. *Studies in Family Planning*, 45(2), 151–69. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1728-4465.2014.00382.x>
- Sensoy, N., Korkut, Y., Akturan, S., Yilmaz, M., Tuz, C., & Tuncel, B. (2018). Factors Affecting the Attitudes of Women toward Family Planning. DOI: 10.5772/intechopen.73255.
- Serour, G. I. (2013). Ethical issues in human reproduction: Islamic perspectives. *Gynaecology Endocrinal*, 29(11), 949–52. <https://doi.org/10.3109/09513590.2013.825714>

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

Global Research Journal of Business Management

Vol. 4, No. 1: 29 - 47, 2024

FACTORS THAT INHIBIT CONSUMPTION OF FAMILY PLANNING PRODUCTS

- Shah, N., M., Shah, M., A., & Radovanovic, Z. (1998). Pattern of desired fertility and contraceptive use in Kuwait. *International Family Planning Perspectives*, 24(3), 133-138.
- Shaikh, S. (2011). Family planning, contraception, and abortion in Islam: undertaking Khilafah. In: Maguire DC, editor. *Sacred Rights: The Case for Contraception and Abortion in World Religions*: Oxford Scholarship Online, 105–28.
- Simms, L.J., Zelazny, K., Williams, T.F., & Bernstein, L. (2019). Does the number of response options matter? Psychometric perspectives using personality questionnaire data. *Psychological Assessment*, 31, 557-566.
- Starbird, E., Norton, M., & Marcus, R. (2016). Investing in Family Planning: Key to Achieving the Sustainable Development Goals. *Global Health: Science and Practice*, 4(2), 191-210. <https://doi.org/10.9745/GHSP-D-15-00374>
- Staveteig, S. (2017). Fear, opposition, ambivalence, and omission: Results from a follow-up study on unmet need for family planning in Ghana. *PLoS One*, 12(7), e0182076. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0182076>.
- Staveteig, S., Shrestha, N., Gurung, S., & Kampa, K. T. (2018). Barriers to Family Planning Use in Eastern Nepal: Results from a Mixed Methods Study. DHS Qualitative Research Studies No. 21. Rockville, Maryland, USA: ICF. Retrieved January 5, 2022 from <https://dhsprogram.com/pubs/pdf/QRS21/QRS21>.
- Stephenson, R., Baschieri, A., Clement, S., Hennink, M., & Madise, N. (2007). Contextual influences on modern contraceptive use in Sub-saharan Africa. *American Journal of Public Health*, 97(7), 1233-1240.
- Storeng, K. T., & Ouattara, F. (2014). The politics of unsafe abortion in Burkina Faso: The interface of local norms and global public health practice. *Global Public Health*, 9(8), 946-959. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17441692.2014.937828>
- Sundararajan, R., Yoder, L. M., Kihunrwa, A., Aristide, C., Kalluvya, S. E., Downs, D. J., Mwakisole, A. H., & Downs, J. A. (2019). How gender and religion impact uptake of family planning: results from a qualitative study in Northwestern Tanzania. *BMC Women's Health*, 19, 99. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12905-019-0802-6>
- Tavakol, M., & Dennick, R. (2011). Making sense of Cronbach's alpha. *International journal of medical education*, 2(1), 53–55. <https://doi.org/10.5116/ijme.4dfb.8dfd>

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

Global Research Journal of Business Management

Vol. 4, No. 1: 29 - 47, 2024

FACTORS THAT INHIBIT CONSUMPTION OF FAMILY PLANNING PRODUCTS

- United Nations, (2015). Transforming our world: the 2030 agenda for Sustainable Development. http://www.un.org/ga/search/view_doc.asp?symbol=A/RES/70/1&Lang=E (accessed 21/1/2022)
- Varley, E. (2012). Islamic logics, reproductive rationalities: family planning in northern Pakistan. *Anthropology & Medicine*, 19(2), 189–206. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13648470.2012.675044>
- Varrella, S. (2020). Population of Nigeria in selected years between 1950 and 2020. Retrieved May 20, 2021 from: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1122838/population-of-nigeria/>
- Ventura, L. (2021). Poorest Countries in the World 2021. Retrieved May 20, 2021 from: <https://www.gfmag.com/global-data/economic-data/the-poorest-countries-in-the-world>
- Wang, W., Alva, S., Winter, R., & Bugert, C. (2013). Contextual influences of modern contraceptive use among rural women in Rwanda and Nepal. DHS Analytic studies no. 14. Washington DC USA: USAID.
- Weaver, D. F. (2018). Birth Control. In: Green JB, Lapsley JE, Miles R, Verhey A, editors. Dictionary of Scripture and Ethics [Internet]. pp. 101–3. Retrieved August 12, 2021 from: <https://corp.credoreference.com/component/booktracker/edition/7367.html>.
- Wheaton, B., Muthen, B., Alwin, D. F., & Summers, G. F. (1977). Assessing reliability and stability in panel models. *Sociological Methodology*, 8(1), 84–136.85. 4 <https://doi.org/10.2307/2707>
- World Health Organization (2011). Quality of care in the provision of sexual and reproductive health services. Retrieved October 10, 2021 from: https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/44343/9789241501897_eng.pdf
- Yeatman, S. E., & Trinitapoli, J. (2008). Beyond denomination: the relationship between religion and family planning in rural Malawi. *Demographic Research*, 19(55), 1851–82. Doi: 10.4054/DemRes.2008.19.55
- Yue, K., O'Donnel, C., & Sparks, P. L. (2010). The effect of spousal communication on contraceptive use in Central Terai, Nepal. *Patient Education and Counselling*, 81(3), 402-408.

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

*Global Research Journal of Business Management**Vol. 4, No. 1: 48 - 59, 2024***WOMEN ECONOMIC EMPOWERMENT ON ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT**

**Women Economic Empowerment on Economic Development in Selected Communities
in Enugu State, Nigeria, 2015 – 2022**Dr. Anikeze Nnaemeka Hillary¹; Egwuagu Uloma Bridget²; Daniel Ukamaka Loveth³

^{1, 2 & 3} Department of Public Administration,
Faculty of Management Science,
Enugu State University of Science and Technology. ESUT.

Emails: ¹nnaemeka.anikeze@esut.edu.ng; ²ulomaegwuagu@gmail.com

Abstract

Research purpose: The current economic state of most women is a product of the roles they are expected to fill. These roles were seen as their primary responsibilities, and they were discouraged or even prevented from pursuing careers outside of these roles. The objectives of the study are to: find out the extent women participating in Small and Medium Scale Enterprises have impacted on poverty reduction in Enugu state, Nigeria, assess the extent women skill acquisition have impacted on poverty reduction in Enugu state, Nigeria.

Methodology: The study adopted a descriptive method of research design, while the population of the study is 172 and sample is 120. Out 120 questionnaires administered, 115 are valid for the study.

Research Findings: This means women participating in Small and Medium Scale Enterprises have impacted on poverty reduction in Enugu state, Nigeria. This implies that women acquiring educational Knowledge have impacted on poverty reduction in Enugu state, Nigeria.

Conclusion: The study concluded that women economic empowerment have impacted on economic development in communities of Enugu state, Nigeria.

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

Global Research Journal of Business Management

Vol. 4, No. 1: 48 - 59, 2024

WOMEN ECONOMIC EMPOWERMENT ON ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

Final recommendations: The society should allow women to participate in Small and Medium Scale Enterprises and it will contribute to economic development in Nigeria, Government should make room for more social skim programs for women especially for skill acquisition has impacted on poverty reduction and it will contribute to economic development in Nigeria, Gender equality, especially the female gender should be allow for white-collar jobs and is part of economic development in the society and Women should be allow to participate in politics hand this will impact on poverty reduction positively in communities in Africa at large.

Key words: Small and Medium Scale Enterprises, women skill acquisition, poverty reduction

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Study

Historically in Nigeria and many other African countries, women were often expected to fulfill traditional roles within the family and household, such as caregiving and homemaking. These roles were seen as their primary responsibilities, and they were discouraged or even prevented from pursuing careers outside of these roles. In some communities in Nigeria, women are seen as house wife has cultural and historical roots, but it's essential to recognize that these perspectives are evolving and not universally applied. Traditional gender roles in many African societies often placed women in domestic roles, including taking care of the home and children (Akpala, 2018). This was influenced by various factors such as cultural beliefs, economic structures, and colonial legacies. However, it's important to note that Africa is a vast and diverse continent with a wide range of cultures and societies, and not all of them held or continue to hold these traditional views.

Problem

The problem of women empowerment in economic development of communities mostly in Nigeria is a serious concern. The situation has engendered political instability, dictatorial governments, lack of rule of law/social justice, and irresponsible leadership's e.t.c, resulting to stagnation in poverty and underdevelopment; this raises some major concerns on the factors responsible for the failure of women empowerment on economic development in communities and even local government areas of Nigeria, like of women financing, bearing of children, illiteracy, gender equality, empowerment etc. in Nigeria. On this backdrop, these project works assess women empowerment on Economic development in communities in Enugu state, Nigeria.

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

Global Research Journal of Business Management

Vol. 4, No. 1: 48 - 59, 2024

WOMEN ECONOMIC EMPOWERMENT ON ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

Objectives

The specific objectives are:

- i. To find out the extent women participating in Small and Medium Scale Enterprises have impacted on poverty reduction in Enugu state, Nigeria
- ii. To assess the extent women skill acquisition have impacted on poverty reduction in Enugu state, Nigeria

Questions

Some questions extracted from the above objectives are below:

- i. To what extent women participating in Small and Medium Scale Enterprises have impacted on poverty reduction in Enugu state, Nigeria?
- ii. What extent women skill acquisition has impacted on poverty reduction in Enugu state, Nigeria?

Hypotheses

- i. H_0 : Women participating in Small and Medium Scale Enterprises have not impacted on poverty reduction in Enugu state, Nigeria.
- ii. H_0 : Women skill acquisition has not impacted on poverty reduction in Enugu state, Nigeria.

2. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Conceptual Review

Review on Women Economic Empowerment and Economic Development of Communities

Women's economic empowerment is recognized as one means for reducing poverty and economic growth. Women play a significant role in Nigerian economy, and are highly visible in the micro and small enterprises sub-sector. The majority of them are engaged in small income generating self-employment in agriculture and non-agricultural activities with low prospect for growth (Dejene, 2014). The economic empowerment of women is a prerequisite for sustainable development, pro-poor growth and the achievement of all the millennium development Goals (MDGs). Gender equality and empowered women are catalysts for

WOMEN ECONOMIC EMPOWERMENT ON ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

multiplying development efforts. Investments in gender equality yield the highest returns of all development investments (OECD, 2010).

Process of Women's Economic Empowerment

Women's economic empowerment is a prerequisite for sustainable economic development and pro-poor growth. To achieve women's economic empowerment anticipation requires sound government policies, and long-term commitment. Gender-specific perspectives must be incorporated at the initial design stage of policy and programming. Women must have equal equitable access to assets and services; infrastructure programmes should be designed to the benefit of the poor, both men and women, and employment opportunities must be improved while increasing recognition of women's vast unpaid work (OECD DAC Network on Gender Equality, 2012). Women's Economic Empowerment can be achieved through equal access to and control over critical economic resources and opportunities, and the elimination of structural gender inequalities in the labour market including a bettering of unpaid care work.

Obstacles to Women's Economic Empowerment

- (a) Lack of Fund: Many of these women rely on personal savings or on contributions from relatives and friends to fund their enterprises, and without property ownership they lack collateral to access credit from formal financial institutions.
- (b) Scale of Operation: Most women in developing countries especially Nigeria has small enterprises operating mainly in the informal sector of economy. They face multiple challenges that diminish their opportunities and dampen their potential as businesswomen and entrepreneurs.
- (c) Education and Training: They have limited access to education and training, have less or no freedom to choose their business, and are faced with discriminatory attitudes in property, marital and inheritance laws.
- (d) Structural and cultural factors: These make it more difficult for women to access vocational training programmes due to their care giving responsibilities and societal expectations about which jobs are suitable for them.

2.1 THEORIES**Marxist Approach**

In theoretical terms, Karl Marx prepared the ground for debate of women's issues. His theory is based in economic determination, especially; he argued that the ownership and control of means of forces of production have exerted the most significant influence on societal satisfaction system. Marxian approach to gender stratification centers, on the extent to which women's access to the control of the forces of production determines their relative position in the society. The approach adopted by the Marxian school is borrowed from the works of Engels (1968). This focuses on the role played by familiar structure and to the extent to

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

*Global Research Journal of Business Management**Vol. 4, No. 1: 48 - 59, 2024***WOMEN ECONOMIC EMPOWERMENT ON ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT**

which women participate in social production. Thus, Engel argues that a nuclear family is based on the supremacy of the man, its expressed aim is the begetting of children of undisputed paternity, this paternity being required in order that those children may in due time inherit their father's wealth.

Socio-Cultural Approach

Socio-cultural approach is the best approach to adopt as my theoretical framework, because it is the culture of the people that placed women as weaker vessels, and sees them as less important when decisions need to be taken for the growth of communities and even in their household, and this belief moves from generation to generation. This cultural approach deals with tradition, beliefs, values, norms and practices system of the people living in the same society.

2.2 EMPIRICAL REVIEW

Abraham, O. and Bridget U. (2023) looked at the relationship and impact of rural women empowerment and rural development in Nigeria's south-south geopolitical zone in their paper titled 'Rural women empowerment and development in Nigeria'. In the study, a cross-sectional research design was used, and data was gathered through a survey of 750 people using a non-probability sampling technique. 476 of the 750 questionnaires distributed were retrieved and analyzed. Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 23 was used to analyze data collected using percentages, Pearson product moment correlation, and linear regression analysis. The study's findings revealed a significant relationship between rural women empowerment and rural development in Nigeria's south-south geopolitical zone. The study also found that rural women empowerment has a positive and statistically significant impact on rural development in Nigeria's south-south geopolitical zone. Based on these findings, the study suggests, among other things, that government empowerment policies should always take the female gender into account for necessary upliftment, as this will help to improve their status and rural development in Nigeria.

Nwabude, and Nwogwugwu, (2022) investigate women empowerment and economic development a case of Idemili north local government in Anambra state of Nigeria. The issue of women empowerment in Nigeria with special focus on the local/rural parts where the main residents are women has been of great concern to scholars and policy makers. In this study we have taken special interest on the developments in the Idemili north local government areas of Anambra state. we found that the women there are not empowered: they have no infrastructure and are least awarded despite that they produce much of the food, do much of the farm work and as well carry on with their biological responsibility of child bearing and rearing. the paper hence recommends that education must be provided for the girl child. It further recommends the elimination of widowhood practices; stopping of early marriages as

WOMEN ECONOMIC EMPOWERMENT ON ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

well as the provision of opportunities for improved agricultural practices for the female gender.

Kingdom, M. (2021) women and socio-economic growth in Nigeria: A development strategy. The contribution of women to the socio-economic growth of developing nations has received little attention in the existing literature in terms of their roles in the process, and Nigeria is not an exception. The study adopted the survey research design with the use of random sampling technique to select respondents. Chi-square was used to analyze the data. The results indicated that 1% increase in women's contribution raised the level of GDP by 58.4%; that income generating activities of women to include agricultural produce, marketing of farm produce, crafts making and food processing; and that despite all the efforts women put in development, their capacities are not optimally utilized due to socio-cultural and political hindrances such as access to land, loans, education. The paper therefore recommended women empowerments, policy initiatives to upgrade their roles which is one of the important objectives of the global development strategy, the Millennium Development Goals (MDG's), where sub-Saharan Africa plays a latecomer role' in its realization.

Many researchers have carried out related studies on women economic empowerment and economic development, but there is a lack of literature on the women economic empowerment on economic development in communities of Enugu State, Nigeria, particularly in areas of on- women participating in small and medium scale enterprises, women acquiring educational knowledge, women going for white-collar jobs, women participation in politics and poverty reduction. Therefore, this study is to adequately fill in this gap.

3. METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study adopted a descriptive method of research design, specifically survey design involving the method of collection of data, analysis and interpretation of data with a view of Women economic empowerment and economic development in communities of Enugu state, Nigeria.

Sources of Data

There are two sources of data used for this study which are primary and secondary data. Primary data were collected, by administering questionnaire to local government workers in Enugu North secretarial of Enugu state. Furthermore, personal and oral interviews were conducted among the selected staff in the faculty used in this study. And these are data

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

Global Research Journal of Business Management

Vol. 4, No. 1: 48 - 59, 2024

WOMEN ECONOMIC EMPOWERMENT ON ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

mainly sourced from already made materials of other authors and researchers. They are available in relevant textbooks, journals, newspapers and internet and in the school library.

Population and Sample Size

The population of the study, amount 172, which is gotten from field survey, conducted using some selected women entrepreneurs registered with National Association of Small Scale Industries (NASSI) in Enugu North Local government area of Enugu State, Nigeria.

The researcher decided to take a sample believing it would be a fair representation of the population. This was achieved using Taro Yamani's formula as given below:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where

n = The desired sample size

N = Population

e = Maximum acceptable level of error

1 = Mathematical constant

The researcher assumed a 5% level of tolerable error hence the sample size was determined as shown below:

Substituting

$N = 172$

$e = 0.05$

Using the formula

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2} = \frac{172}{1 + 172(0.05)^2} = \frac{172}{1 + 172(0.0025)} = \frac{172}{1 + 0.43} = \frac{172}{1.43} = 120$$

$n = 120$

Sampling Technique

The Sampling technique adopted for the selection of respondents was field survey method because each department do not have equal chance of being selected.

Method of Data Presentation and Analysis

The data from the questionnaire were analyzed using frequency tables and simple percentages. Brief analytical comments were used to summarize the findings of that questionnaire as shown in chapter four of this work. Simple percentage formula used will be shown below:

$$\frac{f}{N} \times \frac{100}{1}$$

Where f = frequency

N = sum of cumulative frequency

The hypotheses were tested using the chi-square statistical tool; given as:

WOMEN ECONOMIC EMPOWERMENT ON ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

$$x^2 = \sum \frac{(o - e)^2}{e}$$

Where \sum = summation sign

o = observed frequency data

e = expected frequency data

Decision Rule: Accept null hypothesis if table value is greater than calculated value, otherwise reject null hypothesis

4. PRESENTATION OF DATA AND ANALYSIS

In this chapter, data generated were presented, analyzed and interpreted. However, it commenced with the distribution and return of the instrument of data collected.

Presentation of Data

Distribution and Return of Questionnaire

Table 4.1: Questionnaire Distribution and Response Rate

Options	Number of Questionnaire Distributed	Number of Questionnaire Returned	% of Returned Questionnaire	Number of Valid Questionnaire	% valid Questionnaire
Senior Staff	91	91	75.83	89	74.17
Junior Staff	29	29	24.17	26	21.67
Total	120	120	100	115	95.84

Source:Field Survey, 2023

Table 4.1 shows the 120 copies of questionnaires distributed, and were still returned back with 100%, while 115 copies of the questionnaire representing 95.84% are only valid copies for the study due to mis-handling. The valid copies are used for rest of the analysis of this work.

Test of Hypotheses

The hypotheses were tested using the chi-square statistical tool, which is given as;

$$x^2 = \sum \frac{(o - e)^2}{e}$$

Where: x^2 = chi - square

o = observed frequency

e = expected frequency

Σ = summation sign

Operational Assumptions

Level of significance 5% = 0.05

WOMEN ECONOMIC EMPOWERMENT ON ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

Degree of freedom (df) = $(r - 1)(c - 1)$

Where: r = Number of rows

c = Number of columns

$$df = (2 - 1)(3 - 1)$$

$$1 \times 2 = 2$$

Critical value or table value = 5.991

Hypothesis I

H_0 : Women participating in Small and Medium Scale Enterprises have not impacted on poverty reduction in Enugu state, Nigeria

Table 4.4 was used for testing hypothesis I

Options	Great Extent	%	None	%	Little Extent	%	Total
Senior Staff	60	52.17	5	4.35	20	17.39	85
Junior Staff	20	17.39	5	4.35	5	4.35	30
Total	80	69.56	10	8.70	25	21.74	115

Chi-Square Table

O	E	$(o - e)$	$(o - e)^2$	$\frac{(o - e)^2}{e}$
80	38.33	41.67	1736.39	45.30
10	38.33	-28.33	802.59	20.94
25	38.33	-13.33	177.69	4.64
115				70.88

Table value = 5.991; Calculated value = 70.88

Decision: Since the calculated value (70.88) is greater than the table value (5.991), the H_0 (null hypothesis) is rejected, while the H_1 (alternative hypothesis) is accepted. This means that women participating in Small and Medium Scale Enterprises have impacted on poverty reduction in Enugu state, Nigeria.

Hypothesis II

H_0 : Women acquiring educational Knowledge have not impacted on poverty reduction in Enugu state, Nigeria.

Table 4.5 was used for testing hypothesis II

Options	Great Extent	%	None	%	Little Extent	%	Total
---------	--------------	---	------	---	---------------	---	-------

WOMEN ECONOMIC EMPOWERMENT ON ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

Senior Staff	80	73.91	5	4.35	15	13.04	100
Junior Staff	5	4.35	5	4.35	5	4.35	115
Total	85	78.26	10	8.70	20	17.39	115

Chi-Square Table

O	E	(o - e)	(o - e) ²	$\frac{(o - e)^2}{e}$
85	38.33	46.67	2178.09	56.82
10	38.33	-28.33	802.59	20.94
20	38.33	-18.33	335.99	8.77
115				86.53

Table value = 5.991; Calculated value = 86.53

Decision: Since the calculated value (86.53) is greater than the table value (5.991), the H_0 (null hypothesis) is rejected and the H_1 (alternative hypothesis) is accepted. This implies that women acquiring educational Knowledge have impacted on poverty reduction in Enugu state, Nigeria.

4a. Discussion of Findings

The discussions of findings are as follows:

To what extent women participating in Small and Medium Scale Enterprises have impacted on poverty reduction in Enugu state, Nigeria, long service reward is a strategy to improve employees performance in any organization because it shows that the organization reward the employees priceless effort (Jehanzeb& Bashir, 2013). This is in line with data analysis above that Women participating in Small and Medium Scale Enterprises have not impacted on poverty reduction in Enugu state, Nigeria

What extent women acquiring educational Knowledge have impacted on poverty reduction in Enugu state, Nigeria, bonuses to employees performance encouraged the worker to increase in output and this is an advantage to the organization according to (Khan, Abbasi, Waseem, Ayaz, &Ijaz, 2016) and this were revealed in the hypotheses analysis above, that women acquiring educational Knowledge have not impacted on poverty reduction in Enugu state, Nigeria.

5. SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS**5.1 Summary of Findings**

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

Global Research Journal of Business Management

Vol. 4, No. 1: 48 - 59, 2024

WOMEN ECONOMIC EMPOWERMENT ON ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

From the above analyses, the following findings were made:

1. Since the calculated value (70.88) is greater than the table value (5.991), the H_0 (null hypothesis) is rejected, while the H_1 (alternative hypothesis) is accepted. This means women participating in Small and Medium Scale Enterprises have impacted on poverty reduction in Enugu state, Nigeria.

2. Since the calculated value (86.53) is greater than the table value (5.991), the H_0 (null hypothesis) is rejected and the H_1 (alternative hypothesis) is accepted. This implies that women acquiring educational Knowledge have impacted on poverty reduction in Enugu state, Nigeria.

5.2 Conclusion

In conclusion, the researcher women need education, skills, access to assets/credit, social protection in order to fully develop their productive assets and tackle poverty. In reality, women face many challenges in their entrepreneurial development and overcoming many of the obstacles requires reduction in gender discriminatory norms and practices. However the major conclusion of the study show that women empowerment are have positive significant on economic development in communities of Enugu state, Nigeria.

5.3 Recommendations

- i. the society should allow women to participate in Small and Medium Scale Enterprises and it will contribute to economic development in Nigeria.
- ii. Government should make room for more social skim programs for women especially for skill acquisition has impacted on poverty reduction and it will contribute to economic development in Nigeria.

REFERENCES

- Adegoroye, A. (2018). The Roles of Selected NGOs in Economic Empowerment of Rural Akomolafe, O. (2016). "Open and Distance Learning as a Mechanism for Women Akpala, S. (2018). *Women's Rights are Human Rights*. Enugu: Snaap Press Ltd.
- Alkali, Z. (2020). *Feminism A radical theme in West Africa literature, An African woman right*. Houston, U.S.A: Touchstone Publishers.
- Danjuma, M. & Alkali G. (2013). *Factors Militating Against Women Economic*
- Dejene, Y. (2014). *Promoting Women's Economic empowerment In Africa* retrieved from DEJENE.9-15-07DOC.PDF

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

Global Research Journal of Business Management

Vol. 4, No. 1: 48 - 59, 2024

WOMEN ECONOMIC EMPOWERMENT ON ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

- Eyben , R., Kabeer, N. and Cornwall, A. (2018). Conceptualising empowerment and the from <https://www.oecd.org/dac/povertyreduction/50157530.pdf> Goals , New York: United Nations Halt, Rinchart and Winton Inc.
- Holy Bible (2010), “The Subordination of Women to Men,” Tennessee: Broadman and Holman Publishers.
- Kabeer, N. (2011). Reflections on the measurement of women's empowerment. Discussing Malmberg, C. (2016) “Case study on the role of Women in Rural Transport: Access of Women to *Management*, 13(6), 47-51
- Mayoux, L. (2019). “Questioning Virtuous Spirals: Micro-finance and Women’s Empowerment
- Nziome, M. (2012), “Women in Politics and Public Decision-Making” in U.F. Himmestrand et al (eds.) *African Perspective in Development, Controversies, Dilemma and Opening* London: James Curray.
- OECD DAC Network on Gender Equality (2015) Women’s economic empowerment retrieved of Development Studies.
- Ojo, O. (2010), “Challenges of Sustainable Democracy in Nigeria,” Ibadan: John Archers Publishers. Performance and Job Satisfaction,” *Journal of Organizational Behaviour and Human Performance*, Vol.9.
- Pritchard, D. and Karasack, W. (2010), “The Effect of Organizational Climate on Managerial Job
Routledge, Talor and Fransis Group.
- Schmitz, C.(2019). Working Paper December on Sida Gender Equality Team Indevelop-IPM, Sida.
- United Nations (2010) Keeping the promise: united to achieve the Millennium Development United Nations Development Program (2015) Human Development Report. New York
- Vandana, D. and Robert, P (2014). The companion to development studies, New York.
- Williams, F. (2016) *Reasoning with Statistics – How to Read Quantitative Research*. Florida: Women in Ibadan Land” *Journal of Gender and Behavior*, 6(2), 25-37.
- World Bank (2011) Engendering Development Through Gender Equality in Rights, Resources,
- Zoellick, R. (2010) . Extracted from World Bank President Zoellick’s speech at the MDG3

Effect of Students' Mentorship Programs on Quality Supervision of Research Works in Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu (ESUT), Nigeria

Abonyi Jonas Uchenna¹; Okafor Ifeoma Cordelia¹; Anikeze Nnaemeka Hillary²

¹ Department of Public Administration,

Institute of Management Technology, Enugu, Nigeria.

² Department of Public Administration,

Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Nigeria.

Abstract

Research purpose: The study examined the effect of students' mentorship programs on quality supervision of research works in Enugu State University of Science and Technology Enugu (ESUT) Nigeria. The specific objectives are to: ascertain effect of one-on-one mentoring on quality supervision of research works and evaluate effect of electronic mentoring on quality supervision of research works.

Methodology: The research design was descriptive survey method. Study Area was Enugu Nigeria. The sample size of 399 respondents was drawn from population of 1,603 academic staff of Enugu State University of Science and Technology Enugu. The study used structured questionnaire to obtain data. Research questions of the study were answered using mean score and standard deviation. The hypotheses were tested using single regression analysis.

Research Findings: The empirical results show that one-on-one mentoring has significant effect on quality supervision of research works since mentorship program provides guidance, pragmatic advise and continuing support that will help the student to learn and develop ($t - \text{statistics} (9.826) > P - \text{value} (0.000)$) and electronic mentoring has significant effect on quality supervision of research works since mentorship program provide sufficient advice on

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

Global Research Journal of Business Management

Vol. 4, No. 1: 60 - 79, 2024

STUDENTS' MENTORSHIP PROGRAMS & QUALITY SUPERVISION OF RESEARCH WORKS

how to undertake research work more effectively and handle identified specific problems (t – statistics (5.908) > P – value (0.000).

Conclusion: The study concludes that students' mentorship programs have positive and significant effect on quality supervision of research works in Enugu State University of Science and Technology Enugu (ESUT) Nigeria.

Final recommendations: Governing council of Enugu State University of Science and Technology should be regular capacity building on emerging online technologies through seminars and online platforms such as webinars, Digiface, and face-to-face workshop trainings. This could be realized through partnership with other stakeholders on research.

Key words: Students' Mentorship Program; Quality Supervision, Research works.

1.1 Background of the Study

Universities over the years serve as training grounds of high-level manpower development centers for the various sectors of the economy. The primary responsibility of the University is to produce a world class certified graduate in character and learning. A lecturer is a key element in this process and the success or failure of it depends on individual lecturer effectiveness. The issue of lecturers' effectiveness has become an issue of serious concern because apart from the quality of graduates which is allegedly being challenged by students, parents, employers, government, the international labour market and many foreign Universities, majority of the Universities seem not to be making desired impact in the socioeconomic and political development of the nation (Buddhapriya, 2017). University culture is the atmosphere that is created by the social and professional interactions of the individuals; values, beliefs and norms that exist at the University that can encourage or discourage effectiveness.

The lecturers' effectiveness relies heavily on their environment and assistance they obtain from it in the shape of supervisory or managerial support, consistence learning from seniors, training and development programmes and peer support. Students who are cared and provided timely learning through training and mentoring at different intervals are much encouraged and they comparatively outperform those who are lacking these facilities (Abukari & David, 2019). However, such students' mentorship programs are inadequate as mentors appear inaccessible to mentees. The increased and consistently effective teaching, research and community service performance relies on the lecturers who are the assets of the Universities. The effectiveness of supervising lecturers relies much on their environment and

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

Global Research Journal of Business Management

Vol. 4, No. 1: 60 - 79, 2024

STUDENTS' MENTORSHIP PROGRAMS & QUALITY SUPERVISION OF RESEARCH WORKS

assistance they obtain from it in the form supervisory support, learning from seniors and peer support. The relationship between a student and an academic supervisor or mentor is critical to the success of the learning experience, to the sense of satisfaction of both participants, to the development of research skills, and to the shaping of successful career pathways of both parties (Åkerlind & McAlpine, 2017).

Mentoring is the sharing of personal experiences. It is to informally transmit the knowledge one had gained to someone less experienced, so that he may grow and practice as an individual. This is a relationship in which personal development is the key outcome. Mentoring is a process for the informal transmission of knowledge, social capital and psychosocial support perceived by the recipient as relevant to work, career or professional development. It entails informal communication, usually face to face and during a sustained period of time between a person who is perceived to have greater relevant knowledge, wisdom, or experience and a person who is perceived to have less (Hutchings, 2017). The mentor is someone who engages in a long term, on-going relationship with a new or young employee by mutual agreement. While the relationship may be initiated by arrangements such as academic advising, or classroom teaching, normally for their personal ends. Mentoring is a holistic approach relating primarily to the identification and nurturing of potentials in a long relationship where the goals may change but always set by the learner, the learner owns both the goals and the process (Waddell, Martin, Schwind & Lapum, 2016). Mentoring function at work place can be performed by someone other than the immediate supervisor. Also mentoring in organizations have been described as a viable vehicle for effective management of employees capabilities, time and talent as well as a tool for grooming new and junior employees for future leadership roles (Chatterjee, Dey & Chaturvedi, 2021). In order to help empower students to become more effective and productive in their research work, then providing quality services mentoring programme is a veritable means in enhancement of research work supervision in tertiary institution.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

In Nigeria, there seems to be some controversy on whether research students today are prepared for the 21st century research demands. Many students have a poor understanding of the essential characteristics of research, how it influences society, and how people can and do affect its development. Moreover, studies have pointed out that there are high proportions of students who fail to complete their research works within the time given (Kipkasi, 2022; Walbe, 2019). The most unfortunate and painful thing is the case of dropouts. In spite of laboring hard for their admission, many students drop out without completing their research works. There are some who are very casual towards research work, some are impatient, some are indifferent, and some are otherwise constrained due to work pressure relating to their finance, jobs, transfers, etc. During their various supervisions of students, the present

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

*Global Research Journal of Business Management**Vol. 4, No. 1: 60 - 79, 2024***STUDENTS' MENTORSHIP PROGRAMS & QUALITY SUPERVISION OF RESEARCH WORKS**

researchers observed that many of the students experienced a large array of problems related to writing and information retrieval skills and presenting original work. Some of these students from first year were also exposed to a culture of copying of earlier research works. They also found that the state of research at the universities of technology was poor because of the scarcity of research expertise, inexperienced supervisors, and supervisors working in fields outside their specializations. This resulted in low research outputs and generally discouraged students who would have opted to continue with their studies. Many students did not understand nor value research and had no knowledge of where to find information to base their research endeavours (Udom, Okoedion & Okolie, 2020). The negative consequences of these research problems for building and retaining research capacity in Enugu State University of Science and Technology are obvious. It appears that there were some problems experienced by supervisors of research students in trying to create a balance between dominating and neglecting student's research. These problems may be caused by the characteristics and values inherent in the mentoring received during research received, which unfortunately, have not been empirically researched in South-East of Nigeria. Student's mentorship program and quality of supervision of research work have been subjects of discourse among social scientists from a wide range of disciplines in the last two decades. But unfortunately, very insufficient number of studies in this area has been conducted in Nigeria. This study was undertaken to fill this obvious research gap.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of this study is to examine the effect of students' mentorship programs on quality supervision of research works in Enugu State University of Science and Technology Enugu (ESUT) Nigeria. The specific objectives are to:

- I. Ascertain effect of one-on-one mentoring on quality supervision of research works in Enugu State University of Science and Technology Enugu.
- II. Evaluate effect of electronic mentoring on quality supervision of research works in Enugu State University of Science and Technology Enugu.

Significance of the Study

This study is beneficial and important the following of groups namely students, lecturers in tertiary institutions, students and researchers.

The study findings would help student to have appropriate research skills and that the thesis/dissertation is likely to come to a successful conclusion. The findings of the study gives helpful advice to novice students to improve learning methods and practices. The study opens students' eye in the key factor that is crucial for successful transfer of research knowledge is communication.

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

Global Research Journal of Business Management

Vol. 4, No. 1: 60 - 79, 2024

STUDENTS' MENTORSHIP PROGRAMS & QUALITY SUPERVISION OF RESEARCH WORKS

The outcome of this study will help lecturers in tertiary institutions to identify their expected roles ranging from being an observer, role model, counselor, quality controller, critical friend, assessor, and manager. The mentor should be sensitive to the new student's feelings to help diagnose the situation and come up with the potential solution.

The outcome of this study will be beneficial to researchers because empirical findings of the study are capable of adding new insights to present knowledge in the field. Thus, it would be an additional reference material to students.

Conceptual Review

Mentoring in Academic Environment

Mentoring is the technique of attaching the higher skilled or experienced person with the goal of making lesser skilled person grow and develop specific competences, skills and attitudes. Mentoring not only supports in polishing the abilities and competences of individuals and groups but also provides positive alteration of employees' skills to their improved performance and organizational outcomes (Muraya & Wairimu, (2020). Mentorship is most often described as a guiding relationship in which a more experienced person, the mentor, assumes a supportive role by overseeing and encouraging reflection and learning with a less experienced person, the mentee (Ahmed, Srivastava & Warren, *et al.* 2019). Peretomode and Ikoya (2019) defines mentorship as "a learning and development partnership between someone with vast or in-depth experience and knowledge (the mentor) and someone who wants to learn, build skills and knowledge while attaining his goals.

Mentoring helps and relaxes the employee's behaviour as it guides them to develop and adjust themselves to their working environment. Hence it helps them to provide positive feedback. Planned mentoring programmes are a cost saving activity as its managing is less expensive in terms of avoidable mistakes by employees. In order to increase individual and team commitment to an organization and its goals; allow individuals to gain greater insight into the University workings, an effective mentoring programme in academic environments is useful (Ofobruku & Nwakoby, 2018). It can also help increase communication within the University, help to change organizational culture to a better level, give individuals the chance to meet different people within the university network, and improve levels of performance success. Although, there is no consistent definition of mentoring, in higher education, mentoring programs mostly show positive effects for mentee (e.g., better academic performance, as well as for mentor (e.g., more satisfaction) and the institution itself (e.g., reduced drop-out rates) (Åkerlind & McAlpine, 2017).

Contextual Literature

One-on-one mentoring and quality supervision of research works

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

Global Research Journal of Business Management

Vol. 4, No. 1: 60 - 79, 2024

STUDENTS' MENTORSHIP PROGRAMS & QUALITY SUPERVISION OF RESEARCH WORKS

The goal of one-on-one mentorship relationship is to provide an environment of support and to advise and coach an individual within the context of the culture and expectations of the organization or institution (Baloyi, 2020). It also help the less experienced persons to learn new skills that will position them to be successful in their academic career (Hu, Wang, Wang & et al, (2016). Mentoring in the words of Naim & Lenka, (2017) is where one or more teachers, tutors, coaches or mentors work on a regular, one-to-one or small group basis with students. It is essential to note that the student/mentor relationship may be a powerful influence in a student's life, particularly for those students who are vulnerable for a range of reasons outside the mentoring relationship. Mentoring of students by teachers (lecturers) and adults is crucial for their academic excellence. Mentoring programs have two important features, i.e., communication and support (Okurame & Ajayi, 2017).

In the context of university mentoring program, communication is generally defined as mentors openly delivering information about the procedures, content, tasks and objectives of the mentoring programs, conducting discussions about tasks that should be learned, giving detailed explanations about the benefits of attending mentoring programs and providing performance feedback. While support on the other hand, is defined as providing emotional support (i.e., acquire new knowledge, skills, and attitudes, and guide them to properly apply in daily life) and instrumental support (i.e., assist mentees to adapt to campus environment) at varying times (Kumar, P. (2018).

Electronic mentoring and quality supervision of research works

Mentoring according to Kumar and Kumar (2018), is the process of using specially selected and trained individuals to provide guidance, pragmatic advise and continuing support that will help the person or persons allocated to them to learn and develop. Mentors prepare individuals to perform better in the future and groom them for higher and greater career advancement. In addition, Peretomode and Ikoya (2019) affirm that mentoring is more than just giving advice on how to work more effectively or handle a specific problem. It involves the mentor taking personal interest in seeing that a mentee developed the right talent, skills, values, attitudes, expertise and knowledge needed to succeed, to have a successful career and contribute as much as possible to the organization, society and the nation. Mentoring relationships are categorized into two, namely, formal and informal mentorship. A formal mentorship is one in which the mentor/mentee relationship is organizationally structure. The management of the organization is "responsible for deliberately selecting and pairing the mentee and the mentor with the goal of assisting the mentee grow and develop specific

competencies. In an informal mentorship, on the other hand, it is the mentee or protégé who requires training that selects the mentor—the person with more expertise, experience, knowledge and advice he/she wants to share with or under study” (Buddhapriya, 2017).

Mentoring as a special form of social support is mainly found in three different areas: (i) workplace mentoring, (ii) youth mentoring, and (iii) mentoring in higher education (Abukari & David, 2019).

Theoretical Foundation of the Study

The theory underpinning this study is the Theory of Social Constructivism. The theory of social constructivism was developed by Soviet psychologist Lev Vygotsky (1896-1934). Social constructivism is based on the idea that learners construct new knowledge. Working with new knowledge involves construction, storage or putting new information into memory, and retrieval. Theory of Social constructivism is a sociological theory of knowledge according to which human development is socially situated and knowledge is constructed through interaction with others. Like social constructionism, social constructivism states that people work together to construct artifacts. The central idea of constructivism is that human learning is constructed and that learners build new knowledge upon the foundation of previous learning. This view of learning sharply contrasts with one in which learning is the passive transmission of information from one individual to another, a view in which reception, not construction, is key. Vygotsky’s social constructivist theory can provide adult ESL students with the ability to construct their own meanings by critical thinking. Social constructivism is a learning perspective founded on the assumption that learning is focused on learners and promotes their active participation as they manage to construct their own knowledge depending on their own reality. Constructivism is a combination of various speculations diffused in to one frame. It is the digestion of both behaviouralist and psychological beliefs. The constructivist position keeps up that learning is a procedure of developing significance; it is the means by which individuals understand their experience (Caffarella & Merriam, 1999).

Vygotsky (1978) states that psychological development happens first on a social level and after that it can happen inside the person. Learners can comprehend others and construct knowledge if they relate with conditions (Roth, 2000). To McMahan (1997), culture and setting in understanding what happens in the society and knowledge development in light of this comprehension are underlined in social constructivism. Kim (2001) believes that social constructivism depends on particular assumptions about reality, knowledge, and learning. *i.* Reality: The first assumption of social constructivism is that reality does not exist ahead of time; rather it is developed through human action. *ii.* Knowledge: Social constructivism sees knowledge as a human item that is socially and culturally developed. People can make

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

Global Research Journal of Business Management*Vol. 4, No. 1: 60 - 79, 2024***STUDENTS' MENTORSHIP PROGRAMS & QUALITY SUPERVISION OF RESEARCH WORKS**

meaning when they associate with each other and their environment. *iii*. Learning: Social constructivism believes that learning is a social procedure. Learning does not happen just inside an individual, nor is it created by outside powers (McMahon, 1997).

Social constructivism, influenced by Vygotsky's (1978) work, proposes that knowledge is first developed in a social setting and is then internalized and utilised by people (Kim, 2001). Collaborative elaboration, the process of sharing personal perspective, brings about learners constructing understanding together and this development is not conceivable alone inside people (McMahon, 1997). Social constructivist researchers see learning as a dynamic procedure where learners should figure out how to find standards, ideas and realities for themselves, consequently they empower and advance the mystery and instinctive deduction in learners (Brown, 1994). As it were, social constructivist features that reality is not something that people can find since it does not pre-exist preceding their social development of it.

Empirical Review

Kipkasi, (2022) evaluated effective strategies of doctorate students' blended supervision and mentorship programme at School of Education, Moi University, Kenya. Specifically, the study sought to: to assess the level of preparedness by the doctorate supervisors in adoption of blended supervision and mentorship; to determine the availability of the ICT infrastructure and platforms that support blended supervision and mentorship. The target populations were doctorate supervisors, doctorate candidates, ICT support personnel, and Dean postgraduate studies at Moi University. Data were analyzed descriptively and through thematic coding. Key findings revealed that there was inadequate preparation of doctorate supervision, lack of feedback expectation tool thus delayed responses and poor connectivity especially during interaction. The study suggests that there should be regular capacity building on emerging online technologies through seminars and online platforms such as webinars, Digiface, and face-to-face workshop trainings.

Chatterjee, Dey and Chaturvedi, (2021) examined the relationship between mentoring and job performance among Indian Millennials. The specific objectives of the study were to ascertain the relationship between Indian millennials' mentoring and contextual performance scores; examine the relationship between Indian millennials' mentoring and task performance scores and determine the relationship between Indian millennials' mentoring and total performance scores. Data was collected from 122 Indian millennial mentees, using a 23-item questionnaire on mentoring and job performance. The data analytical techniques were product moment Correlation analysis and single regression. The empirical result showed that mentoring influenced total job performance, and contextual and task performance, in Indian millennials.

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

Global Research Journal of Business Management*Vol. 4, No. 1: 60 - 79, 2024***STUDENTS' MENTORSHIP PROGRAMS & QUALITY SUPERVISION OF RESEARCH WORKS**

The study suggests that Indian organizations should devise and implement more specific mentoring programs for millennials.

Muraya and Wairimu, (2020) conducted a study to investigate effects of teacher mentoring on the classroom practices of lower grade primary school teachers in Kwale County, Kenya. The specific objectives were to: determine whether teacher mentoring was an effective strategy for improving teacher classroom practices, determine the duration of teacher mentoring that was more effective in improving teacher classroom practices, establish the positive experiences from the teacher mentoring process and establish challenges experienced from the teacher mentoring process. Using One Group Repeated Measures Quasi-Experimental Design, one cohort of 40 teachers in 22 public primary schools was mentored for 20 months. The method of data analysis was Repeated Measures ANOVA. The empirical result shows that teacher mentoring had a statistically significant effect on mean classroom practice score at $F=6.282$, $df=2$, $p=0.003$. Significant mean differences were located between 2016 and 2017 in favour of 2017, and between 2016 and 2018 in favour of 2018. There was no significant mean difference between 2017 and 2018. The study recommended that teacher mentoring is effective in improving teacher classroom practices and should be integrated into the formal school programme in Kenya.

Udom, Okoedion and Okolie, (2020) conducted a study to examine the impact of mentorship on students' academic excellence in University of Benin, Benin City. The specific objectives of the study were to: examine the relationship between mentorship and students' academic excellence and evaluate the impact of mentorship on students' academic excellence. A descriptive method was adopted and data was collected via a survey of 300 respondents using accidental sampling technique. Data collected were tested and analyzed using descriptive, frequency distribution, correlation and linear regression analysis. The result of the study showed that there is a positive and significant relationship between mentorship and academic excellence. The result also revealed that mentorship does have a significant impact on academic excellence in University of Benin. Thus, the study recommends among others that Nigerian universities should give due attention to mentorship since mentoring has been recognized as a strategic technique for building and sustaining scholars in research universities that provide advanced education for the academic profession, policy makers and public and private sector professionals involved in the complex globalized economies of the 21st century.

Ahmed, Srivastava and Warren, *et al.* (2019) examined the impact of a nurse mentoring program on the quality of labour and delivery care at primary health care facilities in Bihar, India. Specifically, the study sought to examine the impact of a nurse mentoring programme intended to improve the quality of intrapartum care at primary healthcare centre (PHC) facilities in Bihar, India. The sample size of 319 nurses of public PHCs in Bihar. The

empirical result show that significantly higher proportion of women at mentored PHCs received the recommended clinical care, compared with women at non-mentored PHCs. The overall total score of quality of care, expressed in percent of tasks performed, was 30.2% (95% CI: 28.3 to 32.2) in the control PHCs, suggesting that less than one-third of the expected tasks during labour and delivery were performed by nurses in these facilities; the score was 44.2% (95% CI: 42.1 to 46.4) among the facilities where the nurses were trained within last 3 months. The study suggests the need for further improvement in the provision of quality of intrapartum care when risks to maternal and perinatal mortality are highest.

Walbe, (2019) examined mentorship culture and academic staff job effectiveness in Public Universities in North-Central Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to investigate the extent to which mentoring programmes encourage job effectiveness of public University lecturers in North-central Nigeria. The sample size 501 respondents was drawn from 7747 academic staff thirteen public Universities and the Federal apital Territory in North-central Nigeria. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions and the Pearson correlation was used to test the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. The result showed that there is a significant relationship between job effectiveness of academic staff and University mentoring programmes in public Universities in North-central Nigeria. The findings also revealed that mentorship programmes for lecturers have positive influence on their job effectiveness. The study recommends that the University management should as a matter of policy develop and carry out mentorship programme strategy for junior academic staff to inbuilt it as an important skills learning tool for job effectiveness policy.

Ofofobruku and Nwakoby, (2018) investigated the effects of mentoring on employees' performance in family business. The construction Industry in Abuja was critically investigated. The study employed a survey research design using both quantitative and qualitative approaches. The population was the construction industry in Abuja. Responses from three hundred and sixty-seven construction employees were analysed. The data collected were analysed using Pearson correlation coefficient statistics technique. The findings of the study revealed that mentoring had positive effects on employees' performance; career support had more positive effect on employees' performance than psychosocial support. This research concluded that performances among employees are based on the degree of mentorship program put in place in the organisation. Employees respond better to career support in term of performance. The study recommends that for family business to sustain better employees' performance, the organisation should be encouraged to have a mentorship program for the employees of the organisation, which will result in better employees' performance for the business to achieve its objectives.

Methodology

The research design was descriptive survey method. Study Area was Enugu Nigeria. The sample size of 399 respondents were drawn from population of 1,603 academic staff of Enugu State University of Science and Technology Enugu. The choice for only staff of the organization was owing to the nature of this study. The consideration about academic staff of the tertiary institution was due to accessibility and availability of data. The study used structured questionnaire to obtain data. Research questions of the study were answered using mean score and standard deviation. The hypotheses were tested using single regression analysis.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Table 1: Comprehensive Demographic of Respondents

TITLE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Questionnaire Distribution		
Questionnaires Distributed	399	100%
Returned Questionnaires	240	61%
Not Returned Questionnaires	159	39%
Gender		
Female	170	55%
Male	94	45%
Age Bracket		
21-30 Years	130	39%
31-40 Years	80	32%
41-50 Years	49	20%
51 Years – above	5	9%
Marital Status		
Married	145	60%
Single	83	35%
Widow/widower	7	3%
Divorce	5	2%

Sources: Field Survey, 2023

Three hundred and ninety nine (399) copies of questionnaires were designed and distributed to the respondents. Out of the 399 Questionnaires distributed, 240 (61%) were completed and returned while 159 (39%) were not returned. Therefore, 61 percent respondents were a good

representation. The study showed the respondents profile in frequency and percentage distribution of gender, age bracket and marital status.

Data Analysis

Question One: What is the effect of one-on-one mentoring on quality supervision of research works in Enugu State University of Science and Technology Enugu?

Table 2: Mean rating of respondents on what is the effect of one-on-one mentoring on quality supervision of research works in Enugu State University of Science and Technology Enugu.

S/N	Questionnaire Item	VHE(5)	HE(4)	M(3)	LE(2)	VLE(1)	Total	Mean	SD
1	Mentorship program	785	188	42	24	10	1049	4.370	0.086
	provide an environment of support and to advise and coach students within the context of research	157	47	14	12	10	240		
		53%	27%	8%	7%	6%	100%		
2	It also help the less experienced students to learn new skills that will position them to be successful in their academic career	760	228	36	22	8	1054	4.392	0.088
		152	57	12	11	8	240		
		50%	33%	7%	6%	5%	100%		
3	Mentorship program provides guidance, pragmatic advise and continuing support that will help the student to learn and develop.	840	164	36	20	9	1069	4.454	0.095
		168	41	12	10	9	240		
		59	23%	7%	6%	5%	100%		
4.	Mentorship program prepare students to perform better in the future and groom	825	136	60	24	9	1054	4.392	0.093
		165	34	20	12	9	240		

them for higher and greater career advancement.	57%	19%	11%	7%	5%	100%		
Grand Mean							4.402	0.0908

This table shows that the respondents indicated their option on what is the effect of one-on-one mentoring on quality supervision of research works in Enugu State University of Science and Technology Enugu. The research items 1,2,3,4 have mean score of above 4.0 point respectively and it was rated great extent by respondents. The study revealed that one-on-one mentoring has significant effect on quality supervision of research works in Enugu State University of Science and Technology Enugu since mentorship program provides guidance, pragmatic advise and continuing support that will help the student to learn and develop (grand mean (4.402) is greater than cut-off mean (3.00)).

Question Two: What is the effect of electronic mentoring on quality supervision of research works in Enugu State University of Science and Technology Enugu?

Table 3: Mean rating of respondents on what is the effect of electronic mentoring on quality supervision of research works in Enugu State University of Science and Technology Enugu.

S/N	Questionnaire Item	VHE(5)	HE(4)	M(3)	LE(2)	VLE(1)	Total	Mean	SD
1	Mentorship program provide sufficient advice on how to undertake research work more effectively and handle identified specific problems.	790 158 53%	204 51 29%	66 22 13)%	14 7 4%	2 2 1%	1076 240 100%	4.483	0.098
2	Mentorship program involves taking personal interest in seeing that students develop in the right talent, skills, values,	780 156 50%	204 51 33%	36 12 7%	22 11 6%	10 10 5%	1052 240 100%	4.383	0.088

	attitudes, expertise and knowledge needed to carry out research work.								
3	Mentorship program provides deliberate policy selecting and pairing students with the goal of assisting for growth and develop specific competencies.	825	136	60	24	9	1054	4.392	0.093
		165	34	20	12	9	240		
		57%	19%	11%	7%	5%	100%		
4.	Mentorship program conducting discussions about tasks that should be learned and give detailed explanations about the benefits of attending to research problems.	840	164	36	20	9	1069	4.454	0.095
		168	41	12	10	9	240		
		59	23%	7%	6%	5%	100%		
	Grand Mean							4.428	0.0907

This table shows that the respondents indicated their option on what is the effect of electronic mentoring on quality supervision of research works in Enugu State University of Science and Technology Enugu. The research items 1,2,3,4 have mean score of above 4.0 point respectively and it was rated great extent by respondents. The study revealed that electronic mentoring has significant effect on quality supervision of research works in Enugu State University of Science and Technology Enugu since mentorship program provide sufficient advice on how to undertake research work more effectively and handle identified specific problems (grand mean (4.428) is greater than cut-off mean (3.00)).

Test of Hypotheses

The two hypotheses were formulated for this study and will be tested and a decision taken is based on the rule below. **Decision rule: Reject H_0 if P-value > 0.01**

Test of Hypothesis One

H₁ = One-on-one mentoring has no significant effect on quality supervision of research works in in Enugu State University of Science and Technology Enugu.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.969 ^a	.939	.939	.27115

a. Predictors: (Constant), One-on-one Mentoring

Coefficients^a ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	27.583	1	27.583	8.973	.000 ^b
	Residual	734.686	239	3.074		
	Total	762.271	240			

a. Dependent Variable: Quality Supervision of Research work

b. Predictors: (Constant), One-on-one Mentoring

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.418	.075		5.568	.000
	One-on-one Mentoring	.658	.067	.969	9.826	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Quality Supervision of Research work

In testing this hypothesis, one-on-one mentoring was regressed against quality supervision of research work. The result of the single-regression analysis showed the model to examine the

effect of one-on-one mentoring on quality supervision of research works in Enugu State University of Science and Technology Enugu.

Quality Supervision of Research work = 0.418 + 0.658 One-on-one mentoring

The empirical result showed that the coefficient of one-on-one mentoring has positive effect on quality supervision of research works; it means that one-on-one mentoring has positive and direct effect on quality supervision of research works. The results of the t – statistics denoted that the coefficient of one-on-one mentoring was statistically significance. This was because observed values of t – statistics (9.826) was greater than its P-values (0.000). The results of the F – statistical test showed that the overall regression was statistically significance. This was because observed value of the F – statistics (8.973) was greater than its P-value (0.000). Again, our empirical result showed that the Pearson product moment correlation analysis (r) was 0.969. The strength of relationship between the two variables was high. However, we rejected the null hypothesis and concluded that one-on-one mentoring has significant effect on quality supervision of research works in in Enugu State University of Science and Technology Enugu.

Test of Hypothesis Two

H₂ = Electronic mentoring has no significant effect on quality supervision of research works in Enugu State University of Science and Technology Enugu.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.966 ^a	.933	.932	.30129

a. Predictors: (Constant), Electronic Mentoring

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	25.050	1	25.050	11.980	.000 ^b
	Residual	499.749	239	2.091		
	Total	524.799	240			

a. Dependent Variable: Quality Supervision of Research work

b. Predictors: (Constant), Electronic Mentoring

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.077	.079		9.846	.000
	Electronic Mentoring	.265	.045	.966	5.908	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Quality Supervision of Research work

In testing this hypothesis, electronic mentoring was regressed against quality supervision of research works. The result of the single-regression analysis showed the model to evaluate effect of electronic mentoring on quality supervision of research works in Enugu State University of Science and Technology Enugu.

Quality Supervision of Research Work = 0.077 + 0.265 Electronic Mentoring

The empirical result showed that the coefficient of electronic mentoring has positive effect on quality supervision of research works; it means that electronic mentoring has positive and direct effect on quality supervision of research works. The results of the t – statistics denoted that the coefficient of electronic mentoring was statistically significance. This was because observed values of t – statistics (5.908) was greater than its P-values (0.000). The results of the F – statistical test showed that the overall regression of the hypothesis four was statistically significance. This was because observed value of the F – statistics (11.980) was greater than its P-value (0.000). Again, our empirical result showed that the Pearson product moment correlation analysis (r) was 0.966. The strength of relationship between the two variables was high. However, we rejected the null hypothesis and concluded that electronic mentoring has positive and significant effect on quality supervision of research works in Enugu State University of Science and Technology Enugu.

Summary of Findings

The following are the major findings of the study:

- I. The findings of the study revealed that one-on-one mentoring has significant effect on quality supervision of research works in Enugu State University of Science and Technology Enugu since mentorship program provides guidance, pragmatic advise and continuing support that will help the student to learn and develop (t – statistics (9.826) > P – value (0.000).
- II. The findings of the study revealed that electronic mentoring has significant effect on quality supervision of research works in Enugu State University of Science and Technology Enugu since mentorship program provide sufficient advice on how to undertake research work more effectively and handle identified specific problems (t – statistics (5.908) > P –

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

Global Research Journal of Business Management

Vol. 4, No. 1: 60 - 79, 2024

STUDENTS' MENTORSHIP PROGRAMS & QUALITY SUPERVISION OF RESEARCH WORKS

value (0.000).

Conclusion

The study concludes that students' mentorship programs have positive and significant effect on quality supervision of research works in Enugu State University of Science and Technology Enugu (ESUT) Nigeria. Student research is one of the vital services and output in any University system. Such research is often a scholarly and creative activity that takes place within a community of scholars where constructive relationships between students and their advisors/mentors are essential for the promotion of research excellence and adherence to the highest standards of scholarship, ethics, and professional integrity. Successful mentoring for students should be therefore be built upon effective characteristics and values through several curricula enhancement strategies so that by improving on research mentoring, university can improve the research process and enhance the research progress of education students. One can ask for no less than the effective and coherent integration of research mentoring into an enriched curriculum that meets both student and societal expectations for student research.

5.3 Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made.

- I. Governing council of Enugu State University of Science and Technology should be regular capacity building on emerging online technologies through seminars and online platforms such as webinars, Digiface, and face-to-face workshop trainings. This could be realized through partnership with other stakeholders on research. Students' supervisors should be allocated limited teaching load and un-overwhelming administrative duties.
- II. Governing council of Enugu State University of Science and Technology should give due attention to mentorship since mentoring has been recognized as a strategic technique for building and sustaining scholars in research universities that provide advanced education for the academic profession, policy makers and public and private sector professional involved in the complex globalized economic of the 21st century. Mentor/mentee relationship should focus on the needs of the students. This is because caring and supportive relationship increases self-confidence, academic achievement and positive attitudes towards assisting others.

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

Global Research Journal of Business Management

Vol. 4, No. 1: 60 - 79, 2024

STUDENTS' MENTORSHIP PROGRAMS & QUALITY SUPERVISION OF RESEARCH WORKS

REFERENCES

- Abukari, A., & David, S. (2019). Quality assuring the professional doctorate: Challenging traditional precepts through the supervisors'/advisers' lens. *Quality Assurance in Education*, 27(3), 304-319.
- Ahmed S, Srivastava S, & Warren N, *et al.* (2019) The impact of a nurse mentoring program on the quality of labour and delivery care at primary health care facilities in Bihar, India. *BMJ Global Health*; 12 (3); 56-63.
- Åkerlind, G., & McAlpine, M. (2017). Supervising doctoral students: Variation in purpose and pedagogy. *Studies in Higher Education*, 42(9), 1686-1698.
- Baloyi, G.T. (2020), "Toxicity of leadership and its impact on employees: exploring the dynamics of leadership in an academic setting", *HTS Theological Studies*, 76 (2); 45-53.
- Buddhapriya, S. (2017) 'Mentoring experiences: A study of Indian public sector professionals', *Indian Journal of Industrial Relations*, 52(4), pp.689-705.
- Chatterjee, S. Dey, A.K. & Chaturvedi, H. (2021) Effect of mentoring on job performance among Indian millennials: a quantitative study; *International Journal of Evidence Based Coaching and Mentoring*; 19(1): 90-104.
- Hu, C., Wang, S., Wang, Y.H. and et al, (2016) 'Understanding attraction informal mentoring relationships from an affective perspective', *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 94;104-113.
- Hutchings, M. (2017). Improving doctoral support through group supervision: Analysing face-to-face and technology-mediated strategies for nurturing and sustaining scholarship. *Studies in Higher Education*, 42(3), 533-550.
- Kipkasi, D. K. (2022) Effective Strategies of Doctorate Students' Blended Supervision and Mentorship at School of Education, Moi University, Kenya; *US-China Education Review*; 12 (6); 220-226.
- Kumar, P. & Kumar, S. (2018) 'Mentoring in a start-up company with millennial recruits', in Kumar, P. (eds.) *Exploring dynamic mentoring models in India*. London: Palgrave Macmillan, 49-65.
- Kumar, P. (2018) *Exploring Dynamic Mentoring Models in India*. New Delhi: Palgrave Macmillan.

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

Global Research Journal of Business Management

Vol. 4, No. 1: 60 - 79, 2024

STUDENTS' MENTORSHIP PROGRAMS & QUALITY SUPERVISION OF RESEARCH WORKS

- Muraya, D.N. & Wairimu, N. E. (2020) Effects of teacher mentoring on the classroom practices of lower grade primary school teachers in Kwale County, Kenya; 15 (8); 473-486.
- Naim, M.F. & Lenka, U. (2017) 'How does mentoring contribute to gen y employees' intention to stay? An Indian perspective', *Europe's Journal of Psychology*, 13(2), pp.314-335.
- Ofobruku, S. A & Nwakoby, N. P. (2018) Effects of mentoring on employees' performance in selected family business in Abuja, Nigeria; *Singaporean Journal of business economics, and management studies*:.4 (9); 9-15
- Okurame, D.E. & Ajayi, M.S. (2017) 'Effects of mentoring and feedback on the cognitive task performance of Nigerian undergraduate students', *International Journal of Evidence Based Coaching and Mentoring*, 15(2), 124-139.
- Peretomode, V.F., & Ikoya, P. (2019). Mentorship: A strategic technique for achieving excellence, manpower development and nation building? *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 10(2), 17-24.
- Udom, I.D., Okoedion, E.G. & Okolie, U.C. (2020) Impact of mentorship on students' academic excellence in University of Benin, Benin City; *Journal Plus Education*; 25 (1) 211-228.
- Waddell, J., Martin, J., Schwind, J.K., & Lapum, J.L. (2016). A faculty based mentorship circle: Positioning new faculty for success. *Canadian Journal of Higher Education*, 46(4), 60-75.
- Walbe, S. (2019) Mentorship Culture and Academic Staff Job Effectiveness in Public Universities in North-Central Nigeria; *Kampala International University Journal of Social Sciences*; 5(4): 295-302.

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

Global Research Journal of Business Management

Vol. 4, No. 1: 80 - 90, 2024

STRATEGIC PLANNING PRACTICES AND ORGANIZATIONAL RESILIENCE

Strategic Planning Practices and Organizational Resilience: A Conceptual Review

George, Yebimodei Esther, PhD¹ & Odubo, Angonimi²

Department of Business Administration and Management

Federal Polytechnic Ekowe, Bayelsa State

kariebi2002@yahoo.com

07037211294

ABSTRACT

Research purpose: This study examined the conceptual examination of how strategic planning approaches impact organizational resilience. Managers that implemented strategic planning within their organizations were able to focus their efforts on improving management, which caused this tendency to shift. Although there have been claims that putting strategic planning into practice enhances management, some worry that not all maritime nations that attempt to create strategic plans are happy with the outcome. It also discusses how executives' use of planning methodologies undermines resilience when they don't align their objectives with the financial resources that their maritime business requires. The study sought to determine the relationship between functional coverage and robustness as well as the effects of planning formality on robustness and adaptability. The study also aimed to ascertain how robustness is affected by functional coverage.

Methodology: The Dynamic Capabilities Theory served as the study's cornerstone. The theory and the study are related because an organization's "dynamic capabilities" are its ability to integrate, develop, and reconfigure internal and external competences to meet rapidly changing settings.

Conclusion: The study concluded that the dynamic environment in which an organization operates may have an impact on the organization's well-being. Long-term viability of even physically and technologically adequate maritime enterprises may be compromised if they are unable to build up enough resilience through strategic planning.

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

Global Research Journal of Business Management

Vol. 4, No. 1: 80 - 90, 2024

STRATEGIC PLANNING PRACTICES AND ORGANIZATIONAL RESILIENCE

Key words: Strategic planning techniques, Organizational resilience, Planning formality, Adaptability, Functional coverage, Robustness.

INTRODUCTION

The ability of a maritime to anticipate potentially unfavorable events, adapt potential countermeasures to contain threats, and recover by returning the organization or state as close to a stable and acceptable state as feasible is known as organizational resilience (Burnard & Bhamra, 2011; Umoh et al., 2013). By establishing a resistance system against the multiple disruptions that constantly occur in the organization, an organization can demonstrate its readiness for unforeseen events by its ability to endure shock (Umoh, 2007; Umoh et al., 2013).

According to McManus et al. (2008), definitions of organizational resilience give birth to a number of concepts, such as environmental knowledge, anticipatory awareness, preparedness level, recovery capability, and adaptability. Organizational resilience is defined by Anarelli and Nonino (2016) and Annarelli et al. (2020) as the ability of the organization to tolerate unanticipated changes and disruptions as a result of strategic awareness and cooperation between internal and external capabilities. Although there are many different measures of resilience, this study accepts robustness and adaptability as the criteria for organizational resilience. Starr et al. defined adaptability as "the ability of a firm to alter its strategy, operations, governance structure, management systems, and decision-support capabilities to withstand perturbations and disruptions" (2003).

Academics and business leaders have focused their attention on integrating management processes through strategic planning in recent years for a variety of reasons, including the ever-increasing degree of uncertainty in the competitive environment, political and economic unpredictability, the development of complex corporate structures, and the ongoing and rapid changes in the global marketplace. Pearce et al. (2007) define strategic planning as the process of identifying the main goals, plans, and directives that control how resources are acquired and allocated to achieve an organization's objectives. Despite its extensive use, there is still disagreement on the scope, goals, and effects of strategic planning processes on the overall effectiveness of the business.

In the hotel industry, the word "strategic" has become overused, claim Nanus and Lundberg (2008). A business makes decisions based on its strategy in every area, including recruiting procedures and competitive positioning. The industry, like other businesses that compete fiercely in their respective marketplaces, has significant obstacles from these kinds of problems. However, Nanus and Lundberg (2008) go on to say that developing an effective strategy is a continuous effort in situations that are always changing because a good plan

STRATEGIC PLANNING PRACTICES AND ORGANIZATIONAL RESILIENCE

today could not work tomorrow. Systematic strategic planning is under increasing pressure due to the sector's dynamic character. Moreover, managers appear to have a primary duty to oversee, evaluate, and enhance the process' efficacy given that the goal of strategic planning is to enhance strategic performance. Precise, realistic goals, a logical integration of several follow-up actions, and most importantly, a dedication to carrying out the plan are all necessary for effective strategic planning.

Statement of the Problem

Few research have examined the impact of strategic planning on organizational management practices (Brendan, 2008). This is partially because some businesses don't place as much emphasis on the quality of the services they offer. Managers that implemented strategic planning within their organizations were able to focus their efforts on improving management, which caused this tendency to shift. There have been concerns expressed over the fact that not all firms that attempt to create strategic plans are happy with the process, despite claims of better management through strategic planning implementation.

It also notes that executives who use planning methodologies undermine resilience by not aligning their plans with the financial resources that their company has to take into account (Stonner, 2008). The planning process operates in a dynamic setting, and staff members have voiced concerns about its propensity to be inflexible and inflexible. Inability to adjust poorly to changing environments frequently has a detrimental effect on the company. They feel that the strategic planning process is impracticable if it is not combined with actions, which lowers resilience (Brendan, 2006). Therefore, the goal of the study was to determine how strategic planning methods affect organizational resilience.

Conceptual Framework

This study was anchored on the concepts below:

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

Global Research Journal of Business Management

Vol. 4, No. 1: 80 - 90, 2024

STRATEGIC PLANNING PRACTICES AND ORGANIZATIONAL RESILIENCE

Sources: Strategic Planning Practices Dimensions: (Standing, S. Standing, C., & Liu, C. 2008); Tan, Teoh & Cheah, 2019). Organisational Resilience Measures: (Kantur & Itseri-Say, 2015; Sylva & Ojiabo, 2018; Akpan, Johnny & Sylva, 2022).

Objectives of the Study

The primary objectives of this study were to analyze the literature conceptually and look into how organizational resilience is impacted by strategic planning methods. The specific objectives of the study were to: Examine the relationship between planning formality and adaptability.

2. To evaluate the impact of planning formality on robustness
3. To ascertain the impact of functional coverage on adaptation
4. To assess the effect of functional coverage on robustness

Review of Related Literature

Strategic Planning Practices

The term "strategic planning" has changed significantly over time. "Strategic planning is not an extrapolation of current budgets or a simple aggregation of functional plans," states Steiner (1979). In reality, it's a systems strategy that guides an organization through the choppy waves of its ever-changing environment to help it accomplish its goals. Companies employ several planning techniques to handle changes, as stated by Athiyaman and Robertson (1995). These systems have developed to meet the needs of an ever-evolving corporate environment. Various variables can be used to conceptualize strategic planning and determine the process's efficacy. Scholars have analyzed and discussed the strategic planning process from a number of perspectives. Two themes will be covered in this paper: planning formality and functional coverage.

Planning Formality

The formality of the plans is among the most significant elements of the planning process. Armstrong (1982) defined formal strategic planning as a process that includes determining the organization's long-term objectives, creating and evaluating alternative approaches, and putting in place a system for monitoring the plan's performance after it is implemented. Formality indicators include the usage of planning manuals, the relevance of written plans (Ramanujam & Venkatraman, 1987), and the duration of the planning horizon (Bantel, 1993). Businesses that support the resource dependency perspective and Brinckmann et al. (2010) contend that the resources they require are available to them in their surroundings. As a result, the authors argue that formal written plans can aid an organization in gaining the confidence of outside investors, which could be crucial to the organization's survival and growth. They also suggest that written documentation may help firms tell stakeholders, both internal and external, about their goals, plans, and daily tasks.

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

Global Research Journal of Business Management

Vol. 4, No. 1: 80 - 90, 2024

STRATEGIC PLANNING PRACTICES AND ORGANIZATIONAL RESILIENCE

Functional coverage

"The extent of coverage given to different functional areas with a view to integrating different functional requirements into a general management perspective" is how Ramanujam & Venkatraman (1987) describe functional coverage. Variations in functional coverage might result from strategic differences in the competitive attitudes of enterprises within an industry, according to Ramanujam et al. (1986). The authors state that certain firms may place a higher priority on pricing and volume than others, and that some may place a higher priority on product differentiation and customer service. A balanced focus on all areas may be more acceptable when general management is the main factor impacting performance.

Organizational Resilience

Organizational resilience is defined by Burnard and Bhamra (2011) and Umoh et al. (2013) as a company's capacity to foresee possibly unfavorable events, adjust possible countermeasures to contain threats, and recover by bringing the company as close as possible to a stable and acceptable condition. The capacity of an organization to absorb shock by erecting a resistance mechanism in the face of several disruptions that commonly occur in the workplace may demonstrate that organization's preparation for unforeseen events (Umoh, 2007; Umoh et al., 2013). In the words of McManus et al. (2008), "the various concepts that emerge from definitions of organisational resilience include environmental knowledge, preparedness level, anticipatory behaviour, adaptation, and recovery capacity." Anarelli and Nonino (2016) and Annarelli et al. (2020) describe organizational resilience as the capacity of the company to withstand unforeseen shocks and disruptions as a consequence of strategic awareness and collaboration between internal and external capabilities.

Adaptability

In order to survive in the contemporary economic environment, a firm must possess the capacity to swiftly modify or adjust to novel situations. An adaptable company has to be ready to react to outside dangers as well as opportunities. As per Gîrneală (2014), a company can uphold values such as building strong relationships with customers and staff, operating with minimal waste, taking calculated risks and learning from them, maintaining transparency with internal and external communities, having the backing of stakeholders, and enabling employees to grow, collaborate, create, innovate, discover, and experiment with growth through adaptability.

Robustness

The capacity of a robust system to withstand shock from outside as well as from within (Chandra & Grabis, 2007). According to Agarwal et al. (2007), a system is considered robust if there is no damage that results in a major loss of form and function. When a system is subjected to even one vulnerability mode, it may lose some of its resistance. Paravard et al. (2007) define robustness as a system's ability to adapt its behavior in the face of unanticipated

changes in the external environment or malfunctions within the system. A company's robustness is its capacity to operate in a range of conditions. However, a company's ability to adapt goes beyond just its capacity for independence and teamwork. Enhancing the organization's entire ability to lead and adapt to change should be the aim of capacity building. Systems, rules, procedures, technology, structures, and cultures are all areas where managers should have an impact.

Theoretical Foundation

The Dynamic Capabilities Theory served as the study's cornerstone. The theory is pertinent to the study because dynamic capabilities are a firm's capacity to integrate, develop, and reconfigure internal and external competences to address rapidly changing situations.

The Theory of Dynamic Capabilities

The theory of dynamic capabilities states that when conditions change, current asset positions may deteriorate and new resource configurations may become more popular. To these criticisms, the dynamic capability perspective provides an answer. The basic notion of dynamic capabilities, according to Teece et al. (1997), was a company's potential to "integrate, build and reconfigure internal and external competencies to address rapidly changing environments". Dynamic Capabilities Dynamic maintains that an organization's ability to reinvent, reorganize, and reposition itself is a major determinant of its performance. Some characteristics of organizational change processes, such as organizational resilience, creativity, entrepreneurial behavior, organizational transformation, and crisis management, have been described by the theory of dynamic capabilities (e.g., Sylva & Ojiabo, 2018; Vogel & Güttel, 2013). With regard to actors' impacts on routine adaption processes and renewal, Dynamic Capabilities Dynamic is intended to provide a theoretical framework (Eisenhardt & Martin, 2000; Teece et al., 1997; Teece, 2007; Zollo & Winter, 2002).

Empirical Review

Gichunge (2010) looked at the impact of formal strategic planning on the organizational performance of medium-sized manufacturing enterprises in Nairobi, Kenya. This study attempted to assess the degree of formal strategic planning adoption by medium-sized manufacturing businesses in Kenya, the impact of various administrative and legislative elements on that adoption, and the relationship between the level of competition and that adoption. It also looked at how the organization's operations were impacted by legal and administrative factors.

Ahiazu and Eketu's (2015) study empirically assesses the relationship between product innovation and organizational resilience using primary data from a few public colleges in the south-south of Nigeria. This study looked into three different organizational resilience dimensions: product innovation, situation awareness, adaptive capacity, and milestone vulnerability. We looked at three null hypotheses with the Spearman rank order correlation. The results showed a robust correlation between organizational resilience and product

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

Global Research Journal of Business Management

Vol. 4, No. 1: 80 - 90, 2024

STRATEGIC PLANNING PRACTICES AND ORGANIZATIONAL RESILIENCE

innovation. The results also demonstrate that product innovation had a major impact on the institutions' awareness, sensitivity, and adaptability.

Conclusion

In this study, two organizational resilience indices were applied. The first measure, called adaptability, is based on two parts and examines how effectively an organization can modify its operations, governance structure, management systems, strategy, and decision-support abilities to survive shocks and disruptions. The company's ability to withstand external shocks and maintain steady operations in the face of uncertainty is evaluated by the two components that comprise the second robustness dimension.

The welfare of an organization's employees may be impacted by its dynamic work environment. In the long term, even a technologically and financially sound firm might not be able to exist if strong resilience is not built via strategic planning. The research suggests the following actions:

1. To increase the organization's resilience, the management should tighten up its strategic planning procedures and maintain a close watch on external events. They will be able to recognize urgent needs and act quickly to satisfy them as a result.
2. Organizations ought to create strategic strategies that will strengthen their resilience and help them get through difficult times.
3. It is advised that managers of Nigerian companies take proactive steps to set themselves up to be among the first to recognize and obtain outside knowledge pertaining to their sector, services, and technology. This will enable the businesses to outperform competitors and swiftly adapt to changes in the environment.
4. To reiterate, managers of the organization should be on the lookout for any shifts in the preferences and needs of their customers so they may quickly adjust policies and/or services to meet those needs.

REFERENCES

- Agarwal, J., Blockley, D. I., and Woodman, N. J. (2007). System vulnerability to possible dangers. The essay "Civil Engineering and Environmental Systems" appears on pages 141 through 165 of volume 18.
- Ahiau, L. U., and Eketu, A. C. (2015). Investigating the relationship between organizational resilience and product innovation at public universities in Nigeria's south-south area. The reference may be found on pages 37–46 in the *European Journal of Business and Management*, volume 7, number 33.
- Johnny, E., Sylva, W., and Akpan, E. E. (2022). The study's main objective is to investigate Nigerian manufacturing companies' organizational resilience and dynamic capacity. The source of the information is *Vision*, volume 26, issue 1, pages 48–64.

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

Global Research Journal of Business Management

Vol. 4, No. 1: 80 - 90, 2024

STRATEGIC PLANNING PRACTICES AND ORGANIZATIONAL RESILIENCE

- Annarelli, A., and Nonino, F. (2016). An examination of the present research and prospective future routes for the strategic and operational management of organizational resilience. The material comes from an academic paper with the title "Omega" and pages 1–18.
- In 2020, Annarelli, A., Nonino, F., and Battistella, C. A paradigm for evaluating the effect of organizational resilience on the caliber of services The journal article titled "Sustainability" may be located on pages 958–963 of volume 12 of the journal.
- Armstrong, J. S. (1982) performed a review of empirical research on the value of formal planning for strategic choices. The Strategic Management Journal, volume 3, number 3, pages 197–211, published this study.
- Athiyaman and Robertson (1995) carried out an empirical study on the subject of strategic planning in large tourism businesses. The research was released on pages 199–205 of the journal Tourist Management, volume 16, issue 3
- Bantel, K. A. (1993) "The impact of top team, environment, and performance on the level of formality in strategic planning", Group and Organisation Management, 18 (4), 436-458.
- Brendan K. released an essay titled "HR Strategic Planning in Kenya" in 2006. Parastatals are the subject of this case study, which focuses on a survey report called "Special Report Number 7." This master's dissertation, from the University of Nairobi in Nairobi, Kenya, has not yet been published.
- Brinckmann, J., Grichnik, D., and Kapsa, D. (2010) ask if business owners should pursue their objectives more impulsively or by strategic planning. The Journal of Business Venturing, volume 25, issue 1, pages 24–40, released an article titled "A Meta-analysis on Contextual Factors Impacting the Business Planning–performance Relationship in Small Firms".
- Burnard, K., and Bhamra, R. (2011). Developing a conceptual framework to comprehend how organizations adapt to adversity and preserve stability is known as organizational resilience. The reference may be found in the International Journal of Production Research, specifically on pages 5581–5599, volume 49, issue 18.
- Cameron, K.S., & Quinn, R.E. (2011) is the source. Diagnosing and modifying company culture: Utilising the competing values framework. the third version. John Wiley & Sons, Inc.
- Chandra and Grabis (2007). Numerous facets of supply chain implementation and design are covered in the book "Supply Chain Configuration: Concepts, Solutions, and Applications, First Edition." The magazine is called Springer and it is based in New York.
- Chu (2012), Y. H. Examining the ability of small to medium enterprises in Hong Kong to endure and adapt to environmental instability. This thesis was presented in order to fulfill the requirements for the Doctor of Philosophy degree. University of RMIT.

- Duru, M. I., and Dialoke, I. (2017) The study looks at how specific media organizations in Imo State perform in relation to workforce planning. The International Journal of Social Sciences and Management Research, volume 3, issue 2, pages 1–7, is where the reference is found.
- Martin, J. A., and K. M. Eisenhardt (2000) The capacity of an organization to adjust, incorporate, and reorganize its resources and competences in reaction to shifting market conditions and opportunities is referred to as dynamic capabilities. Stated differently, it refers to an organization's ability to handle innovation and change in an effective and efficient manner. The source comes from the Strategic Management Journal, volume 21, issues 10/11, pages 1105 to 1121.
- Gichunge, E. M. (2010). The effect that formal strategic management has on a subset of Nairobi, Kenya's medium-sized manufacturing enterprises' performance
- Gîrneacă, A. (2014). A critical strategic skill that is especially useful in emergency situations is adaptability. Romania's capital city is Bucharest. Bucharest Academy of Economic Studies is the organization that is being discussed.
- Koufopoulos, D. N., and Gkliatis, I. P. (2013) Techniques of strategic planning used in the Greek hotel industry. The reference may be found on pages 571–587 in the European Business Review, volume 25, number 6. A DOI (Digital Object Identifier) for an article with the reference "EBR-08-2012-0045" may be found at the supplied website.
- A conceptually integrated paradigm for organizational resilience is offered by Kantur and Iseri-Say (2012). The reference comes from pages 762–773 of volume 18 of the Journal of Management & Organization.
- A DOI (Digital Object Identifier) for an article may be found at the specified website. The article may be viewed using this link.
- McManus, S. T. (2008). improving organizations' resilience to shocks and their ability to bounce back in New Zealand This paper is a PhD dissertation that was finished at Christchurch's University of Canterbury.
- The essay "In Quest of Strategic Planning" by Nanus, B., and Lundberg, C. (2008) appeared in Cornell Hotel and Restaurant Administration Quarterly, volume 29, number 2, pages 18–23.
- Nguyen, L. A., Jandug, L., Vesty, G. M., Dellaportas, S., and Pham, V.A.T. (2022). The effect of organizational culture on corporate accountants' ethical judgment and goals in Vietnam The following is the citation: Accounting, Auditing & Accountability Journal, volume 35, number 2, pages 325-354. The paper may be found at 10.1108/AAAJ-05-2020-4573.
- Salembier, P., Saoud, N., Darcy, S., Dugdale, J., and Pavard, B. (2007). the basic ideas of resilience and robustness and how to apply them to sociotechnical system design The given URL leads to a ResearchGate publication with the ID 241137999.

ISSN: 2811-1710 (Paper) ISSN: 2811-1729 (Online)

Global Research Journal of Business Management

Vol. 4, No. 1: 80 - 90, 2024

STRATEGIC PLANNING PRACTICES AND ORGANIZATIONAL RESILIENCE

"The tenuous link between formal strategic planning and financial performance" is the title of a 2007 research by Pearce, J. A., Freeman E., and Robinson R. B. that was published in the *Academy of Management Review*. The study is available on pages 658–675 in volume 12, issue 4.

In 1986, Venkatraman, N., Camillus, J., and Ramanujam, V. Analyse the efficacy of strategic planning using a discriminant analysis approach that incorporates numerous goals. The reference may be found on pages 347–372 in the *Academy of Management Review*, volume 29, number 2.

The paper "Planning system characteristics and planning effectiveness" by Venkatraman, N. and Ramanujam, V. (1987) was published in the *Strategic Management Journal*. The efficiency of planning systems and their features are examined in relation to each other. The article appears on pages 453–468 of volume 8, issue 5.

Starr, R., Newfrock, J., and Delurey, M. (2003). Improving business resilience: Reducing risk in the globalized economy The referenced work may be found in "*Strategy and Business*," volume 30, pages 70–79.

A model for efficiently managing information within strategic partnerships in the biotechnology industry is presented by Standing, Standing, and Liu (2008). The reference may be found in the journal "*Systems Research and Behavioural Sciences*", specifically on pages 783-796, volume 25, issue 6.

A. G. Steiner wrote the book "*Top Management Planning*" in 1979. It's published under the title "New York: MacMillan Publishing."

Sylva, W., and Ojiabo, U. (2018). Examining the influence of management proactiveness on the infrastructure operational capabilities and resilience of indigenous airlines in Nigeria. The reference comes from the journal "*Information and Knowledge Management*", volume 8, issue 4, pages 50 to 76.

In 2019, Tan, C. H., Teoh, A. P., Ramayah, T., and Cheah, J. H. Important variables influencing Malaysian virtual teams' performance. The reference comes from the journal *Kybernetes*, volume 48, number 9, pages 2065-2092. The following DOI points to the article: <https://doi.org/10.1108/K-01-2018-0031>.

D. J. Teece (2007) Examining the idea of dynamic capabilities: Recognizing the traits and fundamental ideas of long-term corporate success The reference may be found in the pages 1319 to 1350 of the *Strategic Management Journal*, volume 28, issue 13.

Shuen, A., Teece, D. J., and Pisano, G. (1997). The capacity to change with the times and react appropriately is known as strategic management. The source comes from the *Strategic Management Journal*, volume 18, number 7, pages 509 to 535.

Umoh (2007) You may find the paper "*Flooding problems in Rivers State*" on pages 44–60 in the *Journal of Environmental Science*, volume 4, number 2.

Umoh, G. I., Amah, E., and Wokocho, I. H. (2013). Improving production efficiency and promoting company growth are the goals for Nigeria's manufacturing industry. The

- reference may be found on pages 3 through 7 of the *Industrial Engineering Letter*, volume 3, issue 9.
- Vogel, R., and Güttel, W. H. (2013). A bibliometric analysis of the strategic management paradigm of dynamic capacities. The reference may be found on pages 426–446 in the *International Journal of Management Reviews*, volume 15, number 4.
- Zeb, A., Safi, A., Rabnawaz, M., Hussain, K., Zeb, F., and Akbar, F. (2021). The model of organisational culture, innovation, and performance based on the competing value framework. Page numbers 658–683, volume 27, issue 2, of the journal "*Business Process Management Journal*" is the source of the citation given. Access to the manuscript may be made at <https://doi.org/10.1108/BPMJ-11-2019-0464>.
- Winter, S. G. and Zollo, M. (2002). the intentional gathering of information and the growth of adaptive abilities. "*Organisation Science*", volume 13, issue 3, pages 339 to 351, is the source of the reference.
- Umoh, G. I., Amah, E., & Wokocha, I. H. (2013). Production improvement function and corporate growth in the Nigerian manufacturing industry. *Industrial Engineering Letter*, 3(9), 3–7.
- Vogel, R., and W. H. Güttel (2013). A bibliometric study of the dynamic capabilities approach in strategic management 15(4), 426–446 in *International Journal of Management Reviews*.
- Zeb, A., Akbar, F., Hussain, K., Safi, A., Rabnawaz, M., & Zeb, F. (2021). The rival value framework model of performance, innovation, and organizational culture 10.1108/BPMJ-11-2019-0464. *Business Process Management Journal*, 27(2), 658–683.
- Zollo, M., & Winter, S. G. (2002). Deliberate learning and the growth of dynamic capacities. 13(3) *Organization Science*, 339–351.
- Umoh, G. I., Amah, E., & Wokocha, I. H. (2013). Production improvement function and corporate growth in the Nigerian manufacturing industry. *Industrial Engineering Letter*, 3(9), 3–7.
- Vogel, R., & Güttel, W. H. (2013). The dynamic capability view in strategic management: A bibliometric review. *International Journal of Management Reviews*, 15(4), 426–446.
- Zeb, A., Akbar, F., Hussain, K., Safi, A., Rabnawaz, M., & Zeb, F. (2021). The competing value framework model of organizational culture, innovation and performance. *Business Process Management Journal*, 27(2), 658–683. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BPMJ-11-2019-0464>.
- Zollo, M., & Winter, S. G. (2002). Deliberate learning and the evolution of dynamic capabilities. *Organisation Science*, 13(3), 339–351.

Functionalism: Role of Gender and Structure in Shaping Organisational Behaviour in Dangote Cement PLC

Kenechi John Onyike¹, Grace Ifeoma Anukwe¹, Chiemelie Benneth Iloka^{1*}

¹ *Department of Marketing,*

Faculty of Management Sciences,

Enugu State University of Science and Technology (ESUT), Agbani

Enugu State, Nigeria.

Iloka.benneth@esut.edu.ng

Abstract

Research Purpose: Functionalist theory, emphasising the importance of social structures for societal stability, has sparked significant debate. Critically, it raises questions about the persistent segregation of women into domestic roles, despite their potential to contribute significantly in other domains. This research investigates how gender and organisational structure interact to shape organisational behaviour at Dangote Cement PLC, a major player in the Nigerian economy.

Methodology: This study employs a two-pronged approach. First, it conducts a systematic review of the existing literature exploring the relationship between gender, organisational structure, and their impact on organisational behaviour. Second, it analyses Dangote Cement PLC corporate press releases, focusing on initiatives and policies related to gender equality and organisational structure.

Findings: Findings reveal that Dangote Cement PLC is dedicated to promoting gender equality within its workforce. This commitment is evident in the company's efforts to create a corporate structure that offers equal opportunities for both men and women. However, despite these efforts, the representation of women in managerial positions remains disproportionately low.

Conclusion: Dangote Cement PLC commitment to gender equality is commendable. However, the lack of women in leadership positions reveals a disconnect between policy and actual practice.

Recommendations: The study recommends that Dangote Cement PLC implement more proactive measures to empower women and facilitate their ascension to leadership roles. This could include targeted mentorship programs, leadership training specifically designed for women, and transparent promotion processes that mitigate unconscious bias.

Key words: Behaviour, Functionalism, Gender, Organization, Structure.

1. Introduction

The concept of organisational behaviour, although old, has received little attention. This is mainly based on the fact that it is founded on culture, as culture underscores what is obtainable in a company. Therefore, most of the attention, at least in the academic setting, has been directed towards corporate culture. In this study, the focus is to assess organisational behaviour based on the functionalism paradigm within Dangote Cement PLC.

To be able to attain this objective, two topics: a) gender and b) structure—rationality, organisation, and bureaucracy—will be covered in relation to how functionalism shapes these topics and their implementation in Dangote Cement PLC. These topics will be used to demonstrate how functionalism shapes organisational behaviour in the company under review.

The remaining parts of this paper are divided into three sections. The next section focuses on discussing the functionalism perspective and its assumptions within the organisational setting. This is followed by a detailed discussion of the company, Dangote Cement PLC, with highlights of the topics considered and how they are integrated in the company. The third section is an analysis of the functionalism paradigm, in relation to the two topics and how they shape organisational behaviour in Dangote Cement PLC. Finally, conclusions and recommendations are presented based on the findings from the study.

2. Functionalism Perspectives

Crossman (2023) posited that the functionalist perspective, also known as the functionalist perspective, is one of the major theoretical perspectives in sociology. The work of Emile Durkheim is attributed to laying the foundation for this paradigm, as the scholar was especially interested in understanding how social order is possible or how relative stability can be created and maintained in society. Thus, this paradigm focuses on the macro-level of social structure as opposed to the everyday micro-level of life. Herbert Spencer, Talcott Parsons, and Robert K. Merton are some of the notable theorists in this paradigm (Whittaker, 2015).

The major assumption of this paradigm is that society is more than the sum of people within it; instead, each aspect of society functions to ensure the overall stability of society at large. As envisioned by Durkheim, society is an organism because each component plays a pivotal role and cannot function on its own. All the components are important, and they also depend on each other to effectively function. Thus, when one part experiences a crisis, other parts must adapt in order to fill the void (Thompson, 2023).

Within the functionalist theory, the different parts of society are primarily made up of social institutions, and each is designed to fill a different need. Therefore, family, economy, media, government, education, and religion are all vital to understanding this theory, as are the major institutions that define sociology. In line with the functionalist view, an institution only exists because it serves a vital role in the overall functioning of society. In the event that the institution no longer serves its role, it will die a natural death (Solanas, 2019). When new

needs emerge or existing ones evolve, new institutions will be created in order to meet these needs.

In many modern societies, the government provides education for the children of the family, and the working members of the family pay taxes in return to keep the state running. The families are also known to focus on education to ensure that their children grow on the right path and can access good jobs to be able to raise and support other family members. Therefore, the children become law-abiding taxpayers that support the overall running of the state. Based on the functionalists' view, *ceteris paribus*, the components of society will provide stability, order, and productivity (Kavous, 2010). However, if all does not go well, society is expected to adapt in order to produce new forms of stability, order, and productivity.

The main emphasis of the functionalists is that consensus and order must exist in society, and there should be a focus on shared public values and social stability. Based on this perspective, disorganisation in the system, like deviant behaviours, is known to bring about change because the societal components must adjust in order to attain stability. When any part of the system becomes dysfunctional, other parts are affected, and this creates social issues, prompting the need for immediate social change (Kavous, 2010).

When integrated into the context of gender, the implication is that both genders have a role to play in order to ensure the smooth running of society. For instance, men are expected to protect and provide for the family, while women are expected to nurture the children and care for the overall wellbeing of the household. In the organisational setting, a similar outcome is expected as both genders have specific roles they play towards ensuring the sustainable operation of any given corporate entity.

Similarly, implication is also obtainable in the context of corporate structure—rationality, organisation, and bureaucracy. Corporate structure deals with the arrangement of all components of the organisation, such as hierarchy, departments, roles, etc. In the corporate setting, all these components are important and dependent on each other for the effective and efficient functioning of the corporation.

3. Organizational Background

For this study, the organization being considered is Dangote Cement, one of the public listed companies under Dangote Industries Limited Nigeria. For a start, Dangote Industries Limited is a diversified and fully integrated conglomerate that maintains operations in Nigeria and the larger African continent, covering wide range of sectors that influence sugar, cement, salt, condiments, energy, packaging, fertilizer, port operations, and petrochemicals (Dangote Industries Limited, 2023). Its core operations are focused on providing value-added, local products and services that are in lien with the basic needs of the people and they do so through construction and operation of larger scale manufacturing facilities in the African markets where they operate. The company reiterated its focus on building local

manufacturing capacity that is capable of creating employment, increasing local value additions, and reducing capital flight (Dangote Industries Limited, 2023).

Dangote Cement PLC, one of the operations of Dangote Industries Limited, is the leading cement company in the entire sub-Saharan African region and maintains operations in 10 African markets (Dangote Cement PLC, 2022). In line with the vision and mission of the parent company, Dangote Cement PLC affirms that it is resolute in transforming Africa while creating sustainable value for its stakeholders. Per its 2022 annual report, the company made ₦1,618.3bn (17% increase from the previous year), with ₦382.3bn in profit after tax (representing 4.9% increase from the previous year) and ₦20 pay out in dividends (Dangote Cement PLC, 2022). Essentially, this represents a robust and sustainable performance, notwithstanding the economic woes faced by corporations in Nigeria in the reported year.

The first topic focuses on gender, specifically gender equality, and it is one of the core values of Dangote Cement PLC. As of 2022, the total number of women on the company's board was 26.7% (Dangote Cement PLC, 2022). In essence, both women and men play a significant role in the smooth running of the company. Both parties need to execute their functions properly, and where one fails, the other party will need to fill in the void. Therefore, it is necessary to assess how both genders play their roles, as well as their supporting functions, in the company and the impact of their roles on the overall sustainability of the company.

Secondly, structure is pivotal to the smooth running of any given corporation, and Dangote Cement PLC is no exception. It is the structure that clearly defines roles, expectations, rewards, and the overall culture of the company. For instance, in the workforce, the company has created a clear structure to ensure equal opportunity for all members, including those with disabilities. It focuses more on performance and outcome—the ability of the workforce to meet defined targets (Dangote Cement PLC, 2022).

Clearly, Dangote Cement PLC is a good company for this assessment because there are defined practices that reflect the two topics considered, and the company's performance is clearly founded on the functionalism paradigm because there are numerous independent components that must function together for the company to attain its defined objectives.

4. Discussion and Analysis

4.1. Gender Equality in Dangote Cement PLC

In its 2022 annual report, Dangote Cement PLC detailed how it has been able to integrate its environmental, social, and governance (ESG) goals. In discussing its core values for stakeholders, the company pointed out that one of its values for its people is to promote the campaign on gender diversity, and to do so, Dangote Cement joined the Nigeria2Equal programme through the Dangote Women Network (DWN). This objective is in line with its strategic UN goals (Dangote Cement PLC, 2022). For Dangote Cement PLC, leadership and development remain at the centre of its plans, and it places gender diversity at the forefront of the leadership plans. The company further reiterated that this is one of its priority goals, and it will continue to allocate a considerable number of resources towards making sure that the

women employed within its workplace are prepared, well-equipped, and supported across different corporate challenges they might face. To further demonstrate this, the number of females employed at the senior management level increased from 9% in 2021 to 15% in 2022; the number of females employed at the executive management level increased from 12% in 2021 to 13% in 2022; and the total number of females in its workforce (representing permanent employees) increased from 8% in 2021 to 9% in 2022 (Dangote Cement PLC, 2022).

According to Garner (2019), structural functionalism focuses on the structure of an organisation or system—how roles are patterned, forms of institutions, and the overall articulation of institutions in society—with the main aim being to explain these structures in terms of their functions and contribution towards ensuring stability and persistence in society.

Within the context of Dangote Cement PLC, structural functionalism imply that the company should have clearly articulated roles and patterns that must be followed by the workforce. There are certain functions that are best suited for men and those best suited for women, and at the same time, the company should be able to provide all genders with equal opportunity to excel in their fields. Therefore, by understanding these values, articulated and shaped by the UN development goals, Dangote Cement is moving in the right direction by empowering women to exist and excel in their workforce. However, it must be pointed out that having just 8% of women in permanent employment position imply that there is more to be done.

4.2. Structure – Rationality, Organization and Bureaucracy in Dangote Cement PLC

In a central sense, organisational structure relates to the people that make the company function and how they are articulated, organised and empowered influence the overall functioning of the company. In the case of Dangote Cement PLC, the company employees over 22,000 permanent and contract staff that cut across 25 nationalities, different geographical areas, and equipped with the right expertise. Further demographic details reveal that they come with different ages, schooled in different disciplines, and these features converge to give them the market leadership that helps position and sustain the company as a leader in the African continent (Dangote Cement PLC, 2022).

The company operates a top-down organisational structure, with managers passing information down to the employees through their different departmental heads and supervisors. Therefore, there is a high degree of bureaucracy in the company, based on clearly defined procedures and operational approaches that the employees must strictly adhere to in delivering their designated functions. To ensure that the employees have the right skills and expertise, Dangote Cement PLC commits a significant amount of funds and efforts towards training and development programs. In 2021, the company trained 16,816 employees while investing ₦553,219,505.40 in the said training and development programmes, and this increased to 24,641 employees trained in 2022 with another investment of ₦812,129,204.79. These training and development programmes are aimed at building professional competence and leadership skills among employees (Dangote Cement PLC, 2022).

Still on the principle of structural functionalism, Josphat (2023) posited that society is viewed as a structure that is equipped with interrelated parts designed to fulfil the needs of people in society. Therefore, one needs to look beyond the individual and consider social facets like morals, culture, laws, and beliefs. The society is viewed as full of stability and harmony, with unemployment considered to be a factor that helps to balance the society. Therefore, it does not see anything wrong with inequality, unlike Marxism.

Similarly, in Dangote Cement PLC, structural functionalism explains the company's behaviour as it relates to rationality, organisation, and bureaucracy. Through organisation, the company is able to structure its system into different departments, and each department is charged with responsibility. When these responsibilities merge together, the outcome is sustainable productivity. On the same note, a high degree of bureaucracy ensures that certain individuals in the company are empowered to make decisions that affect everybody or certain people, while others will have to follow the decisions made (irrespective of whether or not they are happy with them). This ensures consistency in its operations and improves the company's ability to yield productive outcomes. The rationale for this is based on the understanding that different individuals have different skills and expertise, and it is in the best interest of the company to put these skills where they can yield the right outcome. Since no man is a "jack of all trades," Dangote Cement PLC has been able to structure its workforce in such a way that people can utilise the best of their ability to produce desired outcomes.

In essence, it is clear that structural functionalism influences organizational behaviour in Dangote Cement PLC. This is because it leads to the clear definition of functions and roles, as well as attaching the right people to these functions and roles. Through structural functionalism, the company is able to create a strong culture that enforces clear standards and expectations from the workforce.

5. Conclusion and Recommendation

This study sought to assess the functionalism paradigm and how it influences organisational behaviour. To better understand the relationship, the topics of gender and structure were integrated into the study. Overall, functionalism was defined as a perspective that is based on the understanding of society as a system that is made up of different components, and each of these components must function together in order to create coherence and stability. While all the components are independent, the overall stability and harmony of society will depend on all of them functioning together. Where one component fails, it is expected that the other components must be able to fill the void immediately in order to create consistency and sustainability in society. Applied to the organisational setting, the implication is that all the components in an organisation are important, and they need to function together in order to create consistency and stability. The top management depends on the lower-level employees to ensure that the company's operations are sustained, while the lower-level employees depend on the top management for the right direction and ideas to follow towards creating the overall objectives.

This view was integrated into Dangote Cement PLC as it relates to gender and structure in the company. On the topic of gender, it was revealed that the company clearly understands that both male and female employees are pivotal for its overall sustainability, and it continues to push for the employment and engagement of more female employees within its workforce. On the side of structure, the company operates on a clearly defined structure, bureaucracy, and organisation with roles and functions that are expected of each level of employee. It understands that employees are not equal, although necessary measures must be put in place to ensure that they function together because the top management needs the lower-level employees and vice versa.

While the issues of gender and structure seem to be clearly defined and integrated in the company, there are areas that need improvements, and recommendations are made for these areas, as detailed in the table below.

Table 1. Recommendations

Recommendations	Rationale	Obstacles to implementation
Improve employment opportunities for women.	Presently, only 8% of its permanent workforce are females and this shows that there is a lot to be come in terms of giving women more opportunities to join and excel in Dangote group. While 26% of the boards are women, there is a need to increase the overall number of female employees in its workforce.	The major obstacle could be qualifications and expertise. Most of the roles in Dangote Cement PLC
Empower employees to make decisions	The high level of bureaucracy implies that the employees are not empowered to make decisions that could affect their own productivity. However, it must be stated that there are instances where the employees might have to make immediate decisions in order to affect their overall productivity and depending on the existing bureaucracy could negatively impact the said productivity. Thus, it is necessary that the employees are empowered, at least to some extent, within their roles, to make decisions. Another advantage of such is that it could breed creativity and innovation in the system, leading to improved performance.	The major setback here is how to monitor and control the decisions being made by lower-level employees. If employees are empowered to make decision within their own work setting, they might end up drifting the company from its main focus.

<p>Improve commitment to the general stakeholders.</p>	<p>From all indication, it is clear that Dangote Cement PLC is primarily focused on improving returns for the shareholders. While this is necessary, it must be said that modern day business setting requires attending to the need of the general stakeholders. For instance, they need to be genuinely committed to the impact of their operations on the environment.</p>	<p>The absence of clearly defined targets makes it difficult to assess whether the company is moving in the right or wrong direction when it comes to assessing the environmental impact of their operations.</p>
--	---	---

References

- Crossman, A. (2020). Understanding Functionalist Theory. *ThoughtCo*. Retrieved from: <https://www.thoughtco.com/functionalist-perspective-3026625>
- Dangote Cement PLC (2022). Dangote Cement Plc: Annual Report and Accounts 2022. Retrieved from: <https://cement.dangote.com/wp-content/uploads/2023/03/DCP-2022-Annual-Report-2.pdf>
- Dangote Industries Limited (2023). About Dangote Industries Limited. Retrieved from: <https://dangote.com/about-us/>
- Garner, R. T. (2019). Structural Functional Theory. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781405165518.wbeoss289.pub2>
- Josphat, K. (2023). A Comparison of Structural Functionalism and Marxism Theories in Sociology. Retrieved from: <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/comparison-structural-functionalism-marxism-theories-sociology-k-dweyf>
- Kavous, A. (2010). Globalization and Finance: Four Paradigmatic Views. *Journal of Globalization Studies*,1(2).
- Solanas, E. V. (2019). The Functionalist Paradigm. *Medium*. Retrieved from: <https://medium.com/@HarmonizeHumanity/the-functionalist-paradigm-edbf1c437178>
- Thompson, K. (2023). Functionalism – an introduction. *Revisesociology*. Retrieved from: <https://revisesociology.com/2016/09/01/functionalism-sociology/>
- Whittaker, S. (2015). Why We Should Consider Both Functionalist and Interpretive Views of Organisational Culture. *LinkedIn*. Retrieved from: <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/why-we-should-consider-both-functionalist-views-simon-whittaker>

The Importance of Stakeholder Capitalism in Corporate Sustainability

Grace Ifeoma Anukwe¹, Kenechi John Onyike¹, Chiemelie Benneth Iloka¹

¹Department of Marketing,

Faculty of Management Sciences,

Enugu State University of Science and Technology (ESUT), Agbani,

Enugu State, Nigeria.

Iloka.benneth@esut.edu.ng

Abstract

Research Purpose: In a world grappling with climate change and social inequality, businesses face increasing pressure to operate sustainably. This study explores stakeholder capitalism as a potential driver of enhanced corporate performance, examining whether inclusive decision-making processes translate into tangible benefits.

Methodology: This research undertakes a comprehensive review of existing literature on stakeholder capitalism and its impact on business performance.

Findings: The review reveals that engaging stakeholders in decision-making fosters a sense of value and belonging within these stakeholder groups. This heightened sense of inclusion translates into increased commitment and dedication to the company's success, ultimately driving improved performance.

Conclusion: Stakeholder capitalism offers a compelling framework for achieving both corporate sustainability and enhanced performance. By prioritising the interests of all stakeholders, businesses can create a virtuous cycle of shared value and collective prosperity.

Key words: Capitalism, Company, Performance, Stakeholders, Sustainability.

1. Introduction

The article, **What Does “Stakeholder Capitalism” Mean to You?** discusses the concept of "stakeholder capitalism" and outlines four main types: instrumental, classic, beneficial, and structural. As a concept, stakeholder capitalism is all about catering to the interests of all stakeholders instead of solely focusing on generating financial returns for the shareholder (Spak & Lynd, 2021). The instrumental approach suggests that managers should consider stakeholders' interests when maximising long-term returns to shareholders. Classic stakeholderism emphasises ethical and legal obligations to stakeholders, irrespective of shareholder value. Beneficial stakeholderism seeks to improve the well-being of stakeholders, going beyond basic claims, and is more demanding than classic stakeholderism. Structural stakeholderism advocates giving nonshareholder stakeholders formal powers in corporate governance. Irrespective of the kind of stakeholderism being considered, emphasis is on the

need for corporate leaders to understand the implications of different stakeholder capitalism versions, be honest about their potential outcomes for stakeholders, society, and shareholders, and clarify the meaning of "stakeholder capitalism" (Paine, 2023).

In light of the forgoing, this entry presents a detailed analysis of the cover story as it relates to understanding stakeholder capitalism, its types, binding theory, and overall influence on business. To attain this objective, this research is divided into three main parts. The first part presents a summary of the cover story and the overall purpose of the study. Related themes from the cover story are analysed in the second part. The third part contains a discussion of the theories that underpin the cover story, and this is followed by a conclusion—a summary of the findings and directions.

2. Research synthesis

2.1. Themes related to the cover story

A number of themes have been identified in the cover story **What Does “Stakeholder Capitalism” Mean to You?”** and these themes are further discussed below.

- *Stakeholder capitalism*

Discussing the concept of stakeholder capitalism and its four main types, Paine (2023) pointed out that the past couple of years have witnessed an outpouring of statements and articles heralding the arrival of the concept of stakeholder capitalism, a new and more inclusive form of capitalism. The scholar went further to state that this form of capitalism comes with the promise of improving outcomes for its constituencies, bolstering companies, producing higher returns for the stakeholders in the long run, and eventually strengthening the economic situation of a company and society at large. Following this new ideology, there are varied recommendations pointing to the need for business leaders and corporate bodies to adopt a multistakeholder approach to governance instead of the traditionally stakeholder-centred approach, as the former comes with numerous benefits that the latter lacks.

D'Souza (2022) looked at conceptualising stakeholder capitalism, and the author viewed it as a system in which the company is oriented to serve the interests of its stakeholders. The major stakeholders in any company include its customers, employees, suppliers, shareholders, and the local communities. In the concept of stakeholder capitalism, the company's main focus is on how to create long-term value for these stakeholders, although this must also be done by maximising profits and enhancing overall shareholders' value. The interests of all stakeholders are always considered in every decision, as the company seeks to ensure that all stakeholders experience value through its operations. Those who support the concept do so based on the understanding that serving the interests of all the stakeholders, as opposed to focusing only on the interests of the shareholders, is critical for the long-term success of any business. Thus, they make the case that stakeholder capitalism is a sensible form of business decision as well as an ethical choice for any corporation (D'Souza, 2022). A number of studies, such as Abu Haija and Alrabba (2017) and Fortuna et al. (2020), have considered the

THE IMPORTANCE OF STAKEHOLDER CAPITALISM IN CORPORATE SUSTAINABILITY

relationship between stakeholder capitalism and the financial performance of a company. These studies reveal that stakeholder capitalism yields a positive influence on the performance of a company because its approach is centred on satisfying the individual needs of all the stakeholders in a business, not just the shareholders. By so doing, the company will keep its stream of stakeholders satisfied and committed to its overall growth.

Although the theory seems to offer a vivid explanation of what stakeholder capitalism is all about, one might raise the question, “What is stakeholder capitalism in practice?” As D'Souza (2022) pointed out, it can either be an ideology that leaders at individual companies adopt or a model that is enforced by the government via its laws and regulations. However, there are certain ways that a company could possibly demonstrate its commitment to stakeholder capitalism, and they include: paying fair wages; reducing the pay ratio between top management and regular staff; making the workplace safer; avoiding tax loopholes and lobbying for higher tax rates; offering good customer service; investing in local communities; ensuring that the company engages in honest marketing practices; and preventing activities that damage the environment.

Essentially, it seems to be on par with elements of corporate social responsibility. However, for a company to make such a commitment, there is no set of defined expectations. As JUST Capital, an independent research NGO firm, pointed out following the survey of 4,000 Americans on the issues they consider that corporations in the U.S. should prioritise, the respondents revealed that the top priorities of corporations should be acting ethically at the leadership level, paying fair wages, paying a living wage, providing equal opportunity, providing benefits and work-life balance, and ensuring that they offer beneficial products (JUST Capital, 2019). Paul Tudor Jones, the Chairman of JUST Capital, went further to state that stakeholder capitalism is more like a vow that the company makes to do business by providing services to all the stakeholders instead of focusing primarily on profitable returns. This is without a doubt due to the fact that shareholders are pivotal in any organisation, but it is critical that the company also consider the interests of workers, consumers, communities, the environment, and any other stakeholder when defining its objectives, especially in view of the fact that by doing so, the company will be able to deliver benefits not only to society but to its bottom line as well (JUST Capital, 2019). Going further, the Chair pointed out that this approach is not the status quo and does not imply abandoning capitalism altogether. Instead, it focuses on recalibrating the system in such a way that the business should have a deeper outlook and ensure that it creates an economy that is beneficial for every member of society (JUST Capital, 2019).

- ***Types of stakeholder capitalism***

As Paine (2023) also pointed out, there are four main types of stakeholder capitalism. The first is ***instrumental stakeholderism***, which focuses on maximising long-term stakeholder value. Held in this type of stakeholder capitalism is that considering and meeting the interests of all the stakeholders can actually lead to higher value for the shareholders, and this is based on the understanding that how a company treats its non-shareholding stakeholders can

THE IMPORTANCE OF STAKEHOLDER CAPITALISM IN CORPORATE SUSTAINABILITY

actually yield influence on shareholder value. Paine (2023) went further by stating that investing in other stakeholders could possibly lead to a decline in shareholder value in the short run, but it will eventually lead to improved value for the shareholders in the long run. On the same note, not considering the interests of other stakeholders might be beneficial to the shareholders in the short run but detrimental to the shareholders in the long run. Therefore, even the corporate leaders that are charged with maximising value for the shareholders should also ensure that they consider the interests of other stakeholders, as they have direct influence on the overall value of the shareholders in the long run.

This is probably the most common form of stakeholder capitalism, and as D'Souza (2022) pointed out, it is essential because it creates a system of happy individuals that are willing to ensure that the company moves forward. When the employees are happy, they will input the right resources and efforts (commitment and dedication) necessary for pushing the company forward, and this is also expected from the communities and other stakeholders. Therefore, in the long run, the company will be able to create a sustainable operation that will also secure the interests of the shareholders through sustainable, profitable performance. The instrumental stakeholders also have their criticisms, as pointed out by Paine (2023). One of them is that while it requires the business leaders to consider the interests of the entire stakeholder group, it does not require them to actually respect this interest except in cases where such would amount to financial benefits for the shareholders. Thus, what is implied is that any investment in the company's stakeholders must be done in the same manner as any other investment, and such investment should be made only when it is capable of increasing the net present value for the shareholders, and any investment found to be capable of reducing the long-term value for shareholders should be avoided.

The second type is *classic stakeholderism*, and it focuses more on the legitimate claims of the stakeholders. Held in this form of stakeholder capitalism is the notion that at least some of the interests of the stakeholders must be respected and also considered. Per the view of Paine (2023), this form of stakeholder capitalism differentiates among the interests of the stakeholders and prioritises those that are based on ethical or legal norms in place of those that are based on the major desires or wishes of the stakeholders. The foundational idea here is that the interests that are based on desires and wishes actually beget claims whose validity is not aligned with the foundational interests of the shareholders, and it underpins the obligations of the stakeholders that sit alongside strategic and financial imperatives. Recognised in this form of stakeholder capitalism is the idea that serving the interests of stakeholders will usually yield positive influence on the values of the shareholders; however, there are certain stakeholder interests that must also be considered, even when it doesn't increase value for the shareholders. On a similar note, existing studies (Strine & Zwillinger, 2020; Littenberg et al., 2020) agree that leadership should be selective in the kind of stakeholder's interest it tries to protect, as protecting the entire desires and wishes of the stakeholders should amount to more harm than good. However, there is a major criticism of classical stakeholderism, and it is simply the fact that determining the interest that must be protected is not always easy.

The third type is *beneficial stakeholderism*, which is centred on improving the outcomes for stakeholders. This version seeks not only to meet the basic claims of the stakeholders but also to improve their overall wellbeing significantly. It is founded on the belief that optimising returns for shareholders in the past four decades has resulted in numerous companies not making significant investments in their other constituencies, and this has also resulted in a disproportionate share of the gains being allocated to the owners of the capital. It is also rooted in the idea that running companies with the intention of improving overall value for the stakeholders will also help in addressing certain big issues and inequities that society presently faces and, in the process, help in protecting the health of the economy in the long run. The major criticism of this version is that the stakeholders should not expect much because it sometimes entails creating trade-offs among numerous interests (Littenberg et al., 2020). The last type of stakeholder capitalism is structural stakeholderism, which is focused on increasing stakeholder power. The advocates of this type of stakeholder capitalism seem to focus on hardwiring the interests of other stakeholders (aside from shareholders) into the process instead of relying entirely on the business leader to consider them, usually by using the defined power of the stakeholders to select directors or formal representation on the corporate board.

Where this idea has been widely adopted, particularly in Europe, the employees are the stakeholder group that has been accorded the power of representation on the board. However, there is a major criticism of this form of stakeholderism, and it is the fact that adding representatives for employees or other stakeholders to a corporate board does raise questions about the duties of the directors as well as the basis upon which the directors are accorded power to govern (Paine, 2023).

2.2. Reason for the development of the issue

Spak and Lynd (2021) looked at the rise of stakeholder capitalism, and one of their discussions centred on the factors driving stakeholder capitalism. The key point from their discussion was that in recent times, consumers, investors, the general public, and others have all been inspired by a movement that demands more from corporations than just profits. As per their discussions, there are several factors that are driving broader stakeholder capitalism movements, and one of them is *conscious consumerism*. Evidence shows that consumers are increasingly seeking to purchase products they consider to be more environmentally sustainable, healthy, ethically manufactured, and capable of offering varied benefits to society or social purposes. Consumers are seen as desiring to support companies whose ethical, social, and philosophical values are in line with those of the consumers (bethechange.com, 2016), and in turn, businesses have responded with a “vote with your wallet” approach by changing their practices and marketing activities in order to appeal to the intentions of the consumers as well as paying attention to the impact of their activities on society at large (Wong, 2019).

The second factor is *socially responsible investing (SRI) and ESG investing*. Spak and Lynd (2021) stated that the market is currently experiencing a conscientious approach, which is all

THE IMPORTANCE OF STAKEHOLDER CAPITALISM IN CORPORATE SUSTAINABILITY

about investments aimed at attaining not only positive financial returns but also long-term benefits for the environment, society, and its overall performance (US Securities and Exchange Commission, 2023). This has been the reason behind the exponential increase in the number of companies and fund capital systems seeking to prioritise ESG factors like increasing the number of women in their leadership, divesting from petroleum assets, and so on. This is also a factor behind stakeholder capitalism because these companies are now more conscious of the impact of their activities on society at large.

The third factor is *charity brands*, which have seen an increasing number of brands attract customers through the incorporation of different donations or philanthropy into their business models. Usually, this is achieved when the company makes an in-kind or financial donation that is directly correlated with the number of purchases of its products (Chen, 2020). Another reason is *corporate sustainability initiatives*, and it's all about the significant number of companies promoting sustainability goals in their supply chain network, including environmental and labour standards, and even doing so without binding themselves to any particular model. To demonstrate this, Spak and Lynd (2021) gave the case of Louis Dreyfus Company's sustainability initiative, which is designed to voluntarily attain certain goals that are loosely aligned with the UN Sustainability Development Goals (LDC, 2023).

Then, there are the *business and human rights initiatives*, featuring a growing number of national laws that have been founded on human rights reporting and standard requirements for businesses, many of which have been influenced by the UN Guiding Principles on business and human rights (Spak & Lynd, 2021). This is also coupled with corporate benchmarking initiatives developed in recent years where companies are ranked based on their adherence to human rights laws and initiatives, and this pushes more companies towards ensuring that their activities protect the interests of general stakeholders. Essentially, Spak and Lynd (2021) have revealed in their discussions that the issue of stakeholder capitalism has significantly reached the ceiling because the stakeholders have come to the understanding that the actions of businesses influence their own personal lives, and businesses must be made to ensure that they act in a way that yields more of a positive influence on society at large.

2.3. Discussion of the issue and key debates

Generally, the debate on stakeholder capitalism, as discussed by Spak and Lynd (2021), is centred on the understanding that a company can increase value for the shareholders by considering the interests of the larger stakeholders. This is because stakeholders play a pivotal role in the growth and performance of a company, and when they are considered to be part of the company, they demonstrate a higher sense of commitment and dedication towards the growth of the company. However, care must be taken to ensure that the overall sustainability of a company is not undermined by the need to care for the larger stakeholders.

3. Analysis

3.1. Theoretical understanding

3.1.1. Stakeholder theory

The main foundational theory for this cover story is stakeholder theory. The stakeholder theory describes the composition of a company as the collection of different individuals with different interests (Wright, 2023; The Investopedia Team, 2023). These varied interests must always be considered because they represent the will of the company. Therefore, business decisions must always be made in consideration of the different interests of these collective groups as well as the need to advance the overall operations of the company. When conflicts exist in a corporate setting, what it simply means is that these interests are eroding or colliding. At this point, it might not always be possible to bring the different groups together to reach a decision once conflict is already present. Therefore, companies must always ensure that they consider each point of view in their decision-making process and optimise it to include all voices. This is the opposite of the agency theory, which highlights differences between what the principal and the agent think is the best line of action, also known as the principal-agent problem. In the case of stakeholder theory, the best line of action is one that considers the different views and interests of the different stakeholders, aggregates them, and makes decisions that reflect these individual interests as one (Wright, 2023; The Investopedia Team, 2023).

3.2. Implication of stakeholder capitalism on businesses

A number of studies have looked at the possible influence of stakeholder capitalism on businesses. One of such studies is the work of Mhlanga (2022), which focused on stakeholder capitalism in the 4th industrial revolution as it relates to the issues that must be resolved. Findings from the study reveal that stakeholder capitalism helps create sustainable operations in businesses. This is generally based on the understanding that when all stakeholders are satisfied, they all tend to focus on creating the right ground for the business to excel. For instance, happy employees will be dedicated to the company and continue to undertake designated roles in ways that help the company attain its objectives effectively and efficiently. On the same note, when customers are satisfied with the product or service being offered by the company, they tend to repurchase. This is coupled with the fact that there is a growing movement aimed at promoting companies that are conscious of the environment, such as those that pay attention to carbon goals and other actions aimed at creating a sustainable environment for the larger society. While these benefits abound, Mhlanga (2022) also pointed out that there are a number of challenges in integrating stakeholder capitalism into a business. First comes understanding the kind of stakeholder capitalism that the company can integrate, and the overall structure and nature of a company can influence the form of stakeholder capitalism it can actually integrate. The second issue is with respect to culture because culture represents the way things are done in a particular company, and a culture that promotes stakeholder capitalism will make integration easier and vice versa.

THE IMPORTANCE OF STAKEHOLDER CAPITALISM IN CORPORATE SUSTAINABILITY

In another study, Goswami and Bhaduri (2023) pointed out that stakeholder capitalism helps the business have a better outlook on its environment and potential challenges that it might face, essentially leading to more informed decisions that are capable of yielding positive outcomes for the company as a whole. What the authors mean is that when stakeholders are made part of the decisions of a company, the company will be forced to look into areas it has forgotten and, as such, be able to highlight issues that could influence its overall performance. For instance, permitting employees to send representatives during board meetings could allow the leaders to better understand the challenges being faced by their employees, and this would amount to providing solutions that solve these challenges at ease.

Although the benefits that come with stakeholder capitalism abound, Paine (2023) stated that stakeholder capitalism could potentially be more or less what meets the eye—and easily translate more of a challenge to shareholder primacy—depending on the version of stakeholder capitalism that a company considers to adopt. For each of the types of stakeholder capitalism a company might decide to adopt, there are attached commitments and challenges, with each of them having varied practical implications in relation to the functionality of a company and its boards. Therefore, corporate leaders seeking to integrate stakeholder capitalism into their systems must first gain an understanding of these implications and how they could impact their business processes. They must also be honest in relation to what the version they intend to adopt can actually deliver to the stakeholders, what it means for the shareholders, and the impact it can have on a larger society.

4. Conclusion

In conclusion, this study has been able to review stakeholder capitalism as a concept that focuses on ensuring that all stakeholders in the company are considered in any business decision. The essence of this is based on the understanding that, when all stakeholders are considered in the company's decision-making process, they tend to develop a sense of belonging towards the company, which pushes them to contribute more towards the growth and overall positive performance of the company. The essence of stakeholder capitalism in a corporate setting boil down to the fact that it helps companies create sustainable performance. While it might be expensive for companies in the short run, the discussions above point out that it will create huge financial gains for shareholders in the long run. Therefore, it is always beneficial for companies to consider the interests of stakeholders in their decisions. However, it was also pointed out that such considerations must be made to reflect the company's capabilities and entire system because focusing on the stakeholders even when it yields negative influence on the company's financial performance would amount to efforts in futility. The main objective of every company still remains to create and maintain sustainable financial performance, and this must be done even if the stakeholders don't fully benefit. In view of the above understanding, it is recommended that companies seeking to create sustainable performance include the interests of their stakeholders in their decision-making process. This is because when all stakeholders are satisfied, the company will be able to create sustainable positive performance in the long run.

References

- Abu Haija, A. A., & Alrabba, H. M. (2017). Relationship between ownership structure and financial performance. *Corporate Ownership & Control*, 14(3-2), 393-398. <https://doi.org/10.22495/cocv14i3c2art13>
- Bethechange.com (2016). Marketing Myths: The Truth Behind Social Purpose Brand Campaigns. Retrieved from: <https://bthechange.com/marketing-myths-the-truth-behind-social-purpose-brand-campaigns-8f84dec6741d>
- Chen, C. (2020). 35 places to shop for gifts that give back. Retrieved from: <https://www.businessinsider.com/guides/gifts/companies-that-give-back?r=US&IR=T>
- D'Souza, D. (2022). What Is Stakeholder Capitalism? Investopedia. Retrieved from: <https://www.investopedia.com/stakeholder-capitalism-4774323#:~:text=Stakeholder%20capitalism%20is%20a%20system,%2C%20shareholders%2C%20and%20local%20communities.>
- Fortuna, F., Ciaburri, M., Testarmata, S., & Tiscini, R. (2020). CSR reporting and ownership structure: Evidence from Italian listed companies. *Corporate Ownership & Control*, 17(3), 146-157. <https://doi.org/10.22495/cocv17i3art11>
- Goswami, S., & Bhaduri, G. (2023). Communicating Moral Responsibility: Stakeholder Capitalism, Types, and Perceptions. *Sustainability*, 15(5), 4386. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15054386>
- JUST Capital (2019). A Roadmap for Stakeholder Capitalism: 2019 Survey Results. Retrieved from: <https://justcapital.com/reports/roadmap-for-stakeholder-capitalism/>
- LDC (2023). Our Approach. Retrieved from: <https://www ldc.com/sustainability/our-approach/>
- Littenberg, M. R., Oldshue, E. J., & Pifer, B. N. (2020, August 31). Delaware public benefit corporations – Recent developments (Harvard Law School Forum on Corporate Governance). Retrieved from <https://corpgov.law.harvard.edu/2020/08/31/delaware-public-benefit-corporations-recent-developments/>
- Mhlanga, D. (2023). Stakeholder Capitalism, the Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR), and Sustainable Development: Issues to Be Resolved. *Sustainability*, 14(7):3902. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14073902>
- Paine, L. S. (2023). What Does “Stakeholder Capitalism” Mean to You? Retrieved from: <https://hbr.org/2023/09/what-does-stakeholder-capitalism-mean-to-you>
- Spak, W., & Lynd, J. (2021). The Rise of Stakeholder Capitalism. Retrieved from: <https://www.whitecase.com/insight-our-thinking/rise-stakeholder-capitalism>

THE IMPORTANCE OF STAKEHOLDER CAPITALISM IN CORPORATE SUSTAINABILITY

Strine, L., & Zwillinger, J. (2020, September 10). What Milton Friedman missed about social inequality. The New York Times. Retrieved from <https://www.nytimes.com/2020/09/10/business/dealbook/milton-friedmaninequality.html>

The Investopedia Team (2023). Agency Theory vs. Stakeholder Theory: What's the Difference? Retrieved from: <https://www.investopedia.com/ask/answers/031615/whats-difference-between-agency-theory-and-stakeholder-theory.asp>

US Securities and Exchange Commission (2023). Environmental, Social and Governance (ESG) Investing. Retrieved from: <https://www.investor.gov/introduction-investing/investing-basics/glossary/environmental-social-and-governance-esg-investing>

Wong, K. (2019). How to Be a More Conscious Consumer, Even If You're on a Budget. New York Times. Retrieved from: <https://www.nytimes.com/2019/10/01/smarter-living/sustainable-shopping-conscious-consumer.html>

Wright, T. (2023). What Is Stakeholder Theory? Benefits, Challenges & Application. Retrieved from: <https://www.cascade.app/blog/stakeholder-theory>

The Five Stages of Diversity, Equity and Inclusion (DEI) Maturity

Grace Ifeoma Anukwe¹, Jude Eze¹, Kenechi John Onyike¹, Chiemelie Benneth Iloka^{1*}

¹ *Department of Marketing,*

Faculty of Management Sciences,

Enugu State University of Science and Technology (ESUT), Agbani,

Enugu State, Nigeria.

Iloka.benneth@esut.edu.ng

Abstract

Research Purpose: Amidst a global push for social justice and equality, businesses are increasingly recognizing the importance of cultivating diverse and inclusive workplaces. This study examines the five stages of DE&I maturity, providing a roadmap for companies seeking to create equitable environments where all employees can thrive.

Methodology: This research analyses existing frameworks and literature pertaining to the five stages of DE&I implementation within organisations.

Findings: The study clarifies how each stage contributes to building a more just and equitable workplace, ultimately benefiting both employees and the organisation as a whole. It also highlights how corporate DE&I initiatives align with the UN's Sustainable Development Goals.

Conclusion: By understanding and actively progressing through the five stages of DE&I maturity, companies can create truly inclusive workplaces that contribute to a more equitable and sustainable future.

Key words: *Company, Diversity, Equity, Inclusiveness, Performance, United Nations.*

1. Introduction

The article, **The Five Stages of DEI Maturity**, outlines the Five Stages of Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion (DEI) Maturity, providing insights on how organisations can progress from awareness to sustainability. The first stage is awareness, and it focuses on the need for companies to be aware of their present situation and where they desire to be in the future (based on specifically defined targets). Every action undertaken by a company, including DEI, is a product of triggers like social incidents or lawsuits. However, when these triggers occur, companies seem to make more of a high-minded statement without any actual practicality, which is why they need more internal honesty in order to successfully execute

defined objectives. Finally, being aware requires that the leaders define why DEI is personally important to them and set a collective internal vision (Washington, 2022). The second phase is complaint, and it is the stage at which companies must be ready and willing to meet the diverse requirements made by the government and industry about their approach to DEI. However, existing findings suggest that companies usually focus on compliance without having any genuine intention to change their culture towards the DEI objectives. To be successful in this stage, it is recommended that leaders set goals beyond compliance, such as linking their DEI objectives to broader corporate goals, and clearly show how the company's mission is supported by DEI (Washington, 2022). The third stage is tactical. Companies that have reached this stage are known to initiate bottom-up DEI initiatives, such as grassroots efforts. However, it is also common for companies in this stage to lack a comprehensive strategic approach to DEI. Therefore, to overcome the issues at this stage, leaders must be willing to define an overreaching DEI strategy, establish a feedback loop between leadership and grassroots efforts, and create standardised practices. The fourth stage is integrated. Companies in this stage are known to have aligned DEI in their internal and external environments. They feature companies that have clearly defined DEI strategies, developed an inclusive culture, and addressed issues related to discrimination, paving the way for all employees to access equal opportunities in their working systems. At this stage, the leader must be able to establish systems and structures that will allow for long-term integration of DEI and also ensure that the company can continually access effectiveness. The final stage is sustainable. This is the stage when DEI approaches have been clearly embedded in the corporate DNA of such a company. Such companies are known to be capable of withstanding the challenges that come with changes in leadership or economic downturns. This is because even with a change in leadership, the company will continue with its DEI approaches as they have become integrated into their daily operational processes. Finally, companies at this stage require continuous improvements in order to sustain these approaches, and leaders are recommended to challenge the status quo in order to ensure that the DEI efforts live longer than the individual leader.

The article highlights case studies, including Iora Health, Denny's, Slack, and Uncle Nearest, to illustrate organisations' journeys through these stages. It emphasises that DEI is an ongoing commitment, requiring vigilance and adaptation as organisations evolve and face new challenges. A similar view is also held in extant literature (Pollock et al., 2022), and the central focus of these discussions is that companies seeking to integrate DEI approaches must first understand where they are and clearly define where they aim to be in the future.

This study is designed to review the cover story. In order to attain this objective, the study is divided into three sections. The first section is the introduction, and it presents a summary of the cover story as well as steps taken to assess it. The second section is the research and synthesis, focusing on the discussion of related themes developed from the cover story. The third section is the theoretical understanding, and it focuses on the theories surrounding the themes.

2. Research and synthesis

2.1. Themes related to the cover story

A number of themes were identified in the cover story, **The Five Stages of DEI Maturity**, and they are further discussed below.

- **Aware**

As opined by Washington (2022), the first stage in reaching maturity in diversity, equity, and inclusion is being *aware*. The scholar went further by stating that for many organisations, the process of being intentional about their desire to integrate DEI actually starts with a trigger—for instance, a legal action against the company by a victimised party, being called out by the investors, or a traumatic experience like the murder of George Floyd in the USA. Such a great deal of awareness can push the company into sincerely searching for and desiring to change its cause. Usually, companies entering the awareness stage fall within the group of those successful older corporations that have actually prioritised DE, or the start-ups that are so conscious and focused on their sustainability that they actually neglected the need to establish a strong human-capital practice (Washington, 2022). Following a wake-up call, both companies usually make high-minded public statements in relation to their attitudes and actual intention to move towards DEI. However, what is truly needed at this point is genuine sincerity and honesty about their true intentions, especially within their corporate leadership team. Thus, Washington (2022) went further to state that at this stage, leaders should ask themselves the following questions: a) what does DEI matter to us personally, and b) where do we actually want to go from here? However, it is integral to point out that any company making big DEI moves before it is ready will most likely fail to meet the defined objectives, and this will lead to community members and minority employees being continually marginalized. Thus, when setting goals, it is imperative that corporations take extra care to ensure that they do not benchmark themselves against companies that have reached another phase of DEI maturity. To demonstrate this, Washington (2022) gave the instance of an ice cream maker, Ben and Jerry's, founded by longtime social-injustice activists Ben Cohen and Jerry Greenfield, where the company boldly stated on their corporate website and social media handles in 2020 that "they must dismantle white supremacy." While this is laudable, when a company has not built the culture and structure to act in such a way—like Ben and Jerry's had through years of experience—such a statement would appear more performative. Instead, when making sweeping statements in the awareness stage, it is recommended that companies choose a narrower, more tactical goal. A number of scholars and corporate managers have also revealed that awareness is the start of the journey towards DEI maturity. Unguresan (2023) opined that the first step is to demonstrate commitment through awareness. The company becomes aware of the need to implement DEI maturity strategies and eulogises commitment in that direction. Ferry (2021) also developed a DEI maturity model in which awareness was considered integral and the first step towards. Essentially, this is all based on the understanding that it is through awareness that one will be certain of the issues facing the company and make necessary corrective measures to address the said issue.

- **Complaint**

The second stage is compliance, and the author pointed out that in attaining DEIA maturity, companies must meet the numerous government and industry requirements for diversity, like the EEOC laws established in the US (Washington, 2022). Similarly, when corporations have been subjected to DEI lawsuits, they might have agreed to abide by some terms of settlement. On their own, companies might also decide to voluntarily comply and compare their DEI goals with those of competing brands. At this stage, the thinking is usually, "We do DEI because we have the need to do so." It is also pivotal to point out that a company could also comply without ever having to go through the stage of awareness; however, such a company could be ill-equipped to proceed further without undertaking the foundational work done at the aware stage. Khan and Khan (2023) pointed out that DEI maturity requires the company to comply with certain regulations set by the government or the industry where it maintains operations. These regulations are usually designed to assist the company with understanding steps to take at each stage and how to go about taking the said step. Essentially, this step is also integral, as it serves as a guide for the company on what it needs to do, how, and when it should be done.

- **Tactical**

Washington (2022) stated that when companies reach the tactical stage, they have moved beyond meeting the rules that were imposed on them and have now become fully engaged in executing their own DEI initiatives, which is usually bottom-up. It is also possible that these companies might have successful foundation efforts like employee resource groups (ERGs) and teams capable of instituting their own DEI processes—maybe a community guideline designed for handling issues related to micro-aggression or devils advocates appointing in meetings to ensure that diverse opinions are heard. Going further, Washington (2022) also pointed out that there is the possibility of top-down programming or strategy in the said company, like the celebration of Pride month, although it is mainly executed by individual managers independently. At this stage, companies are on their way to adjusting or entirely changing their culture, leading to employees at all levels possibly engaging in tough conversations about possible biases and providing feedback for one another. Additionally, the groups in the company may adopt extra measures to enhance their overall diversity or views in the course of reaching the decision to change. That notwithstanding, it was also pointed out by Washington (2022) that companies at this stage usually still do not have a strategic DEI approach that could drive their entire business. Since their efforts are not properly coordinated, the implication is that one area of the organisation might be championing the DEI efforts while these efforts are being ignored in other areas. In order to better align their corporations at this stage, leaders are expected to ask questions like: what is our strategy, in which areas do we need standardisation, how can we connect the DEI work up and down the company, and what is our full area of influence? Answering these questions will help the company better develop the right tactics to implement the DEI efforts as seamlessly as possible. DeMattia (2023) also highlighted the importance of tactics in maturing at DEI by

stating that tactics are what get the job done. It is through tactics that the company will be able to know what it is exactly doing, how it is doing it, and when changes might be required in order to attain the set objectives of DEI implementation in its system. Therefore, having the right tactics is necessary for overall success.

- **Integrated**

As opined by Washington (2022), once a company has been able to align its internal and external efforts and connect its top-down and bottom-up efforts, it is said to have reached the integrated stage. Companies that are in the integrated stage have defined their overall DEI strategy, and they are also known to have developed an inclusion culture as well as taken a considerable look at the influence of inequality and discrimination on their internal and external stakeholders, thus seeking necessary measures and approaches to address such challenges. Companies at this stage can truly say that DEI is part of all they do. However, Washington (2022) still pointed out that, irrespective of this achievement, companies at this stage are also known to be humble about the whole concept and implementation. For many of such companies that are at this stage, it is through experimentation that they have been able to reach this level, being able to know what works and what doesn't work. Leaders of companies with celebrated and long-standing DEI programmes are expected to be modest enough to change the course in the event that whatever they are doing is not working. In line with the study conducted by KPMG (2022), integration is a key stage, as it is the level at which companies are able to discover new ways of working aimed at creating competitive advantage. Through compliance and regulatory scrutiny, such companies have been able to differentiate themselves as being conscious of DEI, adopting measures that inculcate a spirit of diversity, equity, and inclusion throughout their systems, and in the process earning the respect of stakeholders both within and outside the company. There is a sense of connectedness among the employees due to the alignment of DEI in the company's entire processes, improving workforce loyalty and commitment as well.

- **Sustainable**

Finally, the last stage of DEI maturity is sustainability. Washington (2022) stated that companies whose DEI efforts are deeply rooted in their corporate culture are said to have entered the sustainability stage. At this stage, their DEI efforts have been able to pass the stress stages like changes in leadership and economic challenges, and the company's leaders have developed a mindset of continuous improvement. To solidify his argument further, Washington (2022) gave the case of Intel, a technology giant, when the company's then CEO Brian Krzanich announced in 2015 that the company has a \$300 million plan designed to bring the company's workforce to "full representation" within five years by 2020, and this plan included the initiation of programmes such as a \$4,000 bonus for those who have successfully referred candidates from marginalized groups and another \$5 million partnership aimed at developing a high school computer-science curriculum for the Oakland Unified School District. Within just six months of unveiling this plan, the company hired a number of

minority and female employees, surpassing its initial 40% target for the year. In the course of Krzanich's tenure as CEO, the company's hires from underrepresented communities actually increased by 31%, with the female workforce at Intel also increasing by nearly 43%. However, in 2018, Krzanich resigned due to a violation of the non-fraternisation policy with another colleague. Normally, such a dramatic change in leadership could have also changed the policy towards DEI, but the next leader sustained the company's policy and continued to move in the path of Krzanich's leadership. This demonstrates that the company has reached a level of sustainability. Per Ferry (2021), reaching the sustainable level in DEI implementation implies that the company has integrated DEI policies as part of its culture, and the foundation of these policies has been rooted in their organisational process—one that is less likely to be changed with any change in leadership, as demonstrated in the case of Intel.

2.2. Reasons for the development of the issue

Whatever happens in a business setting happens within its context or background. This is the same case for the widespread expansion of DEI, as it never occurred at once. It was born out of a gradual process, and it has now become integral in all countries, industries, and businesses seeking to create an agile and sustainable atmosphere. The movement for social equity has become so pronounced that its voice can no longer remain unheard. The main reason for the development of DEI is the extreme level of social injustice that exists in the US and some other advanced economies (McKinsey and Company, 2022; Ashutosh, 2023). These social injustices have been analysed globally, with the analysis streaming to the entire professional world. As such, employees began to deliberate on the discrimination they encounter in their workplace, with executives continuously struggling to improve the overall employment practices and culture of their company. This gave rise to the rapid expansion of corporate diversity, equity, and inclusion (DEI) programmes (McKinsey and Company, 2022; Ashutosh, 2023). Although it was previously viewed as a sub-component within the human resources department, DEI has now metamorphosed into a core business function, with both small and larger corporations aggressively investing in it. Notwithstanding the effects of COVID-19 on the US economy, evidence shows that between May and September of 2020, there was an increase of 123% in the number of DEI-related jobs (McKinsey and Company, 2022; Ashutosh, 2023). However, one also needs to be conscious of the fact that this explosive growth raises concerns, namely within the context of the sustainability of industries and businesses.

2.3. Discussions of the issue and key debates

Washington (2022) recounted interactions with countless CEOs and Chief Human Resource Officers since the murder of George Floyd in 2020 in relation to how they addressed the racial violence they witnessed during that summer. The researcher was able to discover that there is an existing pattern: first, the leaders seem to express their deep concern about the issues, and they inquired whether their company is instituting the right tools to ensure diversity, equity, and inclusiveness (DEI) in their workplace. These leaders were eager to know the actions undertaken by other companies (especially their competitors) and how their

own actions could be compared to those of other companies. It was also discovered that many of the companies were taking actions because it was something they saw competitors doing; for instance, there were cases where companies declared themselves champions of people of colour or set a top-down DEI strategy across their entry system, but these enthusiasms usually fizzled out, leaving the leaders voicing their opinion about DEI being too hard for them and taking so much time for the results to appear. Generally speaking, DEI is never a short-term programme, and companies need to compare their environments to understand what works for them and not adopt measures based on what other companies have been found to be doing.

3. Analysis

3.1. Theoretical understanding

3.1.1. Diversity, Equity and Inclusion (DEI) approach

Generally speaking, diversity, equity, and inclusion (DEI) is an initiative that aims to promote a culture developed within a given context where each person is valued and accorded an equal opportunity to succeed. Diversity can be conceptualised as the variability in the characteristics of individuals within a given work unit (Roberson et al., 2017). Such differences are known to occur in three major forms: separation, disparity, and variety (Harrison & Klein, 2007). These forms of diversity reflect differences in a) values, attitudes, and beliefs; b) functional background, knowledge, and experience in the industry; and c) pay, status, and authority to make decisions. It is at this level that researchers see an overlap in the literature on diversity and culture because it addresses the composition of diversity in relation to cultural values (for instance, management mode, cultural diversity, etc.). (Seymen, 2006). On the other hand, equity can be conceptualised as acknowledging that there are numerous ways some people might face barriers (both visible and invisible) in attaining their success and the need for these barriers to be dismantled in order to create a fair playing field for everybody (Hagman, 2021: p. 77). The last concept is inclusion, and it deals with the extent to which individuals feel that the environment they find themselves in provides them with a sense of belonging that creates the right room for them to be authentic (Jansen et al., 2014). While these terms are different, they are actually related. For instance, when an organisation adopts equitable practices, like unbiased hiring and equal opportunities for promotion, they will create the right room for diversity to be optimised.

In a broad sense, the focus of DEI is on ensuring that minoritized employees receive fair treatment in the workplace. The history of DEI can be traced back to the 1960s, the time when educational systems pushed for affirmative actions related to multicultural initiatives (Weissmann et al., 2019).

3.2. Steps to create DEI

A number of studies have looked at the steps that can be followed to create DEI. In one of such studies, it was highlighted that the steps to follow to attain a DEI approach can be broken into introspection, education, and action (Pollock et al., 2022). In another study,

Washington (2022) pointed out that attaining DEI maturity would require the company to be aware, compliant, tactical, integrated, and sustainable. Irrespective of the steps being considered, the fact remains that attaining DEI will require the company to understand its present situation, define its projected outcomes or objectives, and take necessary actions towards making that a reality. It is through a clear understanding of their current positions that the company will be able to set clear targets for the future.

3.3. Impact on businesses

The majority of the discussions on the impact of DEI on organisational performance have focused on the fact that it has a positive influence on productivity. The benefit of DEI is most pronounced in organisations seeking to help their employees navigate diverse settings (for instance, ideologically, culturally, racially, linguistically, sexually, and others) because it comes with a transformation platform that enables the corporate system to think beyond skills, knowledge, and abilities and, in the process, promote focus on action, climate, and organisational context. By so doing, the inherent diversity that comes with such an approach makes cross-cultural management research a logical subfield, and it is helpful for companies seeking to fulfil the overall goal of sustainability as it increases their perceptions positively both among their internal and external stakeholders.

Specifically, when companies adopt the DEI approach, it will provide them with divergent views and backgrounds, making it possible for their employees to brainstorm new, creative ways to solve difficult issues (Prieto et al., n. d.). On a positive note, implementing DEI will exemplify the essence of providing sufficient reward for employees' contributions towards the company's overall objectives, and the employees that make significant contributions will be tremendously valued based on their performance in the corporate process (Inuwa, 2017). Another benefit that comes with DEI is that it promotes the need for cross-cultural competence, paving the way for the development of skills that will naturally enhance cross-cultural performance in the company. For the sake of clarity, cross-cultural competence can be conceptualised as being able to efficiently and independently navigate cross-cultural environments (Abbe et al., 2007). If a company is able to develop these skills, it will be able to facilitate an environment where the employees, notwithstanding differences in cultural perspectives, will have a sense of belonging, value, respect, and inclusion (Johnson et al., 2006). This will ultimately yield a positive influence on the performance of the company because it will positively influence employees' commitment and dedication.

4. Conclusion

This cover story has been able to reflect on the development of DEI and how it has transformed into an important tool for creating a sustainable competitive edge in modern businesses. For the start, the DEI approach was considered a sub-component in the HR department. However, recent social injustices and deliberations in the corporate world have forced it to become part of major corporate decisions in modern industries. Companies are particularly focused on integrating DEI approaches because of the influence it has on their

overall performance as it builds on employees' commitment and dedication. The cover story also highlighted that there are a number of steps—aware, compliant, tactical, integrated, and sustainable—that companies seeking to integrate DEI approaches into their systems must comply with. In conclusion, it is expected that when companies fully integrate DEI approaches and get to a sustainable level, DEI becomes part of their DNA and continues to exist even after a change in leadership or in the face of an economic downturn. The implication is that such a company will be able to create the right atmosphere for a committed and dedicated workforce, as the employees will develop a higher sense of belonging in the company.

References

- Abbe A, Gulick LM, and Herman JL (2007) *Cross-cultural Competence in Army Leaders: A Conceptual and Empirical Foundation*. Arlington, VA: US Army Research Institute for the Behavioral and Social Sciences.
- Ashutosh, K. (2023). The History and Growth of Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion (DEI): How far do we away to achieve the goal. Retrieved from: <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/history-growth-diversity-equity-inclusion-dei-how-far-ashutosh-kumar>
- DeMattia, A. (2023). A Mature Approach to Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion Delivers Real Results. Retrieved from: https://media.bitpipe.com/io_16x/io_168145/item_2693001/ESG-Research-Insights-Paper-AWS-DEI-Mar-2023--.pdf
- Ferry, K. (2021). The Korn Ferry Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion Maturity Model: A new understanding. Korn Ferry tools. Retrieved from: <https://www.bdamerica.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/DEI-Maturity-Model.pdf>
- Hagman JE (2021) The eighth characteristic for successful calculus programs: diversity, equity, & inclusion practices. *Primus* 31(1): 70–90.
- Harrison DA and Klein KJ (2007) What's the difference? Diversity constructs as separation, variety, or disparity in organisations. *Academy of Management Review* 32(4): 1199–1228.
- Inuwa M (2017) Relationship between job equity and performance of employee: a literature review. *International Journal of Business and Management Future* 1(1): 8–15.
- Jansen WS, Otten S, van der Zee KI, et al. (2014) Inclusion: conceptualization and measurement. *European Journal of Social Psychology* 44(4): 370–385.
- Johnson JP, Lenartowicz T, and Apud S (2006) Cross-cultural competence in international business: toward a definition and a model. *Journal of International Business Studies* 37(4): 525–543.

THE FIVE STAGES OF DIVERSITY, EQUITY AND INCLUSION (DEI) MATURITY

- Khan, A. A., & Khan, N. A. (2023). Exploring Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion (Dei) in the Context of Human Resource Management. *Anvesak*, 53(2).
- KPMG (2022). Diversity, Equity And Inclusion. Retrived from: <https://assets.kpmg.com/content/dam/kpmg/ie/pdf/2022/04/ie-inclusion-diveristy-equity-ym.pdf>
- McKinsey and Company (2022). What is diversity, equity, and inclusion? Retrieved from: <https://www.mckinsey.com/featured-insights/mckinsey-explainers/what-is-diversity-equity-and-inclusion>
- Pollock M, Holly J, and Leggett-Robinson P (2022) Inclusive leadership development for engineers. *New Directions for Student Leadership* 2022(173): 119–128.
- Roberson Q, Ryan AM, and Ragins BR (2017) The evolution and future of diversity at work. *Journal of Applied Psychology* 102(3): 483.
- Seymen OA (2006) The cultural diversity phenomenon in organisations and different approaches for effective cultural diversity management: a literary review. *Cross Cultural Management: An International Journal*.
- Unguresan, A. (2023). What Are the Stages of a DE&I Maturity Model? Retrieved from: <https://www.edgeempower.com/wp-content/uploads/2023/04/What-Are-the-Stages-of-a-DEI-Maturity-Model.pdf>
- Washington, E. F. (2022). The Five Stages of DEI Maturity. Retrieved from: <https://hbr.org/2022/11/the-five-stages-of-dei-maturity>
- Weissmann GS, Ibarra RA, Howland-Davis M, et al. (2019) The multicontext path to redefining how we access and think about diversity, equity, and inclusion in STEM. *Journal of Geoscience Education* 67(4): 320–329.

Revitalising Corporate Culture in the World of Hybrid Work

Jude Eze¹, Kenechi John Onyeke¹, Grace Ifeoma Anukwe¹, Chiemelie Benneth Iloka¹

¹ *Department of Marketing,*

Faculty of Management Sciences,

Enugu State University of Science and Technology (ESUT), Agbani,

Enugu State, Nigeria.

Iloka.benneth@esut.edu.ng

Abstract

Research Purpose: With the rise of hybrid and remote work models, maintaining a strong company culture is more crucial than ever. How can organisations ensure their values and standards remain vibrant and impactful when physical presence is no longer a constant? This research explores strategies for building and sustaining a robust corporate culture in the evolving landscape of hybrid work.

Methodology: This research examines the challenges posed by hybrid and remote work to traditional models of corporate culture. It analyses the impact of reduced physical interaction on employee alignment and connectedness, drawing upon relevant studies and real-world examples.

Findings: The study reveals that hybrid and remote work settings can negatively impact employee alignment and connectedness due to the lack of physical interaction inherent in conventional work environments.

Conclusion: Building a strong and sustainable corporate culture within hybrid and remote work models requires innovative approaches that foster a sense of community and shared purpose, even in the absence of consistent physical presence.

Recommendations: The research suggests strategies for companies to adapt their cultural initiatives to the hybrid world, including leveraging technology for enhanced communication and collaboration, promoting virtual team-building activities, and establishing clear guidelines for remote work engagement.

Key words: *Alignment, Connectedness, Corporate Culture, Covid-19, Employee, Hybrid Work, Remote Work.*

1. Introduction

The article, **Revitalising Culture in the World of Hybrid Work**, discusses the challenges organisations face in maintaining a strong culture in the era of remote and hybrid work. Although there was no particular challenge in focus, existing empirical findings indicate that the major challenges with building a strong corporate culture in a remote setting are poor

communication and a lack of connectedness. This is centred on the understanding that in a remote or hybrid setting, workers do not have the opportunity to enjoy the interactions obtainable in a physical setting, and since they also work at their own pace and philosophy, they seem to be less interested in the cultures of the company and more focused on attaining set objectives using any means possible. What this does is that it could push the workers to see social support outside the company, and this can reduce their overall level of commitment and dedication to the company. Despite concerns that such work models may undermine culture, forcing employees back to the office is not a guaranteed solution. A study by Gartner revealed that only 25% of remote or hybrid knowledge workers feel connected to their company's culture (Liu, 2022). Therefore, the only option becomes that corporations must find ways to keep employees within their system, including building a supportive network that encourages interaction, communication, and connectedness for workers in hybrid and remote settings.

The research emphasises the importance of two components in evaluating culture: alignment (employees understanding and believing in the culture) and connectedness (identifying with and caring about the culture). In-office mandates were found to decrease connectedness. Workers with "radical flexibility" reported higher connectedness (53%), compared to those with low flexibility (18%). Studies have shown that the essence of connectedness is far-reaching because it creates a sense of belonging for workers in remote and hybrid settings (Ozimek, 2020, 2021; van Zoonen et al., 2021). It is also through this connectedness that workers exchange ideas and support their respective teams, ensuring that overall objectives are easily attainable. Therefore, improving connectedness in a remote and hybrid setting is a necessity that companies adopting such a work model must consider in order to create a supportive and sustainable working environment.

The cover story suggests three strategies to enhance connectedness among hybrid workers. First, it suggests that the culture should be transferred through work itself. This can be done by the company auditing its processes to ensure that they are compatible with its culture. Once done, the culture should be instilled through daily tasks, with emphasis placed on the values that the employees will drive from the role they undertake and not the physical location where they are undertaking the said roles. Secondly, the teams should be empowered to set their own work rhythms, as this will enable them to envision how the culture can help them attain their set goals and become more aligned with the culture. The second strategy is for the company to connect with the teams through their emotional proximity. This can be done by distinguishing the emotional and physical proximities of its workforce and ensuring that the emotional proximity is given more critical attention. Furthermore, toxic workers should be identified and removed, and the management must avoid inviting members that have no real value to contribute to any meetings. Finally, companies are encouraged to foster microculture. This will require them to shift from optimising corporate culture to focusing on fostering microculture. Additionally, they will need to favour more devolved control that will allow the local teams to gain more autonomy and direct action on issues that affect their

performance. Such companies must also come to the understanding that team-level experiences increase connectedness more than initiatives that cut across the entire enterprise.

Essentially, corporations need to understand and intentionally adapt to the new realities of hybrid and remote work by focusing on their true intentions instead of the osmosis that is obtainable across the industry, as such a focus will allow corporate leaders to yield positive influence on the performance and retention of employees. Each company is unique, and this is why the focus is essential because direct analysis of the situations in a company will allow the company to better define its own direction in relation to the objectives it aims to attain through hybrid and remote work settings.

2. Research and Synthesis

2.1. Themes related to the cover story

The following themes have been identified in the cover story of *Revitalizing Culture in the World of Hybrid Work*, and they are further discussed below.

- *Organizations face numerous challenges in maintaining strong culture in era or remote and hybrid work*

While the cover story was not particularly about any challenges that companies face in maintaining a strong corporate culture in the era of hybrid or remote work, existing research has discussed a number of these challenges. The first is the absence of information and communication. In a remote work setting, informal communication is usually absent because employees do not have the opportunity to interact like they would in hallways, break rooms, shared offices, and co-located office environments obtainable in a physical work setting. As a result of this absence of face-to-face interaction, it has been stated in studies that the ability of remote work employees to recognise underlying assumptions and finer details in communication is actually hindered (Ahuja & Galvin, 2003), and this has a resulting negative effect on their ability to connect with their colleagues and sustain the overall corporate norm housing the company's objectives. In accordance with Holmes and Marra (2004), informal communication is a kind of "social glue" that binds employees in the workplace together and helps them create and sustain great relationships both inside and outside the workplace (Tracy, 2002), and it also helps the employees to truly feel connected with each other (Waldron, 2003). To demonstrate the essence of this informal communication, an interview was conducted with nine employees from different companies working in a remote work setting. Six of the interviewees pointed out that they had a considerably low level of information interaction and contact with their colleagues, and this decreased their overall feeling of connectedness (Eriksson & Santesson, 2021).

Similar evidence was revealed in another study where it was shown that social isolation has a negative impact on employees' ability to adjust to remote work settings, and this contributes to the number of studies highlighting the lack of social connectedness among employees in remote work settings (van Zoonen et al., 2021). The second issue relates to handling the

social connectedness that comes with remote or hybrid work. Evidence from the qualitative study does suggest that remote workers missed the “spontaneous socialisation” that can be enjoyed in a co-located working environment (Tietze & Nadin, 2011). This limited face-to-face interaction, coupled with an increase in physical distance between employees and their supervisors, has also been found to force some employees to feel as if “out of sight might really be out of mind” (Sewell & Taskin, 2015, p. 1518). This challenge was pronounced in a recent study, where it was found that the negative relationship between adjustment and trust in the remote work setting can easily be mitigated through the adoption of different communication technologies, but the quality of communication received had no mitigating effect on employees' feelings of isolation (van Zoonen et al., 2021).

Supervisors can also notice this lack of connectedness and communication. In another study that involved 1,500 hiring managers in the U.S., it was found that 30.5% of those who participated in the study noticed a reduction in the cohesion of their teams due to the implementation of remote work settings during the pandemic period (Ozimek, 2020, 2021). What is revealed in these studies is that with an increase in arrangements for remote work, individuals experience a higher risk of social isolation (Rai, 2020), and this begets poor work relationships, a reduced overall sense of belonging, and a decline in commitment to the organisation (Larson et al., 2020). Essentially, these challenges create issues for companies seeking to create a strong corporate culture in remote work settings because the absence of information communication and connectedness would amount to varied challenges in promoting, adopting, and integrating the corporate culture throughout remote work settings.

- ***Corporate culture is evaluated via alignment and connectedness***

In the cover story, it was pointed out that culture can be evaluated on the basis of two components: alignment (which is all about employees having a vivid understanding of the corporate culture and believing that such can potentially bring about the right outcomes for the company) and connectedness (a situation whereby the employees identify with and care about the corporate culture) (Liu, 2022). Masionis (2022) presented a detailed discussion of how alignment and connectedness can be used to evaluate the overall integration of organisational culture in a corporate system, primarily focusing on how a company can align its culture and ensure that staff are connected to it. In the discussion, the author pointed out that when the people and activities in an organisation are in sync, projects tend to move smoothly, team members can easily be seen collaborating in order to deliver client needs, and there seems to be a constant flow of innovative and creative ideas for improving businesses.

For Masionis (2022), cultural alignment entails the process of syncing the culture, values, and goals of a company with its people, while connectedness is the extent to which the people allow the syncing to become a reality. In alignment, the company gives the people reasons to be part of the system, while in connectedness, the people provide the assurance of being part of the system. The essence of building a strongly aligned and connected corporate culture is based on the understanding that disconnection between the corporate culture and employees

can undermine the strong foundation the company laid in building such a solid corporate system. Essentially, the two components of alignment and connectedness can be used to evaluate the overall integration of corporate culture in any given system.

- **Connectedness in the remote work setting can be enhanced by: a) shifting work through culture itself, b) connecting through emotional proximity, and c) fostering microculture**

Finally, the cover story looked at how connectedness in a remote work setting can be attained. Liu (2022) suggested in the cover story that the first strategy for driving connectedness among hybrid and remote work is to shift from diffusing culture through the office into diffusing it through the work itself. To do so, the management needs to start by auditing the processes in the company in order to make sure that they are in line with the culture as intended. Through this means, the employees will feel connected while doing their designated work. The second strategy is to connect through emotional proximity, not physical proximity. This is based on the understanding that since remote and hybrid workers experience fewer workplace interactions, each exchange is actually impactful. Thus, there is a need to identify and remove toxic workers, especially those who hold positions of influence. It also requires that the company refrain from requiring people to attend meetings unless their presence is truly needed and they will make impactful contributions to the work. The third and final strategy is to shift from optimising corporate culture to fostering microculture. This view is based on the understanding that the pandemic has created a radical change in how employees experience corporate culture, and companies must brace themselves in line with this new reality. Thus, by focusing less on osmosis and more on intentionality, when it comes to driving connectedness, leaders will be able to see significant influence on the intention of employees to stay and their overall performance.

Outlined in Maslow's Theory of Human Motivation (1943) is the hierarchy of basic needs that people attempt to satisfy in their daily lives. In the order of priority is psychological needs, followed by safety, love, and belonging, with esteem and self-actualization in the ending part of priority (Maslow, 1943). Essentially, there is an innate desire in people to connect with their fellow beings, and when there is no communication among remote workers, the implication is that they could easily become socially isolated and seek social support outside their company. This emotional support can be accessed via their family and friends or through technologies that have been created to allow people to connect with distant peers, and they can also adopt social media as a tool for gaining a sense of belonging. Therefore, it is integral that companies create this sense of connectedness with their enterprise and among their workforce (in remote and hybrid settings) in order to ensure that they don't go outside the company to see for social support, as such could negatively impact their overall commitment and dedication to the company.

2.2. Reasons for the development of the issue

Although remote and hybrid work has been in existence for decades, its full adoption came into effect during the COVID-19 era. As Liu (2022) pointed out, two years have passed since the pandemic era, and numerous corporate leaders are worried about how hybrid and remote work are undermining their corporate culture. Their concern is not far-fetched, as a 2022 global study by the research and advisory firm Gartner revealed that about 25% of the remote or hybrid workers (in the knowledge sector) express a sense of connection towards the culture of their company. However, CEOs including Elon Musk and Jamie Dimon have been able to discover firsthand that forcing employees back into the office could pose potential risks, and companies must now take other tactics in handling such corporate issues.

2.3. Discussion of the issues and key debates

When it comes to organisational culture, diffusion is all about ensuring that the employees observe, evaluate, implement, and adopt the values, norms, and practices of other members within the same company. These beliefs and behaviours would then bring about a stronger corporate culture. What is implied by a strong corporate culture are values and beliefs that are widely shared by the employees and strongly adhered to. Essentially, the employees are aligned and connected to the corporate culture. For companies that have a weak corporate culture, what it indicates is that the employees rely more on their personal norms, principles, and values instead of adhering to those of the corporation (Thokozani & Maseko, 2017). When a company has a strong organisational culture, it is able to create group harmony, which makes it easier for the employees to complete designated tasks by adhering to common practices and norms. A weak corporate culture creates numerous issues for the company due to a lack of shared values or goals and makes it difficult for the company to succeed due to differences in values and approaches. Therefore, creating a strong corporate culture is critical, and this is the main objective of this cover story as it relates to remote and hybrid work.

3. Analysis

3.1. Theoretical understanding

3.1.1. Organizational culture: Competing values framework

Typically, organisational culture is conceptualised as "artifacts, assumptions, and values" that are born out of communicative interactions with the members of a company (Keyton, 2011). In defining culture, Schein (1985) included the concept of norms to view culture as a clear indication of how corporate members interact and socialise in order to reinforce and sustain the culture of a company. This aspect of culture can be observed and assessed in all groups of companies, notwithstanding its size, as it covers the entire organisation and its members across different departments (Schein, 1990).

This section specifically relates to applying the relevant academic theories to your chosen area and critically analysing the key issues through these frameworks. Although a review of the existing literature shows that there are different classifications of organisational culture,

the emphasis in this analysis is on Cameron and Quinn's (2011) Competing Values Framework.

In line with the Competing Values Framework, corporate culture can be defined on two dimensions: having an internal or external focus and valuing stability or flexibility in terms of change. Although these dimensions appear in the form of a continuum, the fact is that companies are likely to find themselves aligning in one way or another, therefore creating four distinctive cultures: clan, hierarchy, adhocracy, and market. When a company has a clan culture, the implication is that it has an internal focus and values flexibility in times of change, and such companies are typically viewed as family because of the friendly nature of their employees, with the management focusing on the overall wellbeing of their employees. A company with a culture of hierarchy is viewed as having internal focus and favouring stability and control in times of change, with such a company typically emphasising formal policies and procedures. Companies that adopt a culture of adhocracy are known to promote flexibility, and they have an interest in changing their systems, although such changes are made with a focus on the external environment. Such organisations show a high degree of innovativeness and constantly focus on enacting changes based on their business environment in order to grow and become successful. Finally, companies that exhibit market culture also prefer stability and control because they are oriented towards external focus, emphasising competitiveness, and making major changes within a short period of time (Cameron & Quinn, 2011). No matter the culture a company wishes to adopt, all cultures are established and developed through diffusion, and all the cultures can be described as either strong or weak depending on how the said culture is deeply embraced by the members of an organization.

3.1.2. Connectedness

In the remote work setting, employees within the knowledge-intensive sector are empowered to undertake their designated tasks from any location, and they also have support for their roles and responsibilities. As the internet has penetrated vast areas of the world, coupled with sustainable means of electricity, the workplace has been broadened from exclusively homes and offices to also include other places like airports, hotels, customer sites, and cafes (Charalampous et al., 2019). On the same note, technology makes it possible for individuals to utilise their phones as hotspots, and this implies that any location where employees can access their cellular service could potentially be transformed into a work environment. Therefore, coworkers and teams that are no longer co-located are now empowered to communicate via different mobile platforms, and they are able to replicate the face-to-face communication obtainable in the office setting via video conferencing. However, findings have revealed that the spontaneous interactions obtainable in physical work settings are still missing in remote work settings (Tietze & Nadin, 2011). Due to these limited face-to-face interactions, employees in the remote work setting seem to focus on the external environment as a source of connection, which limits how connected they are to the company. Essentially, it

has a negative influence on their overall commitment and dedication to the company in the long run.

3.1.3. External social support

Similar to group cohesion and culture, social connectedness can be created on an organisational level or on an individual level, paving the way for one to develop a greater connection with a particular person (van Bel et al., 2009). Typically, full-time employees work about 48 hours per week, which allows them to spend about 8 hours per day with their co-workers. A great deal of time is allocated towards communicating and fostering memorable relationships. However, a different scenario exists among remote workers, as they engage with their fellow workers on a much more infrequent basis, especially when it comes to informal communication, as discussed earlier. Therefore, when employees working in remote and hybrid settings are not able to attain the desired level of connectedness within their workplace, they tend to source for such outside their workplace. This is where external social support comes into play, as it represents all other means of connectedness that employees can access outside their workplace. In recent times, employees have been known to attain this desirable means of connectedness via social media and other platforms. Accessing social support from external sources is a big challenge for corporations because it hinders the ability of a company to create a strong culture, as employees tend to value external sources and their cultures more than those of the company they work for. Inevitably, the implication is that they will tend to be less dedicated and committed to bringing about desired outcomes in the company.

3.2. How remote work influences organizational culture

Integral to every organisation is the need to align its efforts towards its goals. This is possible through organisational control mechanisms that are created to ensure efficient coordination among individuals to act in accordance with the objectives of the company. Since its appearance in the 1970s, there have been different arrangements created to provide a needed atmosphere for remote work, such as neighbourhood work centres, satellite work centres, work-at-home, and flexible work arrangements (Olson, 1983). Until recently, there have been diverse motives for remote work, which range from increased productivity and employee well-being (Choudhury, Foroughi, & Larson, 2021) to access to a larger pool of talent (Soroui, 2021) and the need to outsource practices (Feldman, 2006). However, with the advent of the COVID-19 pandemic, companies were forced within a short period of time to adopt remote work, and for the first few months of the pandemic, work-from-home was the predominant form of work across the globe (Banjo et al., 2020). Existing literature suggests that physically isolating employees or teams from their colleagues or other teams does have a negative influence on building a strong corporate culture. Per the findings of Grant, Wallace, and Spurgeon (2013), with the absence of physical interactions, remote workers tend to experience difficulties in nurturing trusting relationships with their colleagues, and this hinders the overall shared experience upon which they can base their corporate culture. For any innovative company, key activities like knowledge sharing seem to be predominantly

founded on culture, both at the individual level (Wang, Noe, & Wang, 2014) and corporate level (Ni et al., 2018), notwithstanding the assistance it gets from the latest technological advancements. Karatsivos and Nkandu (2022). As such, since remote work seems to hinder overall collaboration and the sharing of knowledge, based on the discussion above, the implication is that it will have a negative effect on the creation and sustenance of a strong corporate culture.

3.3. Implication for international business

Given the continued globalization and internationalization of firms, building a strong culture in an international corporation is already difficult and this issue is further raised by remote jobs (Thokozani & Maseko, 2017). Businesses that maintain operations across different markets are forced to “glocalize” their culture in order to adopt to the norms and values of the local cultures. Therefore, with remote work reducing or eliminating physical interactions in such companies, the overall ability of the company to build a strong culture will be further dwindled

(Grant et al., 2013). Thus, remote increases the already existing challenge of building strong culture in international business.

4. Conclusion

The importance of building a strong corporate culture can never be overemphasized. This is based on the understanding that it helps the company create sustainable performance while also averting issues related to employee turnover rates. However, creating such a culture would naturally require alignment and connectedness, two components that are lacking in remote and hybrid work settings. This is because findings indicate that in hybrid and remote work settings, there seems to be a lack of information, communication, and connectedness, and employees are forced to seek external sources of social cohesion. Essentially, integrating the company’s culture becomes difficult because these employees tend to value the connectedness they gain outside the company more than what they can obtain within the company. Therefore, considering that remote work settings have come to stay in today’s corporate world, there is an urgent need for organisations to develop the right strategy to ensure connectedness and alignment, which will pave the way for building a strong organisational culture. Per the work of Liu (2022), these strategies are: The cover story suggests three strategies to enhance connectedness among hybrid workers. Culture should be transferred through work itself. This can be done by the company auditing its processes to ensure that they are compatible with its culture. Once done, the culture should be instilled through daily tasks, with emphasis placed on the values that the employees will derive from the role they undertake and not the physical location where they are undertaking the said roles. Secondly, the teams should be empowered to set their own work rhythms, as this will enable them to envision how the culture can help them attain their set goals and become more aligned with the culture.

The second strategy is for the company to connect with the teams through their emotional proximity. This can be done by distinguishing the emotional and physical proximities of its workforce and ensuring that the emotional proximity is given more critical attention. Furthermore, toxic workers should be identified and removed, and the management must avoid inviting members that have no real value to contribute to any meetings. Finally, companies are encouraged to foster microculture. This will require them to shift from optimising corporate culture to focusing on fostering microculture. Additionally, they will need to favour more devolved control that will allow the local teams to gain more autonomy and direct action on issues that affect their performance. Such companies must also come to the understanding that team-level experiences increase connectedness more than initiatives that cut across the entire enterprise. It is expected that if these measures are integrated into a company that focuses more on remote work settings, the company will be better positioned to build a strong culture that will aid its overall attainment of set corporate objectives.

5. References

- Ahuja, M. K., & Galvin, J. E. (2003). Socialization in virtual groups. *Journal of Management*, 29(2), 161-185.
- Banjo, S. et al. (2020) Coronavirus Outbreak Is World's Largest Work-From-Home Experiment | Time, Time. Retrieved from: <https://time.com/5776660/coronavirus-work-from-home/>
- Cameron, K. S., & Quinn, R. E. (2011). *Diagnosing and changing organizational culture: Based on the competing values framework*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Charalampous, M., Grant, C. A., Tramontano, C., & Michailidis, E. (2019). Systematically reviewing remote e-workers' well-being at work: A multidimensional approach. *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology*, 28(1), 51-73.
- Choudhury, P. (Raj), Foroughi, C. and Larson, B. (2021) "Work-from-anywhere: The productivity effects of geographic flexibility," *Strategic Management Journal*, 42(4), pp. 655–683. doi:10.1002/smj.3251
- Eriksson, L., & Santesson, H. (2021). *Organizational Culture in a Remote Setting: A Qualitative Study on Organizational Culture and the Effects of Remote Work*.
- Feldman, D.C. (2006) "Toward a new taxonomy for understanding the nature and consequences of contingent employment," *Career Development International*, 11(1), pp. 28–47. doi:10.1108/13620430610642363.
- Grant, C.A., Wallace, L.M. and Spurgeon, P.C. (2013) "An exploration of the psychological factors affecting remote e-worker's job effectiveness, well-being and work-life balance," *Employee Relations*, 35(5), pp. 527–546. doi:10.1108/ER-08-2012-0059.

REVITALISING CORPORATE CULTURE IN THE WORLD OF HYBRID WORK

- Holmes, J., & Marra, M. (2004). Relational practice in the workplace: women's talk or gendered discourse?. *Language in society*, 377-398.
- Karatsivos, E and Nkandu, J. (2022). The effects of remote work on organizational culture and innovation. MBA Thesis. Retrieved from: <chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcgclefindmkaj/https://www.diva-portal.org/s mash/get/diva2:1679104/FULLTEXT02.pdf>
- Keyton J. (2011). *Communication and Organizational Culture: A Key to Understanding Work Experiences*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage. 2nd ed.
- Larson, B. Z., Vroman, S. R., & Makarius, E. E. (2020). A guide to managing your (newly) remote workers. *Harvard Business Review*, 18.
- Liu, S. (2022). Revitalizing Culture in the World of Hybrid Work. *Harvard Business Review*. Retrieved from: <https://hbr.org/2022/11/revitalizing-culture-in-the-world-of-hybrid-work>
- Masionis, A. (2022). Cultural alignment: How to align culture at your organization. Retrieved from: <https://www.achievers.com/blog/cultural-alignment/>
- Maslow, A. H. (1943). A theory of human motivation. *Psychological Review*, 50(4), 370-96.
- Ni, G. et al. (2018) “Knowledge-Sharing Culture, Project-Team Interaction, and Knowledge-Sharing Performance among Project Members,” *Journal of Management in Engineering*, 34(2), p. 04017065. doi:10.1061/(ASCE)ME.1943-5479.0000590.
- Olson, M.H. (1983) “Remote office work: changing work patterns in space and time,” *Communications of the ACM*, 26(3), pp. 182–187. doi:10.1145/358061.358068.
- Ozimek, A. (2020). The future of remote work. Available at SSRN 3638597.
- Ozimek, A. (2021). Future workforce report 2021: How Remote Work is Changing Businesses Forever. Upwork. Retrieved from <https://www.upwork.com/research/future-workforcereport>.
- Rai, A. (2020). Editor’s comments: The COVID-19 pandemic: Building resilience with IS research. *Management Information Systems Quarterly*, 44(2), iii-vii.
- Schein, E. H. (1985). *Organizational culture and leadership* San Francisco. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.
- Schein, E. H. (1990). Organizational culture (Vol. 45, No. 2, p. 109). American Psychological Association.
- Sewell, G., & Taskin, L. (2015). Out of sight, out of mind in a new world of work? Autonomy, control, and spatiotemporal scaling in telework. *Organization Studies*, 36(11), 1507-1529.

- Soroui, S.T. (2021) "Understanding the drivers and implications of remote work from the local perspective: An exploratory study into the dis/reembedding dynamics," *Technology in Society*, 64, p. 101328. doi:10.1016/j.techsoc.2020.101328.
- Thokozani, S. B. M., & Maseko, B. (2017). Strong vs. weak organizational culture: Assessing the impact on employee motivation. *Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review*, 7(1), 2-5.
- Tietze, S., & Nadin, S. (2011). The psychological contract and the transition from office-based to home-based work. *Human Resource Management Journal*, 21(3), 318-334.
- Tracy, K. (2002), *Everyday Talk*, The Guilford Press, New York, NY.
- Van Bel, D. T., Smolders, K. C. H. J., IJsselsteijn, W. A., & de Kort, Y. (2009). Social connectedness: concept and measurement. *Intelligent Environments*, 2, 67-74.
- van Zoonen, W., Sivunen, A., Blomqvist, K., Olsson, T., Ropponen, A., Henttonen, K., & Vartiainen, M. (2021). Factors influencing adjustment to remote work: Employees' initial responses to the covid-19 pandemic. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(13), 6966.
- Waldron, V. R. (2003). Relationship maintenance in organizational settings. *Maintaining relationships through communication: Relational, contextual, and cultural variations*, 163-184.
- Wang, S., Noe, R.A. and Wang, Z.M. (2014) "Motivating Knowledge Sharing in Knowledge Management Systems: A Quasi-Field Experiment," *Journal of Management*, 40(4), pp. 978–1009. doi:10.1177/0149206311412192.